

Orthogonal Graph Drawings: Algorithms and Lower Bounds

Diplomarbeit
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Chapter 1

Background

A *graph* is a structure commonly used for representing connections, communication, interference, etc. It consists of two finite sets, the *vertices* and the *edges*. An edge is a connection between two vertices, so it is a pair of vertices.

Figure 1.1: One example of a graph that arises when representing the connections in a recreational park. Gray lines are streets, black lines are the tracks of the tourist train.

There are various ways to represent a graph. For algorithms, one usually employs *incidence lists*: For every vertex v store a list $I(v)$ of its *incident* edges, i.e. the edges where an endpoint is v . Loops have two entries in the incidence list.

$$\begin{aligned} E &: (E, L), (E, R) \\ R &: (R, E), (R, L) \\ L &: (L, Z), (L, Z), (L, R), (L, E) \\ Z &: (Z, Z), (Z, Z), (L, Z), (L, Z) \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1.2: The graph of Figure 1.1, shown as incidence lists.

Obviously, a picture is easier to understand than a long list of lists. This leads to the question of obtaining “good” drawings of a graph. A precise definition of a drawing of a graph requires some topology. Since we do not want to confuse the reader with that, we rely on the reader’s intuition to understand the following properties of a graph drawing:

- vertices are drawn as points in \mathbb{R}^2 ,
- edges are drawn as lines in \mathbb{R}^2 , connecting the points of the vertices,
- no two vertices are drawn at the same point,
- outside of the endpoints, the drawing of an edge does not intersect the drawing of a vertex,
- outside of the endpoints, the drawing of an edge may cross the drawing of another edge, but they may neither touch nor overlap.

Once a drawing is given, vertices and edges are identified with their drawings, e.g. we say that “the edges e_1 and e_2 intersect” when in reality we mean “the drawing of edge e_1 intersects the drawing of edge e_2 ”.

In this thesis we concentrate on *orthogonal drawings* of graphs. Here we have the special requirement that the drawing of an edge is a sequence of horizontal and vertical lines.

Figure 1.3: The graph of Figure 1.1 drawn orthogonally.

The interest in these drawings originally came from chip-design, where orthogonality was a technology requirement. Various algorithms have been developed (see [Len] for an overview). However, they do not concentrate on the aesthetic quality of the drawing, which is our main goal. Therefore, we do not present them here.

“Nice” orthogonal drawings are of interest since some diagrams (e.g. Entity Relationship diagrams for databases) are drawn with this standard. Also, the minimum angle in the drawing is at least 90° , and a large minimum angle is considered advantageous for the intuitive understanding of a picture.

A drawback of orthogonal drawings is that every vertex can have at most four incident edges (graphs that fulfill this are called *4-graphs*). For practical applications, this dilemma is resolved by drawing vertices as a box with larger area, or by splitting the vertex into a chain of vertices, which is drawn as a straight line (see for example visibility representations [RT, TT86]). For our purposes we always assume that the given graph is a 4-graph.

The main objective is to obtain a “nice” orthogonal drawing. Since being nice is not well-defined, we now explain the criteria used to judge a drawing. The place where the drawing of an edge changes its direction is called a *bend* of this edge.

- **Grid-size:** To ensure a minimum distance between vertices and edges, we assume that all vertices and all bends are at points with integer coordinates. The drawing is then an embedding of the graph in the (2-dimensional) grid. If the drawing can be enclosed by a quadrangle of *width* n_1 and *height* n_2 , we call it a drawing with *grid-size* $n_1 \times n_2$.

Minimizing both width and height is important to keep the picture small. If width and height cannot be computed individually, we also consider the *area* $n_1 \cdot n_2$, and the *half-perimeter* $n_1 + n_2$.

- **Bends:** Every bend needs one grid-point. Intuitively a drawing with many bends has a larger grid-size, and this is undesirable. Also, every bend makes it harder to follow the course of the drawing of an edge. For this reason we want to keep both the total number of bends and the number of bends per edge small. An edge is called *k-bent* if its drawing has at most k bends.
- **Crossings:** Every crossing bears potential for confusion of the two crossing edges. So crossings should be avoided, if possible. In particular, if the graph can be drawn without any crossings at all (i.e., it is *planar*), then the drawing should be planar as well.

Every 4-graph has an orthogonal drawing. E.g., we can place all vertices on one row with their edges looking “upward”. By adding a row for each edge we can connect the two endpoints of this edge. This gives an orthogonal drawing, but the grid is large and we have many bends and crossings.

Figure 1.4: Any 4-graph has an orthogonal drawing.

Unfortunately the problem of minimizing the number of bends is \mathcal{NP} -complete [GT], and so is the question whether a graph can be embedded in a grid of prescribed size [KvL, FW]. The problem of minimizing the number of crossings is \mathcal{NP} -complete as well [GJ]. Therefore it is of interest to find heuristics that obtain provably good bounds. In order to measure their quality, one wants to have lower bounds, i.e. graphs that need a certain number of bends or a certain grid-size in any drawing.

We do not try to give a complete review of all known heuristics here, this is beyond the scope of a diploma thesis (see [BETT] and [Ta89] for reviews). Instead, we do the following:

- We present algorithms for various classes of graphs:
 - We show a heuristic for biconnected graphs. It is simple and bounds on the grid-size and the number of bends are achieved easily.
 - We describe a scheme how an algorithm for biconnected graphs can be used to obtain drawings of non-biconnected graphs. The demands posed on the algorithm for biconnected graphs are fairly small; and are fulfilled by the above mentioned heuristic.
 - We apply both the heuristic and the merging scheme to various classes of graphs (non-planar, planar, and plane graphs; simple graphs and non-simple graphs). We describe the changes necessary for each class and compute worst-case bounds.

The main goal in the descriptions of these heuristics is to give the ideas and to prove worst-case bounds, not to give a ready-to-implement algorithm. For an actual implementation there are many more issues to consider than can be treated in this diploma thesis. Quite often the drawings can be improved with a few simple changes, even though nothing has yet been shown about a theoretical better quality.

For the same reason we do not deal with issues of time complexity. The heuristics do perform well ($\mathcal{O}(n)$ for the planar case, $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$ for the non-planar case), but what would be really interesting is the time complexity of an implementation incorporating the above mentioned improvements. This has to be left for further study.

- We develop various new lower bounds. These are very close to optimal for planar graphs where the drawing is fixed. They are also near optimal for the number of bends in the other cases, while finding good lower bounds on the grid-size still remains an open problem.
- We come back to two algorithms of the literature [Ta87, Ka], since we managed to find a new respectively better bound than given there.

See Chapter 5 for a complete tabular overview of the results obtained in this thesis.

As usual in introductions there are some people that I want to mention. I owe much to my advisers, Prof. Möhring from TU Berlin, and Prof. Boros from Rutgers University. Also, part of this thesis was written while the author was working at Tom Sawyer Software, and permission and support to do so is gratefully acknowledged. Many thanks also to all the others who through their listening to and discussing mathematical and language questions helped to bring this thesis into shape. Particularly I want to name Ondřej Čepek, Uğur Doğrusöz, Goos Kant, Alexander Lawrenz, Brendan Madden, Dale Peterson, David Rader, and Reuben Settergren.

Chapter 2

Framework

In this chapter we describe some basic framework. After giving definitions, we present a heuristic for biconnected graphs. Then we describe a merging scheme that enables us to draw non-biconnected graphs. Finally, we provide some techniques for lower bounds.

2.1 Definitions

Assume a graph G is given. Denote its vertices by $V(G)$ and its edges by $E(G)$. Let $n(G)$ and $m(G)$ be the number of vertices and edges. If the graph in question is clear, we use V, E, n , and m , respectively.

If an edge e connects the two vertices v and w , then e is written as $e = (v, w)$, and v and w are called the *endpoints* of e . We say that v and w are *adjacent* or *neighbors*. The vertex v and the edge e are said to be *incident* to each other.

Edges of the form (v, v) are not necessarily forbidden; such edges are called *loops*. Also, two vertices may be connected by more than one edge; such edges are called *multiple edges*. Graphs without loops and multiple edges are called *simple graphs*. Graphs without loops are called *multi-graphs*. If G is not simple, and G' is the graph resulting from deleting all loops and multiple edges, then G' is called the *underlying simple graph* of G .

The number of edges incident to a vertex v is called the *degree* of v and denoted by $deg(v)$. Loops count twice to the degree of the incident vertex. A simple counting argument gives $\sum_{v \in V} deg(v) = 2m$.

The *complete graph* K_n is a simple graph with n vertices in which any pair of different vertices is connected with an edge.

A *path* in G is a sequence of vertices u_1, u_2, \dots, u_l , such that $(u_i, u_{i+1}) \in E$ for all $i = 1, \dots, l-1$. G is called *connected* if for any two vertices v and w there exists a path containing both v and w .

Definition 1 For a connected graph G and some $k \geq 1$, a k -separation is a partition of G into two graphs $G_1 = (V_1, E_1)$ and $G_2 = (V_2, E_2)$, such that $|V_1 \cap V_2| = k$, $|E_1 \cap E_2| = 0$; and $|E_i| \geq k$ for $i = 1, 2$. So that means that G_i either contains a cycle, or a vertex not in $V_1 \cap V_2$.

A graph is called k -connected if it has no l -separation for $1 \leq l < k$. We will only consider the cases $k = 2, 3$. A 2-connected graph is also called biconnected, a 3-connected graph is also called triconnected.

This definition can be reformulated as “a biconnected graph has no loop and removing a vertex leaves a connected graph” respectively “a triconnected graph is simple, and removing two vertices leaves a connected graph.”

Remark: In most textbooks on graph theory, the condition on a k -connected graph is slightly weaker. Namely, for a k -separation, the condition $|E_i| \geq k$ is replaced by $|V_i| > k$, $i = 1, 2$. This means that loops and multiple edges are allowed for biconnected and triconnected graphs.

Definition 1 is motivated for planar graphs, since then the dual graph is k -connected if and only if the original graph is k -connected (see [Tru]). The reason why we prefer it lies in that otherwise we would have to do even more case analysis. For example, every biconnected graph without loops can be embedded with $2n + 4$ bends (Theorem 3.1). But the graph consisting of an n -cycle and a loop attached to each vertex needs $3n$ bends in any drawing (Theorem 3.10). This graph would be biconnected in the weaker sense, and therefore we prefer the stronger definition.

Assume we have an orthogonal drawing. When speaking of the *grid*, we mean the collection of rows and columns. We consider the rows to be ordered from bottom to top and the columns to be sorted from left to right. Then we can write $r_1 < r_2$ if the row r_1 is below the row r_2 . We also write $r_1 + 1$ for the row directly above the row r_1 , and $r_1 - 1$ for the row directly below the row r_1 . The terms are similarly defined for the columns.

A grid-point is described in terms of its column and its row as (c, r) . We only compute those grid-point coordinates. The conversion to x - and y -coordinates happens after the algorithm is finished by means of assigning consecutive numbers to the rows and columns.

The four grid-segments adjacent to a grid-point are called *connections* of the grid-point and denoted according to their direction as *top*, *bottom*, *right*, and *left*. A column (row) of the drawing is called *edge-used* if it contains a vertical (horizontal) part of an edge, *vertex-used* if it contains a vertex, and *used* if it is vertex-used or edge-used or both.

We assume that all unused columns and rows are deleted before computing the final coordinates. Then the width (height) is one less than the number of used columns (rows).

2.2 Heuristic for biconnected graphs

Assume we are given a biconnected graph $G = (V, E)$. It is fairly easy to draw G , since we have the following powerful tool for biconnected graphs.

Definition 2 An ordering $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ of the vertices is called an *st-ordering* if for every $1 < j < n$ there exist indices i, k , $i < j < k$ such that (v_i, v_j) , $(v_j, v_k) \in E$.

The first vertex is usually denoted s , and the last vertex is usually denoted t , hence the name *st-ordering*.

Once an *st-ordering* is given, we consider the edges to be directed from the lower-numbered to the higher-numbered vertex (since we have no loops in a biconnected graph, this is well-defined).

The number of incoming (outgoing) edges of v is called the *indegree* (*outdegree*) of v and denoted $indeg(v)$ ($outdeg(v)$). Definition 2 can then be reformulated as “every vertex v_i , $i \neq 1$ has $indeg(v_i) > 0$; and every vertex v_i , $i \neq n$ has $outdeg(v_i) > 0$.”

Every edge contributes to the indegree of exactly one vertex and to an outdegree of exactly one vertex. Hence $m = \sum_{v \in V} indeg(v) = \sum_{v \in V} outdeg(v)$. Call a neighbor of v_j a *predecessor* (*successor*) of v_j if it is the other endpoint of an incoming (outgoing) edge.

The existence of an *st-ordering* for a biconnected graph has been shown by Lempel, Even and Cederbaum [LEC]. They also showed that it is possible to specify which vertex should be s and which should be t .

The *st-ordering* is the crucial idea behind the heuristic for biconnected graphs, which first has been described in [B]. Assume we are given a biconnected 4-graph G . The idea is to embed the vertices consecutively according to an *st-ordering* $\{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$, upholding the following invariant.

Invariant 1 Assume that $\{v_1, \dots, v_k\}$ are drawn, for some $1 \leq k \leq n$. Then, all edges (v_i, v_j) with $i, j \leq k$ are completely drawn. An edge of the form $e = (v_j, v_l)$ with $j \leq k < l$ is drawn up to a certain point, its temporary endpoint (c_e, r_e) . The column of the endpoint is empty above the endpoint, i.e. no grid-point in $\{(c_e, r), r > r_e\}$ is used by a vertex or a bend.

We draw the first vertex as shown in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Embedding of the first vertex for various degrees.

To embed v_k , $k \geq 2$, we distinguish cases by the indegree of v_k . We maintain the invariant by adding as many new columns as necessary. The procedure is demonstrated for a vertex of degree 4 in Figure 2.2 and also described in formulas in algorithm BICONN in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.2: Embedding v ($\text{indeg}(v) = 1, 2, 3, 4$).

Algorithm BICONN

- (1) Choose two vertices s and t .
- (2) Compute an st -ordering $\{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$, where $v_1 = s$ and $v_n = t$.
- (3) Embed v_1 as shown in Figure 2.1.
- (4) **for** $k = 2, \dots, n$, embed v_k as follows:
 - (a) Let $i = \text{indeg}(v_k)$, we know $i > 0$.
 - (b) Find the columns c_1, \dots, c_i of the temporary endpoints of the incoming edges.
 - (c) Sort the columns so that $c_1 < \dots < c_i$, and set $c(v_k) = c_{\lceil \frac{i}{2} \rceil}$.
 - (d) Find the row $r(v_k)$ of v_k as follows:
 - (i) Add a new row on top of all previous rows and assign it to v_k .
 - (ii) **if** $\text{indeg}(v_k) = 4$, add another row on top of all previous rows.
 - (e) Draw the incoming edges of v_k as follows:

for $j = 1, \dots, i$ connect the temporary endpoint (c_j, r_j) with v_k as shown in Figure 2.2.
 - (f) Draw the outgoing edges of v_k as follows:
 - (i) **if** $\text{outdeg}(v_k) \geq 2$:
Add a new column between $c(v_k)$ and $c(v_k) + 1$. Connect v_k with this column.
 - (ii) **if** $\text{outdeg}(v_k) = 3$:
Add a new column between $c(v_k)$ and $c(v_k) - 1$. Connect v_k with this column.
 - (iii) Assign the temporary endpoints of outgoing edges to $c(v_k)$ and the new columns.

Figure 2.3: The algorithm for biconnected graphs.

Remark: For the algorithm, we have used that every vertex has a predecessor, but we have not yet exploited that every vertex has a successor. In fact, this heuristic works for any ordering of the vertices where $\text{indeg}(v) > 0$ for all $v \neq v_1$.

One sees that BICONN leaves parameters to be determined. Some of those will be exploited in later specifications, for example in order to get planar drawings. Others have no effect on planarity and grid-size. Nevertheless, these are very interesting factors for determining a “better” drawing and deserve further study. Some of them are the following:

- How should we choose s and t in Step (1) of BICONN? This will be exploited in the merging scheme for non-biconnected graphs. It is also very important for planar graphs, since only with a suitable choice of s and t is the drawing planar.
- How to embed v_k in Steps (3) and (4c)? In Step (4c), we could place v_k at $c_{\lceil \frac{i+1}{2} \rceil}$, which gives a reflected drawing in the cases $\text{indeg}(v_k) = 2, 4$. Similarly, in Step (3) we could as well take a symmetric drawing. Even though this does not affect the grid-size or the number of bends, it very well affects the quality of the final drawing.
- Which st -ordering should be chosen in (2)? This is a very interesting subject, but not much is known about it. A graph usually has many different st -orderings, even when s and t are fixed. Each of them gives a different picture, but we have not found a paradigm how to choose among the possible orderings.
- Can rows and columns be reused? In Step (d) respectively (f i) and (f ii) we always added a new row/column for reasons of simplicity. However, quite often there are some older rows and columns which could be used. A test whether this is possible should be incorporated into any implementation. First results showing better worst-case bounds have been given by Papakostas and Tollis (see Theorem 3.3).
- Which edge should be assigned to which temporary endpoint in Step (f iii)? This is a very important point. For planar graphs we have no freedom if we want to obtain a planar drawing. For non-planar graphs the number of crossings produced depends on this choice.
- Where should new columns be added? We added new columns directly neighbored to v_k . For planar drawings, this is necessary in order to avoid crossings. For non-planar drawings, sometimes we would get less crossings when adding the column at a different place.
- Where should new rows be added? For simplicity, we always added new rows on top of the drawing. However, quite often crossings can be avoided by adding the new row above the highest row of the temporary endpoints of incoming edges. On the other hand, we will need that v_n is placed in the highest row for graphs that are not biconnected.

The fact that we have an st -ordering is important for good estimations on the grid-size and the number of bends. For an easier formulation of different cases we define the following.

Definition 3 The characteristic function $\chi(\dots)$ is a function which is 1 whenever what is inside the parenthesis is true, and 0 otherwise.

Lemma 2.2.1 *The width is $m - n + 1$, the height is $n - 1 + \chi(\deg(v_1) = 4) + \chi(\deg(v_n) = 4)$.*

Proof: When embedding $v_i \neq v_1, v_n$ we have $1 \leq \text{outdeg}(v_i) \leq 3$, since we have an *st*-ordering. As one checks easily case by case, we increase the number of columns by $\text{outdeg}(v_i) - 1$. v_1 uses $\text{outdeg}(v_1)$ new columns. v_n uses no new column, and $\text{outdeg}(v_n) = 0$. So the number of columns is

$$\text{outdeg}(v_1) + \text{outdeg}(v_n) + \sum_{v \neq v_1, v_n} (\text{outdeg}(v) - 1) = \sum_{v \in V} (\text{outdeg}(v) - 1) + 2 = m - n + 2.$$

Every vertex $\neq v_1, v_n$ has $\text{indeg}(v_i) \leq 3$ and $\text{outdeg}(v_i) \leq 3$, and increases the number of rows by 1. v_1 and v_n each need two rows if they have degree 4, and one row otherwise. So the number of rows is $n + \chi(\deg(v_1) = 4) + \chi(\deg(v_n) = 4)$.

The proof now is finished since the width (height) is one less than the number of used columns (rows). \square

Lemma 2.2.2 *There are $2m - 2n + 2 + \chi(\deg(v_1) = 4) + \chi(\deg(v_n) = 4)$ bends.*

Proof: Every $v_i \neq v_1, v_n$ has $1 \leq \text{indeg}(v_i) \leq 3$ and $1 \leq \text{outdeg}(v_i) \leq 3$, since we have an *st*-ordering. Again case by case one checks that there are $\text{indeg}(v_i) - 1$ and $\text{outdeg}(v_i) - 1$, hence $\text{deg}(v_i) - 2$ new bends. Embedding $v = v_1, v_n$ gives $\text{deg}(v)$ bends if $\text{deg}(v) = 4$ and $\text{deg}(v) - 1$ bends otherwise. Hence the number of bends is

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{deg}(v_1) - 1 + \chi(\text{deg}(v_1) = 4) + \text{deg}(v_n) - 1 + \chi(\text{deg}(v_n) = 4) + \sum_{v \neq v_1, v_n} (\text{deg}(v) - 2) \\ &= \sum_{v \in V} (\text{deg}(v) - 2) + 2 + \chi(\text{deg}(v_1) = 4) + \chi(\text{deg}(v_n) = 4) \\ &= 2m - 2n + 2 + \chi(\text{deg}(v_1) = 4) + \chi(\text{deg}(v_n) = 4) \end{aligned}$$

\square

Lemma 2.2.3 *All but at most two edges are 2-bent. The two exceptions are the edge at the bottom connection of v_1 , which exists only if $\deg(v_1) = 4$; and the edge at the top connection of v_n , which exists only if $\deg(v_n) = 4$.*

Proof: Assume we have an edge $e = (v_i, v_j)$ with $i < j$. We consider the number of bends at e when embedding either endpoint.

If $\text{outdeg}(v_i) \leq 3$, then e gets at most one bend at v_i . If $\text{indeg}(v_j) \leq 3$, then e gets at most one bend at v_j . So the only way e could have more than two bends is that either $\text{outdeg}(v_i) = 4$ or $\text{indeg}(v_j) = 4$.

This can happen only if $i = 1$ and $\text{deg}(v_1) = 4$; or if $j = n$ and $\text{deg}(v_n) = 4$. Moreover, it can happen only to the edge at the bottom connection of v_1 , since only this edge gets two bends at v_1 ; or to the edge at the top connection v_n , since only this edge gets two bends at v_n . \square

2.3 Merging scheme for not biconnected graphs

Assume G is a 4-graph that is connected, but not biconnected. The idea for drawing G is to split it into its biconnected components, to embed them, and then to merge them into one drawing. We need some definitions for this.

Remember that a graph is biconnected if it has no 1-separation (see Definition 1 on Page 6). So if a graph is connected, but not biconnected, it must have a 1-separation. The unique vertex v in $V_1 \cap V_2$ is called a *cutvertex*. One sees easily that either v is incident to a loop, or that after removing v the graph is not connected anymore.

The biconnected components are obtained as follows: take the two subgraphs G_1 and G_2 that defined the 1-separation. If one of them, say G_1 , is not biconnected and not a loop, then find a 1-separation of G_1 with the graphs G_{11} and G_{12} . Iterate this, until all so obtained subgraphs are biconnected or loops. These graphs are the *blocks* of G . If v is not a cutvertex, then it belongs to exactly one block. If v is a cutvertex, it belongs to at least two blocks.

With the blocks we associate a graph \mathcal{B} , the *blocktree*. \mathcal{B} has one vertex for every block, and one vertex for every cutvertex. Two vertices of \mathcal{B} are adjacent if and only if one is a cutvertex that belongs to the block represented by the other. \mathcal{B} is a *tree*, which means that it is connected and $m(\mathcal{B}) = n(\mathcal{B}) - 1$.

We assign one block B_0 to be the *root* of \mathcal{B} . If v is a cutvertex contained in B_0 , and B_1 is another block containing v , then B_1 is called a *child-block* of B_0 . v is called the *parent-vertex* ($parent(B_1)$) of B_1 .

If in \mathcal{B} we remove $parent(B_1)$, then we obtain some number of subtrees. The one that contains B_1 is called the *subtree of \mathcal{B} rooted at B_1* , and denoted $\mathcal{B}(B_1)$. The graph represented by $\mathcal{B}(B_1)$ is denoted $G(\mathcal{B}(B_1))$. Since we have a 4-graph, and since $parent(B_1)$ must have incident edges in B_0 , $parent(B_1)$ has degree at most 3 in $G(\mathcal{B}(B_1))$.

Consider B_1 to be the root of $\mathcal{B}(B_1)$ and iterate the definition of parent-vertex and child-blocks in $\mathcal{B}(B_1)$. After this procedure is finished, every block except the root has a unique parent-vertex.

Figure 2.4: Splitting G into its blocks. B_0 is the root of the blocktree, and B_1 and B_2 are its child-blocks. v_i is the parent-vertex of B_i ($i = 1, 2$).

Some blocks have degree 1 in \mathcal{B} , these blocks are called *leaves* of \mathcal{B} . A leaf contains exactly one cutvertex. If the graph is not biconnected, then we have at least two leaves in the blocktree.

We now describe the merging scheme, which has been used in [B] and [BK] without being given abstractly. The idea is to embed the blocks and merge them into each other. More precisely, we first embed the leaves of the blocktree, and then recursively build up the subtrees of \mathcal{B} . To allow for merging, we put a special condition on the drawing of the parent-vertex of the root of each subtree.

Definition 4 Let Γ be a drawing of G . Let v be a vertex of G with $\deg(v) \leq 3$, drawn in row $r(v)$ and column $c(v)$. We say that v is drawn as final vertex in Γ , if the grid-points in S are unused, where S is defined as follows:

- if $\deg(v) = 1$, then $S = \{(c, r), r \geq r(v)\} - \{(c_v, r_v)\}$,
- if $\deg(v) = 2$, then $S = \{(c, r), c \geq c(v), r \geq r(v)\} - \{(c_v, r_v)\}$,
- if $\deg(v) = 3$, then $S = \{(c, r), c = c(v), r > r(v)\}$.

So this means that the column of v is unused above v , for $\deg(v) \leq 2$ that the row of v and every row above it is unused to the right of v , and for $\deg(v) = 1$ that v is drawn in the last row which is unused to either side. See also Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5: Drawing a vertex of degree 1,2,3 as final vertex.

Directly case by case one checks:

Lemma 2.3.1 *BICONN* draws v_n as final vertex, if $\deg(v_n) \leq 3$.

The following lemma is quite trivial. However, the important part is the algorithm described in the proof.

Lemma 2.3.2 Assume we have an algorithm to draw any biconnected graph with one prespecified vertex w , $\deg(w) \leq 3$, as final vertex. Then any connected graph G can be drawn with a prespecified vertex v , $\deg(v) \leq 3$ as final vertex.

Proof: Compute the blocktree \mathcal{B} of G and root it at a block containing v . We prove the claim by induction on the number of cutvertices. The base case is the case of a biconnected graph, which by the assumption is trivial. The inductive step falls into two cases:

Case 1: G contains a bridge:

A *bridge* is an edge whose removal splits G into two graphs, each containing at least one edge. Each endpoint of the bridge is a cutvertex, and the bridge is a block B of G . Let v_1 be the parent-vertex of B , and let v_2 be the other endpoint of the bridge.

Removing the bridge from G we get two subgraphs, G_1 and G_2 . Since v was part of the root of \mathcal{B} , G_1 contains v_1 . G_2 is $G(\mathcal{B}(B))$ with the bridge removed.

v_2 does not belong to G_1 , so G_1 has at least one cutvertex less than G . We can apply induction and embed G_1 with v as final vertex. In this drawing v_1 has a connection in one direction free, assume it is to the left. (If the direction to the left is occupied, take the one to the right. If that one is occupied, take the one to the bottom. Only if no other is free, take the one to the top.)

v_1 does not belong to G_2 , so G_2 has at least one cutvertex less than G . We can apply induction and embed G_2 with v_2 as final vertex. By adding rows and columns to the left of the drawing of v_1 and rotating the drawing of G_2 , we can merge it into the drawing. This is possible since v_2 was drawn as final vertex in G_2 and $\deg_{G_2}(v_2) \leq 3$. See also Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6: How to merge a subgraph connected by a bridge.

Case 2: G contains no bridge:

Every cutvertex of degree ≤ 3 is incident to a bridge. Since we have no bridge, every cutvertex has degree 4 (in particular v is no cutvertex, since $\deg(v) \leq 3$). Also, every cutvertex belongs to exactly two blocks.

We are not in the base case, so G must contain a cutvertex v_1 . We have no bridge, so $v_1 \neq v$. This cutvertex splits the blocktree into two trees. Let the graphs represented by these subtrees be G_1 and G_2 . Assume that G_1 contains v , and by induction embed it with v as final vertex.

Embed G_2 with v_1 as final vertex. v_1 must have at least two neighbors in G_2 , otherwise we had a bridge. But it also must have at least two neighbors in G_1 , for the same reason. So it has two neighbors in each of G_1 and G_2 .

In G_2 , the two incident edges of v_1 are drawn with right angle, with the definition of a final vertex. If the two incident edges of v_1 in G_1 are likewise drawn with a right angle, then a merging of G_2 is possible as shown in Figure 2.7, after adding a suitable amount of rows and columns.

Figure 2.7: Cutting G_1 and merging G_2 if v_1 is drawn with right angle.

Otherwise the two incident edges are drawn to opposite directions, and we say that v_1 is drawn *straight* in G_1 . Assume the two connections are *top* and *bottom*. By cutting the drawing and adding one column and a bend, we can achieve that the vertex is drawn with right angle, see Figure 2.8. After doing this we merge G_2 as above. We have two possible placements of v_1 , and depending on this we add G_2 “to the right” or “to the left” of v_1 .

We have to ensure that v is still drawn as final vertex after we merged G_2 . This is a rather nasty case analysis, where we distinguish cases by the placement of v_1 . Let $r(v)$ be the row and $c(v)$ be the column of v . Let $r(v_1)$ be the row and $c(v_1)$ be the column of v_1 .

Figure 2.8: Convert a straight drawing into one with a right angle.

The crucial observation is that all new rows for the merging are added between $r(v_1) - 1$ and $r(v_1) + 1$ (where the “+1” and “-1” operations are taken in the drawing of G_1). Similar, all new columns are added between $c(v_1) - 1$ and $c(v_1) + 1$. Furthermore, if c is a newly added column, then no grid-point (c, r) with $r \geq r(v_1) + 1$ or $r \leq r(v_1) - 1$ is used by a vertex or a bend in the merged drawing (similar for the newly added rows).

1. $r(v_1) < r(v)$:

All newly added rows are smaller than $r(v_1) + 1 \leq r(v)$. Also, all newly added columns are empty in and above $r(v)$. Consequently, no new vertex or bend is added in a place (c, r) with $r \geq r(v)$, and v is still drawn as final vertex.

(1)

Figure 2.9: The case $r(v_1) < r(v)$.

2. $r(v_1) \geq r(v)$:

We distinguish cases by the column of v_1 .

(a) $c(v_1) < c(v)$:

This condition implies that before the merging $\deg(v) \geq 2$, since v was drawn as final vertex. All new columns are smaller than $c(v_1) + 1 \leq c(v)$. Also, all newly added rows are empty in and to the right of $c(v)$. Consequently, no new vertex is added into a place (c, r) with $c \geq c(v)$ and $r \geq r(v)$ and v is still drawn as final vertex.

(b) $c(v_1) > c(v)$:

This condition implies that before the merging $\deg(v) \geq 3$, since v was drawn as final vertex. All new columns are greater than $c(v_1) - 1 \geq c(v)$. Also, all new rows are empty in and to the left of $c(v)$. Consequently, no new vertex or bend is added into a place (c, r) with $c = c(v)$ and v is still drawn as final vertex.

Figure 2.10: The cases $r(v_1) > r(v)$, and either $c(v_1) < c(v)$, or $c(v_1) > c(v)$.

(c) $c(v_1) = c(v)$:

Since v was drawn as final vertex, the column above it was empty. Since $r(v_1) \geq r(v)$, this implies $v = v_1$. We distinguish cases by the degree d of v before the merging. Since v was final vertex, we had $\deg(v) \leq 3$ after the merging, so before the merging the degree was either 1 or 2.

i. $d = 1$:

v is the endpoint of a bridge in G_1 . In the algorithm, we first removed all subgraphs connected by a bridge. So v must also be endpoint of a bridge in G_2 . Since v was drawn as final vertex, the connection to the left is free. By the order in which we tried the connections, we use this one. So all new columns are added to the left of $c(v)$, and all new rows are empty in and to the right of $c(v)$. So if we have a point (c, r) with $c \geq c(v)$ and $r \geq r(v)$, then either $(c, r) = (c(v), r(v))$, or the point is unused. Since now $\deg(v) = 2$, this means that v is drawn as final vertex.

ii. $d = 2$:

Since $\deg(v) \leq 3$, v must be endpoint of a bridge in the other graph. v was drawn as final vertex, so the connection to the right is free. So no new vertex or bend is added into the column of v , and v is drawn as final vertex afterwards. \square

Figure 2.11: The cases $v_1 = v$, and either $\deg_{G_1}(v) = 1$ or $\deg_{G_1}(v) = 2$.

In Figure 2.12 we give a detailed description of the algorithm CONN inherent in this proof. We choose the bridges and cutvertices such that we quickly isolate one biconnected component. This will be useful for estimations later.

Algorithm CONN

- I Split G into its blocktree \mathcal{B} .
- II Choose the root B_0 of \mathcal{B} .
- III Call EMBED-SUBTREE with B_0 .

Algorithm EMBED-SUBTREE

Input: A block B of the graph. Possibly a vertex v with $\deg_{G(\mathcal{B}(B))}(v) \leq 3$.

Output: A drawing of $G(\mathcal{B}(B))$, with v as final vertex if it is given.

- (1) Treat all bridges of $G(\mathcal{B}(B))$ at B as follows:
 - (a) Set $b = 0$.
 - (b) **while** $G(\mathcal{B}(B))$ has a bridge with one endpoint in B :
 - (i) Set $b = b + 1$.
 - (ii) Let B_{i_b} be the block of this bridge. Let v_{i_b} be the endpoint of the bridge in B .
 - (iii) Call EMBED-SUBTREE with B_{i_b} and v_{i_b} .
 - (iv) Delete $G(\mathcal{B}(B_{i_b}))$ from $G(\mathcal{B}(B))$.
- (2) Treat all cutvertices of $G(\mathcal{B}(B))$ in B as follows:
 - (a) Set $c = 0$.
 - (b) **while** $G(\mathcal{B}(B))$ has a cutvertex in B :
 - (i) Set $c = c + 1$.
 - (ii) Let v_{j_c} be the cutvertex in B . Let B_{j_c} be the (unique) other block containing v_{j_c} .
 - (iii) Call EMBED-SUBTREE with B_{j_c} and v_{j_c} .
 - (iv) Delete $G(\mathcal{B}(B_{j_c}))$ from $G(\mathcal{B}(B))$.
- (3) Now $G(\mathcal{B}(B))$ is biconnected. Embed it using the algorithm for biconnected graphs, with v as last vertex if it is given.
- (4) **for** $l = c, \dots, 1$
 - (a) Assume the drawing of $G_{j_l} = G(\mathcal{B}(B_{j_l}))$ obtained in (2iii) has size $w_{j_l} \times h_{j_l}$.
 - (b) **if** v_{j_l} is drawn straight in the drawing of B ,
 - add a column and change the drawing as shown in Figure 2.8.
 - (c) Add w_{j_l} columns and h_{j_l} rows, and merge v_{j_l} as shown in Figure 2.7.
- (5) **for** $l = b, \dots, 1$:
 - (a) Assume the drawing of $G_{i_l} = G(\mathcal{B}(B_{i_l}))$ obtained in (1iii) has size $w_{i_l} \times h_{i_l}$.
 - (b) Take the first possible connection at v_{i_l} in the drawing of B ,
 - in order left, right, bottom, and top connection.
 - (c) **if** the chosen connection is left or right:
 - (i) Add h_{i_l} columns and w_{i_l} rows.
 - (ii) Rotate the drawing of G_{i_l} and merge it as shown in Figure 2.6.
 - (d) **else**
 - (i) Add w_{i_l} columns and h_{i_l} rows.
 - (ii) Merge the drawing of G_{i_l} similar as in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.12: The algorithm for non-biconnected graphs.

The obtained grid-size and number of bends depend on the grid-size and number of bends given by the algorithm for biconnected graphs. We now give a “formula” for computing this relationship.

Definition 5 *A critical cutvertex of a block B is a cutvertex of G in B that is not $\text{parent}(B)$, and that is not incident to a bridge. In other words, a critical cutvertex is a cutvertex encountered in Step (2) of CONN. The number of critical cutvertices in B is denoted $\text{cr}(B)$.*

For a critical cutvertex v it is important how it is embedded in B . If v is drawn straight, then we have to add units of width or height, and a bend, to merge the subgraph of the (unique) other block containing v .

Definition 6 *Call a drawing of a block B a proper drawing, if all critical cutvertices are drawn in such a way that no increase is necessary to merge the subgraphs.*

In particular, in a proper drawing all critical cutvertices are drawn with right angle, but more conditions will be put on this when we apply the merging scheme.

Definition 7 *The correction terms Φ_w, Φ_h and Φ_b are functions on the blocks of G , such that a block B has a proper drawing of width $n(B) - 1 + \Phi_w(B)$, height $n(B) - 1 + \Phi_h(B)$, and with $2n(B) - 1 - \text{cr}(B) + \Phi_b(B)$ bends.*

It is easier to deal with bridges separately in each application, so we here analyze only the case of graphs without bridges. In the following we use the notation $\sum_{B \in G}$ which means that we sum over all blocks of G . Sometimes we denote $\Phi.(B)$ to mean either of the three functions.

Lemma 2.3.3 *Assume G has no bridges. The drawing of CONN has*

- width $n(G) - 1 + \sum_{B \in G} \Phi_w(B)$,
- height $n(G) - 1 + \sum_{B \in G} \Phi_h(B)$, and
- $2n(G) - 1 + \sum_{B \in G} \Phi_b(B)$ bends.

Proof: Assume first that G is biconnected. Then G itself is one block, so $\sum_{B \in G} \Phi.(B) = \Phi.(G)$. The claim is true by the definition of the correction terms, and since $\text{cr}(G) = 0$.

Consider the case when G is not biconnected, i.e. we remove some parts of G before drawing it. Since we have no bridge, this happens only in Step (2) of CONN. If B is a block in G , then it is either the block remaining in Step (3) (call it B_0). Or B is part of one of the subgraphs G_{j_l} , $l = 1, \dots, \text{cr}$. So

$$\sum_{B \in G} \Phi.(B) = \Phi.(B_0) + \sum_{l=1}^{\text{cr}} \sum_{B \in G_{j_l}} \Phi.(B). \quad (2.1)$$

Every critical cutvertex in B belongs to exactly two blocks, and the blocks are disjoint otherwise. So we have

$$n(B_0) + \sum_{l=1}^{\text{cr}} n(G_{j_l}) = n(G) + \text{cr}. \quad (2.2)$$

Take a proper drawing of B_0 with width $n(B_0) - 1 + \Phi_w(B_0)$ in Step (3). By induction on the number of vertices, we know that G_{j_l} is embedded with width $n(G_{j_l}) - 1 + \sum_{B \in G_{j_l}} \Phi_w(B)$.

Since the drawing of B_0 is proper, we need not add units for the merging. After all mergings the width is at most the width of B_0 plus all the widths of G_{j_l} , $l \geq 1$. So it is

$$n(B_0) - 1 + \Phi_w(B_0) + \sum_{l=1}^{cr} \left(n(G_{j_l}) - 1 + \sum_{B \in G_{j_l}} \Phi_w(B) \right) = n(G) - 1 + \sum_{B \in G} \Phi_w(B)$$

by Equations 2.1 and 2.2. The calculation for the height is the same. B_0 is embedded with $2n(B_0) - 1 - cr + \Phi_b(B_0)$ bends, and each G_{j_l} with $2n(G_{j_l}) - 1 + \sum_{B \in G_{j_l}} \Phi_b(B)$ bends. We need not add bends for the mergings, and get a total number of bends of

$$2n(B_0) - 1 - cr + \Phi_b(B_0) + \sum_{l=1}^{cr} \left(2n(G_{j_l}) - 1 + \sum_{B \in G_{j_l}} \Phi_b(B) \right) = 2n(G) - 1 + \sum_{B \in G} \Phi_b(B). \quad \square$$

We collect a few properties in relationship with this merging scheme that will be useful later.

Observation:

- *We never produce a new crossing, since the new rows and column are added right next to the drawing of v_1 in G_1 .*
- *The parent-vertex $\text{parent}(B)$ for a block B is the vertex that was prescribed to be drawn as last vertex in CONN .*
- *$\text{parent}(B)$ is defined for all blocks B , except for the block chosen as root for \mathcal{B} (this block is referred to as the outer-most block).*
- *If $\text{parent}(B)$ is defined, then $\deg_{G(\mathcal{B}(B))}(\text{parent}(B)) \leq 3$ and $\text{parent}(B)$ is not a critical cutvertex.*

If a vertex v_i is drawn straight, then we presented only the case when v_i used the connections *top* and *bottom*. If we use BICONN to draw biconnected graphs, this is justified.

Observation: *In BICONN , all vertices of degree 2 are either drawn with right angle, or they are drawn straight using the connections *top* and *bottom*.*

Lemma 2.3.4 *Let G be a 4-graph with r vertices of degree 2 and one (different) vertex of degree ≤ 3 . Then $m(G) \leq 2n(G) - r - 1$.*

Proof: Let w_1, \dots, w_r be the vertices of degree 2, and let w_0 be the (different) vertex of degree at most 3. Write $W = \{w_0, \dots, w_r\}$. We apply the formula $2m = \sum_{v \in V} \deg(v)$ to get an estimation on m . Namely,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{v \in V} \deg(v) &= \sum_{v \in V-W} \deg(v) + \deg(w_0) + \sum_{i=1}^r \deg(w_i) \leq 4|V - W| + 3 + 2r \\ &= 4(n - r - 1) + 3 + 2r = 4n - 2r - 1. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $m(G) \leq \lfloor \frac{1}{2} \sum_{v \in V} \deg(v) \rfloor \leq 2n - r - 1. \quad \square$

Since every critical cutvertex of B has degree 2 in B , and since the parent-vertex is not a critical cutvertex and has degree ≤ 3 , we have

Corollary 2.1 *If for a block B the parent-vertex is defined, then $m(B) \leq 2n(B) - \text{cr}(B) - 1$.*

2.4 Lower bounds

In this section, we establish some results which are useful for proving lower bounds for specific cases later. We start with a theorem that gives the relation between the grid-size and the number of bends. This will be used in two ways: if we know that a graph needs at least a certain grid-size in any drawing, then we get a lower bound on the number of bends. Vice versa, if we have an algorithm that gives a good bound on the number of bends, the grid-size can be bound with this theorem.

Theorem 2.1 *Assume we are given an orthogonal drawing Γ of G with b bends. Then the half-perimeter is at most $b + 2n - m - 2$, and the width and height each are at most $\frac{1}{2}b + 2n - m - 1$.*

Proof:¹ Define $Top(\Gamma)$ to be all those vertices of G where the top connection is not used in Γ . Similarly, define $Bottom(\Gamma)$, $Right(\Gamma)$ and $Left(\Gamma)$. Define $unused(v) = 4 - deg(v)$, which is the number of sets out of $Top(\Gamma)$, $Bottom(\Gamma)$, $Right(\Gamma)$ and $Left(\Gamma)$ to which v belongs.

The first step is to show that the width is at most $\frac{1}{2}(b + |Top(\Gamma)| + |Bottom(\Gamma)|) - 1$; or reformulated, that there are at most $\frac{1}{2}(b + |Top(\Gamma)| + |Bottom(\Gamma)|)$ used columns. Consider a used column. If it is not vertex-used, then it contains a vertical line and at least two bends. If it is vertex-used, let u be the top-most vertex and w be the bottom-most vertex in this column ($u = w$ is possible). If the top connection at u is used, then it must contain a bend, since there is no vertex above u in the column. So we either have a bend above u , or $u \in Top(\Gamma)$. Similarly, we either have a bend below w , or $w \in Bottom(\Gamma)$. So in all, this column contributes at least 2 to the expression $b + |Top(\Gamma)| + |Bottom(\Gamma)|$.

Since no bends or unused connections belong to two columns, $b + |Top(\Gamma)| + |Bottom(\Gamma)|$ is at least twice as much as the number of used columns. We are done with the first step. The same way one shows that the height is at most $\frac{1}{2}(b + |Left(\Gamma)| + |Right(\Gamma)|) - 1$. We know

$$|Top(\Gamma)| + |Bottom(\Gamma)| + |Right(\Gamma)| + |Left(\Gamma)| = \sum_{v \in V} unused(v) = \sum_{v \in V} (4 - deg(v)) = 4n - 2m.$$

This gives the claim on the width and height. The half-perimeter is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{width} + \text{height} &\leq \frac{1}{2}(b + |Top(\Gamma)| + |Bottom(\Gamma)|) - 1 + \frac{1}{2}(b + |Right(\Gamma)| + |Left(\Gamma)|) - 1 \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(2b + 4n - 2m) - 2 = b + 2n - m - 2. \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

A graph is called *4-regular* if every vertex has exactly degree 4, in particular $m = 2n$. For 4-regular graphs we get a useful corollary of this theorem.

Lemma 2.4.1 *A 4-regular graph has $2\lceil\sqrt{n}\rceil + 4$ bends in any drawing.*

Proof: We show that in any drawing the larger of width and height is at least $\lceil\sqrt{n}\rceil + 1$. Then by the above lemma we must have $\frac{1}{2}b + 2n - m - 1 \geq \lceil\sqrt{n}\rceil + 1$. Since $m = 2n$ this implies $b \geq 2(\lceil\sqrt{n}\rceil + 2)$.

Let a drawing be given with c vertex-used columns and r vertex-used rows. After possible rotation we may assume $c \geq r$. Now $c \cdot r \geq n$, and $c \geq \lceil\sqrt{n}\rceil$. Let u and w be vertices in the right-most respectively left-most vertex-used column. By 4-regularity the connection from u to the right and from w to the left is used. Consequently the drawing has at least $\lceil\sqrt{n}\rceil + 2$ used columns and the width is as claimed. \square

¹Many thanks to Goos Kant for useful discussions.

Remember that a simple graph is a graph without loops and multiple edges. Assume we have a 4-regular simple graph. Then we have $n \geq 5$, and the only graph with $n = 5$ is K_5 , the complete graph with five vertices. For simple 4-regular graphs, the above estimation gives a lower bound of 10 bends in any drawing. But in fact, we can do better.

Lemma 2.4.2 *A simple 4-regular graph has at least 12 bends in any drawing.*

Proof: We show that for simple 4-regular graphs we have at least 6 used columns or rows. So the maximum of width and height is at least 5, and with $m = 2n$ we have at least 12 bends by Theorem 2.1. Let c and r be as in the proof of Lemma 2.4.1. If $c \geq 4$ we are done: By 4-regularity the vertices in the right-most and left-most vertex-used column have an outgoing edge at the right connection respectively at the left connection, so we have at least 6 used columns.

Likewise, we are done if the top-most vertex-used row contains two or three vertices: By simplicity, those vertices must be incident to at least 6 edges whose other endpoint is not in that row. So all those other endpoints must be drawn below the row, and to connect them we need at least 6 columns. Similarly we are done if the bottom-most vertex-used row contains two or three vertices. If the right-most vertex-used column or the left-most vertex-used column contains two or three vertices, we similarly have at least 6 rows.

Figure 2.13: A top-most vertex-used row with two or three vertices.

The remaining case is when all extreme vertex-used rows and columns contain only one vertex. By $r \leq c \leq 3$ and $n \geq 5$ there is only one possibility: we have five vertices (i.e. the K_5) and the vertices are placed on a cross. The row in the middle needs five columns to accommodate all its incident edges. But since we have the K_5 , we know that the vertex on top and on bottom are also connected. To accommodate this edge, we need a sixth column. \square

Figure 2.14: Placing on a cross we need 6 columns.

In order to construct larger graphs out of small ones, we will *subdivide* an edge $e = (u, w)$. By this we mean that we delete e , add a new vertex v_e , and add the edges (u, v_e) and (v_e, w) to the graph. The converse process is called *removal of the subdivided vertex v_e* . Subdividing an edge does not change the lower bound too much, as shown in the following lemma.

Lemma 2.4.3 *Assume G has a lower bound of b bends. If G_s results from subdividing an edge of G , then G_s has a lower bound of $b - 1$ bends.*

Proof: Let G_s be drawn with c bends. Removing the subdivided vertex adds at most one bend, so we get a drawing of G with $c + 1$ bends. Consequently $c \geq b - 1$ and $b - 1$ is a lower bound on the number of bends for G_s . \square

Chapter 3

Nonplanar Graphs

3.1 Algorithms

It is very easy to apply the schemes BICONN and CONN to non-planar graphs. This was first shown for simple graphs in [B], we give the results here, and extend them to non-simple graphs.

3.1.1 Biconnected graphs

Assume G is a biconnected graph. Draw it by applying BICONN with the following parameters:

- Choose t to have minimum degree, choose s to have minimum degree in $V - \{t\}$.
- If $\deg(v_1) = 4$, assign the edge leaving v_1 at the bottom connection to be the edge (v_1, v_2) (this exists since we have an st -ordering: $\text{indeg}(v_2) \geq 1$, and v_1 is the only possible predecessor of v_2). Embed v_1 and v_2 together as shown in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Embedding v_1 and v_2 so that there is no 3-bent edge.

- If $\deg(v_n) = 4$, change the drawing of v_n slightly, so that the edge leaving v_{n-1} at the top connection is the one that comes into v_n at the top connection (this exists since $\text{outdeg}(v_{n-1}) \geq 1$). See also Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: By bending a different edge, we can avoid the 3-bent edge at v_n .

We refer to this variant of BICONN as BICONN-NONPLANAR.

Lemma 3.1.1 *In BICONN-NONPLANAR every edge gets at most two bends.*

Proof: Remember that the only possible 3-bent edges are the one at the bottom connection of v_1 , and the one at the top connection of v_n (Lemma 2.2.3). One checks easily that by embedding v_1 and v_n in the way described above, we avoid all 3-bent edges. \square

With the estimations from the previous chapter, we can immediately obtain the grid-size produces with BICONN-NONPLANAR.

Theorem 3.1 (Biedl [B]) *Let G be a biconnected 4-graph with n vertices. Then G can be embedded in an $(n + 1) \times (n + 1)$ -grid with $2n + 4$ bends. Every edge is 2-bent.*

Proof: With BICONN every graph was embedded in an $(m - n + 1) \times (n + 1)$ -grid and $2m - 2n + 4$ bends (Lemma 2.2.1 and Lemma 2.2.2). Since $m \leq 2n$ for all 4-graphs, the result follows. \square

Consider the special case that G is not 4-regular. We then chose the last vertex to have degree ≤ 3 , and get smaller bounds.

Special Case: *Let G be a biconnected 4-graph with n vertices and $m \leq 2n - 1$ edges. Then G can be embedded in an $n \times n$ -grid with $2n + 1$ bends. Every edge is 2-bent.*

This theorem holds for both simple and non-simple graphs. For simple graphs improvement is possible. Biedl [B] showed a improvement of one unit in width and height each, and in two units in the number of bends. Though this seems very little, it is useful for graphs that are not biconnected, since here the improvement counts for every block.

We cite this theorem (and its special case) since it is important for non-biconnected graphs. A proof seems irrelevant in light of Theorem 3.3, but see the treatment for planar graphs on Page 38 for some proof ideas.

Theorem 3.2 (Biedl [B]) *Let G be a simple biconnected 4-graph with n vertices. Then with a variation, BICONN-NONPLANAR embeds G in an $n \times n$ -grid with $2n + 2$ bends. Every edge is 2-bent.*

Special Case: *Let G be a simple biconnected 4-graph with n vertices and $m \leq 2n - 1$ edges. Then with a variation, BICONN-NONPLANAR embeds G in an $(n - 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid with $2n - 1$ bends. Every edge is 2-bent. Moreover, a vertex v with $\deg(v) \leq 3$ can be prespecified to be drawn as final vertex.*

This result can be improved significantly, as shown by Papakostas and Tollis. Their algorithm is based on BICONN-NONPLANAR but with the help of row-reusal and column-reusal a better worst-case lower bound can be achieved. Their algorithm is as of yet unpublished, first ideas can be found in [PT].

Theorem 3.3 (Papakostas & Tollis) *Let G be a biconnected simple 4-graph with n vertices. Then G can be embedded in a grid with half-perimeter $\frac{7}{4}n + 2$ with $2m - 2n + 4$ bends. Every edge has at most 3 bends.*

3.1.2 Connected graphs

The merging-scheme of Section 2.3 is easy to apply to non-planar graphs, as shown first for simple graphs by Biedl [B]. We extend this to non-simple graphs. We use the following parameters:

- Choose the root of the blocktree to be a leaf of the blocktree.
- Loops are embedded in a 1×1 -grid with 3 bends.
- All other blocks B are embedded with BICONN-NONPLANAR with the following parameters:
 - Define t to be the parent-vertex, if it is defined. Otherwise, set it to be a critical cutvertex, if $cr(B) > 0$. Otherwise, set it to be some vertex of minimal degree.
 - Define s to be a critical cutvertex $\neq t$, if such exists, and to be a vertex of minimal degree in $V(B) - \{t\}$ otherwise.
 - If B is simple and $cr(B) = 0$, then apply the improvement step that leads to Theorem 3.2.
- A “proper drawing” means a drawing where all critical cutvertices are drawn with right angle.

We refer to this algorithm as CONN-NONPLANAR.

We assume that \mathcal{B} was non-trivial, i.e. that we have at least two blocks in the graph. In this case, every block contains at least one cutvertex. Consequently, in every block there is at least one vertex with degree less than 4 in this block.

Lemma 3.1.2 *The vertex t chosen to embed a block B with BICONN-NONPLANAR fulfills $\deg(t) \leq 3$.*

Proof: Either $t = \text{parent}(B)$, then this is true since $\deg_{G(\mathcal{B}(B))}(\text{parent}(B)) \leq 3$ for all blocks. Or t is a critical cutvertex. Then $\deg_B(t) = 2$. If neither exists, then t is a vertex of minimum degree. Since the blocktree was assumed to be non-trivial, each block has a vertex of degree less than 4, so $\deg(t) \leq 3$. \square

We mentioned already that with BICONN-NONPLANAR the last vertex is drawn as final vertex, if its degree is at most 3. We get the following corollary.

Observation: *The vertex t chosen to embed a block B with BICONN-NONPLANAR is drawn as final vertex.*

We now give a series of lemmas to compute the correction terms for various types of blocks. Remember that $cr(B)$ is the number of critical cutvertices in a block B . Also, remember that the correction terms of B are numbers $\Phi_w(B)$, $\Phi_h(B)$ and $\Phi_b(B)$ such that B has a proper drawing in a grid of width $n - 1 + \Phi_w(B)$ and height $n - 1 + \Phi_b(B)$, and with $2n - 1 - cr(B) + \Phi_b(B)$ bends.

Lemma 3.1.3 *Assume B is a block that is not a bridge. If the parent-vertex of B is defined and $cr(B) > 0$, then all correction terms are non-positive.*

Proof: Since $\text{parent}(B)$ is defined, we chose $t = \text{parent}(B)$, so t is not a critical cutvertex. Since $cr(B) > 0$, s was chosen to be a critical cutvertex. So both s and t have degree less than 4, and the grid-size obtained with BICONN-NONPLANAR is $(m - n + 1) \times (n - 1)$ and $2m - 2n + 2$ bends.

BICONN-NONPLANAR draws s with a right angle, so we need to add at most $cr - 1$ units in width and $cr - 1$ bends to get a proper drawing. So this proper drawing has height $n - 1$, width $cr - 1 + m - n + 1$ and $cr - 1 + 2m - 2n + 2$ bends. Since $m \leq 2n - 1 - cr$ by the corollary of Lemma 2.3.4, the width is at most $n - 1$ and there are at most $2n - 1 - cr$ bends, and the result follows. \square

Lemma 3.1.4 *Assume B is a block that is not a bridge. If the parent-vertex of B is defined and $cr(B) = 0$, then the correction terms are $\Phi_w(B) \leq 1$, $\Phi_h(B) \leq 1$ and $\Phi_b(B) \leq 2$.*

Proof: Since $cr(B) = 0$, any drawing is a proper drawing. We have to show that B is embedded in an $n \times n$ -grid with $2n + 1$ bends. We have two cases to consider: either B was a loop, or it was embedded with BICONN-NONPLANAR. If it was a loop, it is embedded in a 1×1 -grid with 3 bends and $n = 1$, so we are done.

If B was embedded with BICONN-NONPLANAR we chose $t = \text{parent}(B)$, so $\text{deg}(t) \leq 3$. With that, we get an $(m - n + 1) \times n$ -grid with $2m - 2n + 3$ bends. We know that $m \leq 2n - 1$ by the corollary of Lemma 2.3.4. So the width of the proper drawing is at most $(2n - 1) - n + 1 = n$. The number of bends is at most $2(2n - 1) - 2n + 3 = 2n + 1$. \square

Lemma 3.1.5 *If \mathcal{B} is non-trivial, and the outer-most block B_0 is not a bridge, then its correction terms are $\Phi_w(B_0) \leq 1$, $\Phi_h(B_0) \leq 1$ and $\Phi_b(B_0) \leq 3$.*

Proof: We need to find an $n \times n$ -grid with at most $2n - cr(B) + 2$ bends. By choice of the outer-most block, B_0 is a leaf in the blocktree and only adjacent to one cutvertex. So $cr(B_0) \leq 1$. If $cr(B_0) = 1$, t was chosen as the critical cutvertex, and embedded with right angle. So the drawing produced by BICONN-NONPLANAR is a proper drawing. If $cr(B_0) = 0$, then the drawing is a proper drawing as well. Since \mathcal{B} is non-trivial, $\text{deg}(t) \leq 3$, and we obtained an $n \times n$ -grid with $2n + 1$ bends. We are done by $cr(B_0) \leq 1$. \square

We will for now assume that we have no bridges.

Lemma 3.1.6 *Assume G has no bridges. If le is the number of leaves in the blocktree, then*

$$\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_w(B) \leq le, \sum_{B \in G} \Phi_h(B) \leq le, \text{ and } \sum_{B \in G} \Phi_b(B) \leq 2le + 1.$$

Proof: We know that the only way a correction term could be positive is that either the block has no critical cutvertex, or it is the outer-most block. Since we have no bridges, every block without critical cutvertex is a leaf of the blocktree. The outer-most block is a leaf of the blocktree as well. The results follow immediately with Lemma 3.1.4 and Lemma 3.1.5. \square

Unfortunately the number of leaves in the blocktree can be large, up to n for a 4-graph without bridges. We show this in two steps:

Lemma 3.1.7 *Every 4-graph G without bridges has at most $n + 1$ blocks. If G is not 4-regular, it has at most n blocks.*

Proof: Since we have no bridges, every cutvertex must have two neighbors in each block it belongs to. Since we have a 4-graph, every cutvertex belongs to precisely two blocks and has degree 4 in G and degree 2 in \mathcal{B} .

In \mathcal{B} , there are no edges between two blocks, and there are no edges between two cutvertices. Such a graph is called *bipartite*. For a bipartite graph with vertex classes A and B we have the formula $m = \sum_{v \in A} \text{deg}(v) = \sum_{v \in B} \text{deg}(v)$. Let bl be the number of blocks and cv be the number of cutvertices. We have $n(\mathcal{B}) = bl + cv$, and, since \mathcal{B} is a tree, $m(\mathcal{B}) = bl + cv - 1$ edges, so

$$bl + cv - 1 = m(\mathcal{B}) = \sum_{v \text{ cutvertex}} \text{deg}_{\mathcal{B}}(v) = \sum_{v \text{ cutvertex}} 2 = 2cv,$$

and $bl \leq cv + 1$. Since every cutvertex has degree 4, we get $bl \leq \#\{\text{vertices of degree 4}\} + 1 \leq n + 1$. If G is not 4-regular, then we have at most $n - 1$ cutvertices and at most n blocks. \square

Lemma 3.1.8 *Every 4-graph G without bridges has at most $\max\{2, n\}$ leaves in the blocktree.*

Proof: Assume there are more than n leaves in the blocktree. By the above lemma, we must have $n + 1$ blocks, and every block is a leaf. So every block has degree 1 in \mathcal{B} , and $bl + cv - 1 = m(\mathcal{B}) = \sum_{B \text{ block}} \deg(B) = bl$. This implies $cv = 1$. Since we have no bridge, there exist then only two blocks, and therefore only two leaves. \square

Figure 3.3: The bounds of the above two lemmas are tight: The first shown graph has $n + 1$ blocks and n leaves, the second graph is not 4-regular and has n blocks and $n - 1$ leaves.

We state now only the result for graphs without bridges. Graphs with bridges are treated together with multi-graphs and simple graphs in Theorem 3.8.

Theorem 3.4 *Let G be a 4-graph without bridges with $n > 1$ vertices. Then G can be embedded in a $(2n - 1) \times (2n - 1)$ -grid with $4n$ bends.*

Proof: By Lemma 2.3.3 the width is $n - 1 + \sum \Phi_w(B)$, the height is $n - 1 + \sum \Phi_h(B)$ and the number of bends is $2n - 1 + \sum \Phi_b(B)$. The result follows from Lemma 3.1.6 and 3.1.8. \square

Multi-graphs

Theorem 3.4 can be improved for graphs without loops. The key observation is that small blocks need no positive correction terms.

Lemma 3.1.9 *Let G be a connected multi-graph without bridges with $n \geq 3$. If B is a block that is not a bridge, and $n(B) = 2$, then its correction terms are non-positive.*

Proof: We claim that B must be a double edge. It cannot be a simple edge, since we have no bridge. It cannot be a quadruple edge, since $n \geq 3$, and since G is a connected 4-graph. It also cannot be a triple edge. For assume B were a triple edge. By $n \geq 3$ there are more vertices in the graph, so one vertex v of B is a cutvertex. But then v is connected to the rest of the graph by a bridge, a contradiction.

So B indeed is a double edge, and can be embedded in a 1×1 -grid with 2 bends. We are done if we can show that $cr(B) \leq 1$. If B is the outer-most block, then it is a leaf in the blocktree, and $cr(B) \leq 1$. If B is not the outer-most block, then $parent(B)$ is defined and not a critical cutvertex, so by $n \leq 2$ we have $cr(B) \leq 1$. \square

Lemma 3.1.10 *Let G be a multi-graph without bridges and $n \geq 6$. Then $\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_w(B) \leq \frac{n}{3}$, $\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_h(B) \leq \frac{n}{3}$, and $\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_b(B) \leq \frac{2}{3}n + 1$.*

Proof: By Lemma 3.1.4 and Lemma 3.1.9, every block B of G with positive correction terms has at least 3 vertices and is a leaf of \mathcal{B} . We are done if we know that no such two leaves intersect. In this case we can assign three vertices to each leaf with positive correction terms, without counting vertices twice. So there are at most $\frac{n}{3}$ many such blocks, and each of them contributes at most 1 in width and height and 2 in bends (Lemma 3.1.4) except the outer-most block, which contributes one more in bends (Lemma 3.1.5).

So assume two leaves of the blocktree do intersect. They can do so only in a cutvertex. Since we have no bridges, the cutvertex must have degree 2 in either of the leaves. Since we have a 4-graph, this means the cutvertex has no other neighbors than those in the leaves. But also each of the leaves has no other cutvertex, and the blocktree consists of two leaves only. So the sums of the correction terms are at most 2 for the width and height and at most 5 for the number of bends. We are done by $n \geq 6$. \square

Lemma 3.1.11 *If G has at least one cutvertex, then the resulting drawing is 2-bent.*

Proof: Since we have no loop, every block is drawn with BICONN-NONPLANAR. So each block B is embedded with at most 2 bends per edge. The only problematic case is to change the drawing of B into a proper drawing. Namely, when v_i was drawn straight, we add a bend to one edge.

However, we know that B was drawn with BICONN-NONPLANAR. Furthermore, since v_i was drawn straight, it was not chosen as s , so some other critical cutvertex was s , and both s and t had degree ≤ 3 . In this case, every edge that leaves one of its endpoints at the top connection or at the bottom connection has at most one bend. So both incident edges of v_i are only 1-bent in BICONN-NONPLANAR. So after adding a bend to get a proper drawing, they are 2-bent. \square

With this, we can now get a better bound for multi-graphs.

Theorem 3.5 *Let G be a multi-4-graph without bridges with $n \geq 6$ vertices. Then G can be embedded in a $(\frac{4}{3}n - 1) \times (\frac{4}{3}n - 1)$ -grid with $\frac{8}{3}n$ bends. Every edge is 2-bent.*

Proof: This follows from the general analysis in Lemma 2.3.3 and Lemma 3.1.10, and from Lemma 3.1.11. \square

Simple graphs

We can do even better for simple graphs: hardly any positive correction terms are necessary.

Lemma 3.1.12 *Assume B is a simple block that is not a bridge. If the parent-vertex of B is defined, and $cr(B) = 0$, then all correction terms of B are non-positive.*

Proof: Remember that the special case of Theorem 3.2 stated that we can embed any simple not 4-regular simple graph in an $(n - 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid with $2n - 1$ bends. Moreover, we can choose the last vertex and it is drawn as final vertex. Since we have no critical cutvertex in B , this drawing is a proper drawing and none of the correction terms is positive. \square

Lemma 3.1.13 *If \mathcal{B} was non-trivial, and the outer-most block B_0 is not a bridge, then its correction terms are $\Phi_w(B_0) \leq 0$, $\Phi_h(B_0) \leq 0$ and $\Phi_b(B_0) \leq 1$.*

Proof: Since B_0 is chosen as a leaf of the blocktree, it has $cr(B_0) \leq 1$. So it suffices to get a proper drawing in an $(n - 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid with $2n - 1$ bends. Since the blocktree is non-trivial, the last vertex chosen for BICONN-NONPLANAR has degree ≤ 3 . If B_0 had a critical cutvertex, then it was chosen as last vertex for BICONN-NONPLANAR, and drawn with right angle. Together with the special case of Theorem 3.2 we get the correct sizes. \square

So the sums of the correction terms are non-positive for the width and the height, and at most 1 for the bends. Applying this to the general analysis in Lemma 2.3.3, we get together with Lemma 3.1.11 the following result.

Theorem 3.6 *Let G be simple 4-graph with n vertices without bridges. Assume G is connected, but not biconnected. Then G can be embedded in an $(n - 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid with $2n$ bends. Every edge is 2-bent.*

One would expect that this result can be improved significantly by replacing the algorithm of Biedl by the algorithm of Papakostas and Tollis for drawing biconnected simple graphs. However, this is not the case. The problem is that the algorithm by Papakostas and Tollis is better only if the number of vertices is large. But in the worst case we could have a graph consisting of many small blocks. Here, both algorithms would work equally well.

It is nevertheless advisable to implement the algorithm of Papakostas and Tollis, since quite often we have blocks with a higher number of vertices, which leads to a decrease in the grid-size.

Treatment of bridges

For the analysis thus far, bridges have not been considered. The following theorem justifies this: we never need a larger grid or more bends for graphs with bridges.

Theorem 3.7 *In a 4-graph G , all bridges can be removed by adding edges, such that*

1. *the resulting graph is a 4-graph,*
2. *we do not add loops,*
3. *we do not add a triple edge,*
4. *if we add a double edge, then this double edge is a block afterwards.*

Proof: We proceed by induction on the number of bridges. The case of no bridges is trivially correct. Assume (v_1, v_2) is a bridge, and removing it splits G into H_1 and H_2 , where $v_i \in H_i$.

We claim that H_i contains a vertex w_i , so that the degree of w_i in G is odd. Assume there is no such vertex. So in particular the degree of v_i in G was even, and the degree of v_i in H_i , which is one less, is odd. For all other vertices in H_i the degree in G is the same as the degree in H_i . So H_i has exactly one vertex of odd degree. This is a contradiction to the well-known fact that every graph has an even number of vertices of odd degree.

We claim that adding an edge (w_1, w_2) does not violate any of the above conditions:

1. Since both w_1 and w_2 had odd degree, they had degree ≤ 3 , so the resulting graph is a 4-graph.
2. w_1 and w_2 are different, since the intersection of H_1 and H_2 is empty. So the added edge is not a loop.
3. Assume that the edge (w_1, w_2) did exist already. There is only one edge between H_1 and H_2 , namely, the bridge (v_1, v_2) . This edge is a single edge (by definition of a bridge), so we do not introduce a triple edge.
4. As shown before, if the edge (w_1, w_2) exists, then it is a bridge. So if we introduce a double edge, then it is a block of its own.

The graph resulting from adding (w_1, w_2) has one bridge less, by induction we are done. \square

With this, we get the theorem for 4-graphs.

Theorem 3.8 (for simple graphs due to Biedl [B]) *Let G be a 4-graph with n vertices that is not biconnected. Then G can be embedded as follows:*

- *If G is simple: in an $(n - 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid with $2n$ bends. Every edge is 2-bent.*
- *If G is a multi-graph and $n > 5$: in a $(\frac{4}{3}n - 1) \times (\frac{4}{3}n - 1)$ -grid with $\frac{8}{3}n$ bends. Every edge is 2-bent.*
- *If G has loops and $n > 1$: in a $(2n - 1) \times (2n - 1)$ -grid with $4n$ bends.*

Proof: First, take G and remove all bridges by applying Theorem 3.7. Call the resulting graph G' . If G had loops, then apply Theorem 3.4 on G' . If G was a multi-graph, then so is G' , and we can apply Theorem 3.5. Either way, we get a drawing of G' of the appropriate size, and deleting the drawings of the added edges can only reduce it.

If G was simple, then G' is not necessarily simple. However, if there is a multiple edge, then it is a double edge and a block. Such a block needs a 1×1 -grid and 2 bends, so it has non-positive correction terms. So the sums of the correction terms for G' are non-positive in width and height, and at most 1 in bends, which proves the claim. \square

Previously known results: *This theorem compares favorably with the previous best bound of Schöffter [Sch], who gave a $2n \times 2n$ -grid with at most 5 bends per edge.*

Figure 3.4: The restrictions $n > 1$ for graphs with loops and $n > 5$ for multigraphs are necessary. With methods similar as in the proof of Theorem 3.10 on Page 31, one can show that the first graph needs $6 = 4 \cdot 1 + 2$ bends, while the second graph needs $14 > \frac{8}{3} \cdot 5$ bends.

Remark: *It is possible to avoid the use of Theorem 3.7 and deal directly with merging bridges. In fact, this leads to better results if the number of bridges is large. However, the analysis is lengthy, and for brevity we skip this here. The approach will be shown for planar and plane graphs.*

3.2 Lower bounds

3.2.1 The grid-size

Valiant [V81] mentioned that there exists a family of 3-graphs with $\Omega(n^2)$ crossings in any drawing. Since every crossing needs a grid-point, we get the same lower bound for the size of the grid. In this section we work out the proof-sketch in more detail, which in particular enables us to get an estimate of the constants involved. This graph class is created using the following type of graphs.

Definition 8 *An r -superconcentrator is a graph with r inputs $\mathcal{I} = \{a_1, \dots, a_r\}$ and r outputs $\mathcal{O} = \{b_1, \dots, b_r\}$, such that for any $1 \leq k \leq r$ and any pair of subsets $I \subseteq \mathcal{I}$ and $O \subseteq \mathcal{O}$ of size k , there exist k vertex-disjoint paths between I and O .*

A trivial example of an r -superconcentrator is $K_{r,r}$, the complete bipartite graph on $2r$ vertices. This has $\mathcal{O}(r^2)$ edges. Valiant [V75] showed the existence of r -superconcentrators of *linear size*, i.e. there exists a constant K such that they have at most $K \cdot r$ edges. Pippenger [Pi] gave another construction that yields linear size superconcentrators, with $K < 40$ and a maximum degree of 16.

For a family of r -superconcentrators the crossing number grows with $\Omega(r^2)$. This is shown by converting a superconcentrator into a planar superconcentrator which has many vertices.

Operation 1 *Assume a graph is embedded such that at most two edges cross at a point. Replace a crossing of the edges e_1, e_2 by a cycle $\{v_1, \dots, v_4\}$. Connect the endpoints of e_1 with v_1 respectively v_3 and the endpoints of e_2 with v_2 respectively v_4 .*

Lemma 3.2.1 *Applying Operation 1 to an r -superconcentrator gives an r -superconcentrator.*

Proof: Let G be an r -superconcentrator. Let G' be the graph that results from applying Operation 1 to two crossing edges e_1 and e_2 . Let a_{i_1}, \dots, a_{i_k} , and b_{j_1}, \dots, b_{j_k} be any choice of k inputs and outputs. Those are connected in G by k vertex-disjoint paths P_1, \dots, P_k , and after possible renaming assume that P_l connects a_{i_l} with b_{j_l} . There are two cases to consider, namely whether one or two paths used the edges e_1 and e_2 .

If it is exactly one path, replace the edge by a part of the cycle. So assume two paths P_g and P_h use the edges e_1 respectively e_2 . Write P_g as $a_{i_g} - Q_g - e_1 - R_g - b_{j_g}$ and P_h as $a_{i_h} - Q_h - e_2 - R_h - b_{j_h}$. Now connect Q_g with R_h and Q_h with R_g using the appropriate edges of the cycle. We get the new paths $P'_g = a_{i_g} - Q_g - R_h - b_{i_h}$ and $P'_h = a_{i_h} - Q_h - R_g - b_{i_g}$.

Figure 3.5: Reassign paths at a former crossing.

This agrees with the definition of an r -superconcentrator: we only need to connect the sets by r disjoint paths, but it is not prescribed which vertex is connected to which. \square

In order to get a superconcentrator with maximum degree 3, replace a vertex of high degree by a cycle of vertices of degree 3.

Operation 2 *Remove a vertex v and replace it by a cycle of length $\deg(v)$. Connect the neighbors of v with one vertex on the cycle each. If v was an input or output, then let one of the new vertices be an input respectively output.*

Lemma 3.2.2 *Applying Operation 2 to an r -superconcentrator gives an r -superconcentrator.*

Proof: Using the notation of the proof of Lemma 3.2.1, assume one path P_l used the vertex v of high degree. Say P_l contained the segment $Q_l - u - v - w - R_l$. Then let P'_l be the same path as P_l , except for that v is replaced by a part of the cycle to connect u and w . If v was an input respectively an output, then replace the first respectively last part of P_l with the part of the cycle that leads to the new input respectively output. \square

The following result is known about the number of vertices of a planar superconcentrator:

Lemma 3.2.3 (Lipton & Tarjan [LT]) *A planar r -superconcentrator has at least $r^2/72$ vertices.*

With that, superconcentrators can be used to get the graph class with many crossings.

Theorem 3.9 (Valiant [V81]) *There exists a class $\{G_n\}$ of 3-graphs, where G_n has n vertices, such that the crossing number grows with $\Omega(n^2)$.*

Proof: Start with a class $\{G'_r\}$ of r -superconcentrators with less than $40r$ edges [Pi]. Apply Operation 2 simultaneously to all vertices of degree at least 4 to get $\{G''_r\}$. G''_r has at most $\sum_{v \in V(G'_r)} \deg(v) = 2|E(G'_r)| \leq 80r$ vertices.

$\{G''_r\}$ now is the desired graph class. G''_r has maximum degree 3. To show that the crossing number is $\Omega(n^2)$, draw G''_r such that at most two edges cross in one point. Denote by c_r the number of crossings in this drawing, and apply Operation 1 for each. The obtained graph G''_r is a planar r -superconcentrator with at most $80r + 4c_r$ vertices. By Lemma 3.2.3 we get $80r + 4c_r \geq n \geq \frac{r^2}{72}$ or $c_r \geq \frac{1}{4 \cdot 72} r^2 - 20r = \Omega(r^2) = \Omega((n(G''_r))^2)$. Setting now $n(r) = n(G''_r)$ and $G_{n(r)} = G''_r$ we get the desired class. \square

Corollary 3.1 (Valiant [V81]) *There exists a class $\{G_n\}$ of 3-graphs, where G_n has n vertices, such that the size of a minimal two-dimensional orthogonal drawing of G_n grows with $\Omega(n^2)$.*

This proof has two drawbacks. For one thing the constant is very small: G_n is an r -superconcentrator for an r with $r \geq \frac{1}{80}n$ and has at least $\frac{1}{4 \cdot 72} r^2 \geq \frac{1}{4 \cdot 72 \cdot 6400} n^2$ crossings, hence the constant is roughly 10^{-6} . Also for c_r to be at least positive we need $r \geq 5760$; so the smallest graph where this applies has $\approx 450,000$ vertices! It remains open to find smaller graphs that need a grid of quadratic size, preferably with a larger constant.

3.2.2 The number of bends

Previously known results: Only lower bounds for the simple biconnected graphs have been considered. Storer [St] showed a lower bound of $\frac{8}{7}n$ bends (he incorrectly reported it as $\frac{10}{7}n$ bends), and Papakostas and Tollis showed a lower bound of $\frac{8}{5}n$ (private communication).

We develop lower bounds for the number of bends. We will improve the known bounds and develop new ones for non-simple graphs. We will also give lower bounds for non-planar drawings of planar graphs. Such drawings are interesting, since it is possible to draw planar graphs with a significantly smaller grid when allowing for crossings (Leiserson [Leis]).

Our lower bounds are derived by taking small graphs which need many bends, and building larger graphs from these small graphs. We use the following graphs: The complete graph K_5 , the octahedron O , and the quadruple edge graph Q , which are shown below.

Figure 3.6: The complete graph K_5 , the octahedron O , and the quadruple edge graph Q .

Lemma 3.2.4 K_5 and O need at least 12 bends, while Q needs at least 8 bends in any drawing.

Proof: In Lemma 2.4.2 we showed that every simple 4-regular graph needs 12 bends in any drawing. This proves the claim K_5 and O . In Lemma 2.4.1 we showed that for every 4-regular graph needs $2\lceil\sqrt{n}\rceil + 4$ bends in any drawing. This proves the claim for Q . \square

To get 4-graphs of arbitrary large size which need many bends, we subdivide one edge in a small graph, take many copies of the resulting graph, and connect the vertices of degree 2.

Theorem 3.10 There exist the following lower bounds for drawing a connected 4-graph G :

1. G simple and planar: $\frac{11}{7}n$ bends
2. G simple: $\frac{11}{6}n$ bends
3. G a multi-graph and planar: $\frac{7}{3}n$ bends
4. G with loops and planar: $3n$ bends

Proof: We demonstrate only case (1) in detail, the other cases are analogous. Take an octahedron and subdivide one edge. We get a graph with 7 vertices that by Lemma 3.2.4 and Lemma 2.4.3 needs 11 bends. Now we take k copies of this graph and connect the vertices of degree 2. This graph is connected, has $7k$ vertices and needs at least $11k = \frac{11}{7}n$ bends.

For case (2) and case (3), take the K_5 respectively Q . For case (4) we take k copies of a loop and connect the vertices with each other. Every loops needs 3 bends, so this graph needs at least $3n$ bends. \square

Figure 3.7: Connected graphs that need many bends in any drawing.

For biconnected graphs we subdivide two edges, and identify vertices of degree 2.

Theorem 3.11 *There exist the following lower bounds for drawing a biconnected 4-graph G :*

1. G simple and planar: $\frac{10}{7}n$ bends
2. G simple: $\frac{10}{6}n$ bends
3. G a multi-graph and planar: $\frac{6}{3}n = 2n$ bends

Proof: Again we demonstrate only case (1). Take an octahedron and subdivide two edges on the outer-face. We get a graph with 8 vertices that by Lemma 3.2.4 and Lemma 2.4.3 needs 10 bends. Now we take k copies of this graph and identify the vertices of degree 2. This graph is biconnected, has $7k$ vertices and needs at least $10k = \frac{10}{7}n$ bends. For the other cases we take the K_5 respectively Q and subdivide two arbitrary edges. \square

Figure 3.8: Biconnected graphs that need many bends.

Remember that a graph is called *triconnected* if it is simple and for any two vertices $\{v, w\}$ the graph $G - \{v, w\}$ is connected. We did not deal with algorithms for triconnected graphs, since we know of no algorithm that makes use of this feature for non-planar graph. However, in this context it is easy to provide lower bounds for triconnected graphs as well.

Theorem 3.12 *There exist the following lower bounds for drawing a triconnected 4-graph G :*

1. G simple and planar: $\frac{6}{5}n$ bends.
2. G simple: $\frac{18}{13}n$ bends.

Proof: Again we demonstrate only case (1). Take an octahedron and subdivide the three edges on the outer-face. We get a graph with 9 vertices that by Lemma 3.2.4 and Lemma 2.4.3 needs 9 bends. Take $2k$ copies and identify the vertices of degree 2 in such a way that the resulting graph is planar and triconnected (see also Figure 3.9). The graph has $(6 + \frac{3}{2})2k = 15k$ vertices and needs at least $9 \cdot 2k = \frac{18}{15}n = \frac{6}{5}n$ bends.

For the other case we take a quadruple edge and subdivide three edges. \square

Figure 3.9: Triconnected graphs that need many bends.

Chapter 4

Planar and Plane Graphs

In this chapter we deal with planar graphs. We first give an introduction to planar graphs. Then we show how based on BICONN and CONN, we obtain planar orthogonal drawings of planar graphs. Finally, we give lower bounds.

4.1 Definitions for planarity

Remember that for any given drawing of a graph, a *crossing* is a place where the drawings of two edges intersect. Crossings are highly undesirable in a drawing: they bear the possibility of confusion of the two edges, and make the drawing less readable.

It would be nice to avoid as many crossings as possible. Unfortunately, the problem of computing the minimum number of crossings is \mathcal{NP} -complete [GJ] and this task is hopeless. However, it can be computed in linear time whether a graph can be drawn without crossings at all [HT, BL]. Such a graph is called *planar*.

A drawing of a planar graph G without a crossing is called a *planar drawing* of G . Such a drawing defines a circular ordering of the edges incident to a vertex v when we go around the drawing of the vertex in clockwise order. Hence we can order the entries of the incidence list in this order.

If a planar graph is given such that the orderings of the incidence lists come from some planar drawing, this is called a *combinatorial embedding* of the graph. A planar drawing splits the plane into different components, called *faces*. The unbounded component is called the *outer-face*.

Assume a combinatorial embedding is specified, and the incidence lists of vertices are ordered in clockwise direction. By *going around a face in clockwise order* we mean the following process: Start at a vertex v and an incident edge e_v . Let w be the other endpoint of e_v and let e_w be the edge before e_v in the incidence list of w . Iterating this, we end at some point at v and e_v again, and we have circulated the face F “to the right” of e_v .

The vertices and edges encountered while going around F are called *incident* to F . The number of edges incident to F is called the *degree* of F and denoted $deg(F)$. This number is the same as the number of vertices incident to F . We can encounter vertices and edges repeatedly, and they are then counted repeatedly to the degree.

The faces change if we change the combinatorial embedding. However, their number stays the same, call it f . Euler’s formula tells that $n - m + f = 2$ for every planar graph. In a simple graph every face has a degree of at least 3, hence $3f \geq 2m$, which implies that $m \leq 3n - 6$ for any planar simple graph. In a planar simple graph $m = 3n - 6$ if and only if every face has degree 3. Such a graph is called *triangulated*.

From a given combinatorial embedding we can reconstruct the faces. If we specify a combinatorial embedding and one face of it to be the outer-face, then we get a unique planar drawing, up to topological deformations.

We want to stress the difference between a *planar* and a *plane* graph. A planar graph *can* be drawn without crossing. A plane graph *is* drawn without crossing, i.e. both a combinatorial embedding and the outer-face are specified. For a plane graph we want to get a *plane drawing*, i.e. a drawing with that gives this combinatorial embedding, and has this outer-face.

4.2 Algorithms for planar graphs

The schemes presented in Chapter 2 have been exploited by Biedl and Kant [BK] for simple graphs to get planar drawings of planar graphs. We present their results here, and extend them to graphs with multiple edges and loops.

4.2.1 Biconnected graphs

Assume G is a biconnected planar graph. We assume that G has at least three vertices (for graphs with two vertices, the same bounds can be achieved easily). To get an orthogonal drawing of G , apply BICONN with the following parameters:

- Choose t as follows:
 - (i) Let t be a vertex of minimal degree.
 - (ii) Let G' be the underlying simple graph of G .
 - (iii) Choose some combinatorial embedding of G' .
 - (iv) **if** $\deg_G(t) \leq 3$, choose a face F incident to t with $\deg_{G'}(F) \geq 3$ (see Lemma 4.2.1).
 - (v) **else**
 - (a) Let F be a face of maximal degree.
 - (b) Choose a new t incident to F .
 - (vi) Make face F the outer-face of the planar embedding.
 - (vii) Obtain a planar drawing of G
 - by inserting multiple edges directly next to their copy in G' .
- Choose s such that $s \neq t$ and s is incident to the (above determined) outer-face F .
- Change the combinatorial embedding and compute an st -ordering such that the edges (v_1, v_2) and, possibly, (v_{n-1}, v_n) are on the outer-face (see Lemma 4.2.2 and 4.2.3).
- Assign temporary endpoints to outgoing edges according to the combinatorial embedding.
- If $\deg(v_1) = 4$, assign the edge leaving v_1 at the bottom connection to be the edge (v_1, v_2) . Embed v_1 and v_2 together as shown in Figure 4.1.
- If $\deg(v_n) = 4$, change the drawing of v_n slightly, so that the edge leaving v_{n-1} at the top connection enters v_n at the top connection. See also Figure 4.2.

We refer to this algorithm as BICONN-PLANAR.

Lemma 4.2.1 *The claim of Step (iv) is true, i.e. if $n \geq 3$, then for every vertex there exists an incident face F with $\deg_{G'}(F) \geq 3$.*

Proof: Assume there is no such F . Since G' is biconnected, and since loops are not allowed in a biconnected graph, all incident faces have degree 2. But G' is simple, and a face can have degree 2 only if G' is a single edge. So G has only two vertices, a contradiction. \square

For non-planar graphs, it was relatively easy to avoid 2-bent edges. It is possible for almost all planar graphs, too, but some more work is necessary.

The idea is that BICONN produces only two 3-bent edges. These edges were the one at the bottom connection of v_1 and the one at the top connection of v_n . Assume we have a planar embedding and an st -ordering of G , such that the edge (v_1, v_2) is on the outer-face. We can do what we did in the non-planar case: we embed v_1 and v_2 together without creating a crossing (see also Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1: Embedding v_1 and v_2 so that there is no 3-bent edge. The reason for the seemingly “stupid” drawing of the simple edge is that we need it for the improvement for simple graphs, see Lemma 4.2.8.

So we need a planar embedding and an st -ordering such that the edge (v_1, v_2) is on the outer-face. Such an ordering is called a *weak pl-st-ordering*.

In order to avoid the other 3-bent edge, we simply changed the way v_n is drawn in the non-planar case. This does not work here, since it possibly introduced a crossing. Instead, we proceed similar as for the first edge. Assume that $\deg(v_n) = 4$, and that the edge (v_{n-1}, v_n) is on the outer-face.

Since we preserve the planar embedding (see Lemma 4.2.5), the edge (v_{n-1}, v_n) is left-most or right-most incoming edge for v_n . Assume it is left-most. By the way we treated multiple edges in Step (vii), all copies of the edge (v_{n-1}, v_n) are at the left end. Depending on the multiplicity of this edge, we can now embed v_{n-1} together with v_n and avoid the 3-bent edge (see Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.2: Embedding v_{n-1} and v_n so that there is no 3-bent edge. The reason for the seemingly “stupid” drawing of the simple edge is that we need it for the improvement for simple graphs, see Lemma 4.2.8.

So what we really want is a planar embedding and an st -ordering such that both the edge (v_1, v_2) and the edge (v_{n-1}, v_n) are on the outer-face. We call such an ordering a *(strong) pl-st-ordering*. As we show now, such an ordering exists for almost all biconnected planar graphs.

Lemma 4.2.2 *Let G be a biconnected planar graph. Let $s, t \in V$. If there is a planar embedding of G such that s, t belong to the outer-face F ; and if $\deg(F) \geq 3$, then G has a weak pl - st -ordering with s as first and t as last vertex.*

Proof: In the following for any given planar embedding with s on the outer-face, denote by v^* the neighbor of s to the right on the outer-face.

We start with a planar embedding of G such that F is the outer-face, and such that t is not the right neighbor of s on F (if necessary, we reflect the embedding to achieve this. It is always possible since $\deg(F) \geq 3$).

The next step consists to change the embedding such that s and v^* do not form a *cutting pair*, i.e. removing s and v^* leaves a connected graph. Assume $\{s, v^*\}$ indeed was a cutting pair. Move all other copies of the edge (s, v^*) next to the edge on the outer-face. It is known that now there is a face incident to both s and v^* , but not incident to the edge (s, v^*) . Into this face we swap (s, v^*) , and all copies of it, if it was a multiple edge.

Figure 4.3: Swap the edge away from the outer-face.

Now a new neighbor of s appears on the outer-face and we repeat the argument with it. Can this process cycle, i.e. can the old v^* ever become neighbor of s on the outer-face again? After swapping the edge (s, v^*) , the length of the path between s and v^* on the outer-face increases, since we swapped all copies. It never decreases, so it can never become 1, and v^* can never be neighbor of s on the outer-face again.

So we must stop after at most $\deg(s)$ swaps, and then s and its neighbor v^* on the outer-face are not a cutting pair. Let G_c be the graph resulting from contraction of the edge (s, v^*) , i.e. delete s, v^* , and all copies of the edge (s, v^*) ; add a new vertex v_c , and connect it with all edges where one endpoint was s or v^* before.

It is known that if G is biconnected, and if $\{s, v^*\}$ is not a cutting pair, then G_c is biconnected. Calculate an st -ordering for G_c with v_c as first and t as last vertex. Assume it was $\{w_1, \dots, w_{n-1}\}$, then one checks easily that $\{s, v^*, w_2, \dots, w_{n-1} = t\}$ is now the desired weak pl - st -ordering. \square

Lemma 4.2.3 *Let G be a biconnected planar graph, $s, t \in V$. If there is a planar embedding of G such that s, t belong to the outer-face F , and $\deg(F) \geq 4$, then G has a strong pl - st -ordering with s as first and t as last vertex.*

Proof: We compute the graph G_c , the graph with one edge contracted, as described in the above proof. The degree of the outer-face never decreases during these operations. So the degree of the outer-face of G before the contraction is at least 4, and the degree of the outer-face of G_c is at least 3. By the above lemma we can find a weak pl - st -ordering of G_c with t as first and the contracted vertex v_c as last vertex. Call it $\{u_1, \dots, u_{n-1}\}$.

Since the reversal of an st -ordering is an st -ordering, $\{u_{n-1}, \dots, u_2, u_1 = t\}$ is an st -ordering of G_c . Since $u_{n-1} = v_c$, we know that $\{s, v^*, u_{n-2}, \dots, u_2, t\}$ is an st -ordering of G . One checks easily that it is in fact a strong pl - st -ordering. \square

With this we can show how to avoid the 3-bent edges for planar drawings.

Lemma 4.2.4 *If G is not 4-regular, or if $n \geq 7$, then BICONN-PLANAR draws G with at most 2 bends per edge.*

Proof: Assume first that G is not 4-regular. Then t is a vertex of $\deg(t) \leq 3$, and F is an incident face with $\deg(F) \geq 3$. We can find a weak pl - st -ordering with Lemma 4.2.2. Applying BICONN-PLANAR with this st -ordering, and drawing v_1 and v_2 together as described above we avoid the 3-bent edge at v_1 . By $\deg(t) \leq 3$ no edge is bent twice with the embedding of t .

Now assume G is 4-regular. So $\deg(t) = 4$, and we chose as the outer-face a face F with maximum degree. If F has $\deg(F) \geq 4$, we chose s and t on this face, found a strong pl - st -ordering, and applied BICONN-PLANAR with this ordering; avoiding the 3-bent edges at v_1 and v_n as shown above.

So assume G is 4-regular, but all faces in G' (the underlying simple graph) have degree 2 or 3. G' is simple and $n \geq 7$, so no face can have degree 2. So G' is triangulated and has $3n - 6$ edges. This gives $m(G) \geq m(G') = 3n - 6$, but also $m(G) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{v \in V} \deg_G(v) = 2n$. This implies $n \leq 6$, a contradiction. \square

Now we need to show what we claimed before: the resulting drawing is planar.

Lemma 4.2.5 *BICONN-PLANAR gives a planar orthogonal drawing that exactly reflects the planar embedding which we had after computation of the st -ordering.*

Proof: First we show that the drawing is planar. Every edge (v_k, v_{i+1}) is drawn with at most two horizontal lines. We show that we produce no crossing when drawing either horizontal line. This is clear for the first one: As we connect from $c(v_k)$ to a column directly neighbored to it, there is no vertical line that could be crossed.

The second line is drawn when we connect the predecessors of v_{i+1} with v_{i+1} . Let $L(i)$ be the list of columns that contain a temporary endpoint, sorted from left to right. Let c_1, \dots, c_b be the columns of the temporary endpoints of the incoming edges of v_{i+1} . We need to show that c_1, \dots, c_b are consecutive in $L(i)$. Let $G(i)$ be the subgraph induced by v_1, \dots, v_i , embedded as induced by G . Let E_i be the set of edges from $G(i)$ to $G - G(i)$. For an edge in $E(i)$ the endpoint in $G(i)$ must be on the outer-face of $G(i)$, otherwise we had a crossing.

Let P_1 and P_2 be the two paths between s and t on the outer-face. Write the edges of P_j as $\{e_1^j, \dots, e_{l_j}^j\}$, where e_1^j is incident to s and $e_{l_j}^j$ is incident to t . By biconnectivity these two paths have no common edge. Since s is in $G(i)$ and t in $G - G(i)$, both paths must have at least one edge in $E(i)$. Let k_j be minimal such that $e_{k_j}^j$ is in $E(i)$. Sort the edges in $E(i)$ in clockwise order around the outer-face boundary of $G(i)$, starting with $e_{k_1}^1$ and ending with $e_{k_2}^2$ of G .

Figure 4.4: Definition of $e_{k_1}^1$ and $e_{k_2}^2$. Since both edges are on the outer-face, all edges of $E(i)$ lie between them.

We claim that $E(i)$ and $L(i)$ are in correspondance, i.e. the j th element in $E(i)$ has assigned the temporary endpoint that defined the j th element of $L(i)$. We show this by induction on i . With that we have shown that the drawing exactly reflects the planar embedding. Also, by planarity the incoming edges of v_{i+1} must be consecutive in $E(i)$. For if there were another edge between them, then it would not be on the outer-face of $G(i+1)$, a contradiction. So if we show the claim, then also the columns of the temporary endpoints of them are in consecutive order in $L(i)$, and the drawing is planar.

The claim is true for v_1 , since we assigned temporary endpoints in the correct order. Assume it was true after step $i - 1$. The incoming edges of v_i are consecutive in $E(i - 1)$. For any st -ordering the incoming (outgoing) edges of v_i are consecutive in the rotation around v_i [TT87]. Since $E(i - 1)$ and $L(i - 1)$ were in correspondance, we embedded the incoming edges of v_i according to the planar embedding. Since we assigned temporary endpoints according to the planar embedding, after embedding v_i we have the correspondance between $E(i)$ and $L(i)$. \square

Lemma 4.2.6 *The width is $m - n + 1$, the height is $n + \chi(\deg(v_n) = 4)$, and there are $2m - 2n + 3 + \chi(\deg(v_n) = 4)$ bends.*

Proof: The lemma is actually a weaker statement than Lemma 2.2.1 and Lemma 2.2.2 which were proved in the introductory chapter. We only have to check that the changes of Figure 4.1 and Figure 4.2 do not interfere with those proofs, which can be done easily case by case. \square

We can collect all these statements into one theorem.

Theorem 4.1 (Biedl & Kant [BK]) *Let G be a biconnected planar 4-graph with n vertices. Then G can be embedded in an $(n + 1) \times (n + 1)$ -grid with $2n + 4$ bends such that the resulting drawing has no crossings. If $n \geq 7$, every edge has at most 2 bends.*

Previously known results: *This theorem was discovered independently by Liu, Morgana, and Simeone [LMS]. In fact, the results on the grid-size and the number of bends were known even before [St, TT87, TT89]. The results of [LMS] and [St] hold only for simple graphs, though.*

By choice of t , we get a better bound for graphs that are not 4-regular.

Special Case: *If $m \leq 2n - 1$, then the grid-size is $n \times n$ and there are at most $2n + 1$ bends. Every edge is 2-bent.*

An improvement for simple graphs

For simple graphs with $n \geq 3$, an improvement of Lemma 4.2.6 is possible. It may seem a waste to spend a lot of effort on an improvement of a few units. However, it is very useful for non-biconnected graphs later, since here the improvement sums up over all blocks. Biedl and Kant [BK] showed the improvement only for graphs with at least $2n - 1$ edges. We extend it here to any graph.

Assume an st -ordering $\{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ is given. Define l to be the smallest index such that $b = \text{indeg}(v_l) \geq 2$. This exists for $n \geq 3$, since by biconnectivity $\text{indeg}(v_n) \geq 2$. Let v_{i_1}, \dots, v_{i_b} be the predecessors of v_l which are all different by simplicity, and assume $i_1 < \dots < i_b$. If we define a new ordering $\{v_1, \dots, v_{i_b}, v_l, v_{i_b+1}, \dots, v_{l-1}, v_{l+1}, \dots, v_b\}$, then this is also an st -ordering. So we may as well assume $i_b = l - 1$.

By definition of l , all vertices v_i with $i < l$ have $\text{indeg}(v_i) \leq 1$. Since we have an st -ordering, we have $\text{indeg}(v_i) = 1$ for $1 < i < l$, and the vertices v_1, \dots, v_l induce a tree. The idea is to embed two vertices together in one row. We distinguish by the indegree of v_l :

Case 1: $\text{indeg}(v_l) = 2$

We embed v_l and v_{l-1} together as shown in Figure 4.5. To see the improvement, we also show how the embedding with BICONN-PLANAR would have been, both for $\text{deg}(v_{l-1}) = 2$ and $\text{deg}(v_{l-1}) \geq 3$. We see that we save one row and one bend, and in case $\text{deg}(v_{l-1}) \geq 3$ even one row, one column and two bends.

Figure 4.5: The improvement for $\text{indeg}(v_l) = 2$, contrasted with the old embedding.

Case 2: $\text{indeg}(v_l) = 3$

At the time of the embedding of v_{l-1} , there are three significant columns: c_{l-1} , the one that contains the temporary endpoint of the incoming edge of v_{l-1} , and c_l^1 and c_l^2 , the two columns of the other two incoming edges of v_l . We assume that $c_l^1 < c_l^2$ and distinguish by the order of these columns:

Case 2a: c_{l-1} is outside, i.e. the order of the columns is $c_{l-1} < c_l^1 < c_l^2$ or $c_l^1 < c_l^2 < c_{l-1}$.

Quite similar as to the first case, we embed v_l and v_{l-1} together in one row. We save one row and one bend, and in case $\text{deg}(v_{l-1}) \geq 3$ even one row, one column and two bends.

Figure 4.6: The improvement if the columns are in order $c_l^1 < c_{l-1} < c_l^2$.

Case 2b: c_{l-1} is in the middle, i.e. the order of the columns is $c_l^1 - c_{l-1} - c_l^2$.

The improvement cannot be achieved with v_{l-1} in this case. We describe now how to find another vertex for the improvement.

Let $G(l)$ be the graph induced by v_1, \dots, v_l . We find a cycle C in $G(l)$ containing v_{i_1}, v_{i_2} and v_l in the following way: there is a unique path between v_{i_1} and v_{i_2} in $G(l-1)$ (which is a tree). We combine this path with the edges (v_{i_1}, v_l) and (v_{i_2}, v_l) . Let v_{i_0} be the vertex with the smallest st -number in this cycle ($i_0 = i_1$ is possible). See also Figure 4.7.

Since we have a planar graph, we have vertices “inside”, “outside” and “on” the cycle. Since we preserve the planar embedding, and since c_{l-1} is between c_v^1 and c_v^2 , v_{l-1} is inside the cycle.

Lemma 4.2.7 *The vertices inside the cycle induce a path. Each of them has degree 2.*

Proof: By planarity, every neighbor of a vertex inside the cycle is either inside the cycle or on the cycle. Every vertex $\neq v_l$ on the cycle has only one predecessor, and the predecessor is on the cycle, or, for v_{i_0} , outside the cycle. v_l has two predecessors on the cycle, and only one inside the cycle. Altogether, there can be only one vertex inside the cycle that has a successor on the cycle, and this vertex is v_{l-1} .

The vertices inside the cycle induce a forest F , since each has at most one predecessor inside the cycle. Every tree in the forest has some leaves; one of them possibly is a vertex with a predecessor on the cycle, all other leaves are vertices with a successor on the cycle. However, we just showed that only v_{l-1} has a successor on the cycle. Consequently, F has only two leaves, so it is a path and every vertex v on it has $deg_G(v) = 2$. \square

Figure 4.7: The vertices inside the cycle have degree 2 and induce a path.

Now back to our improvement. Let v_{j_1}, \dots, v_{j_k} with $j_1 < \dots < j_k$ be the vertices of the path inside the cycle. There are two subcases, depending on whether the predecessor of v_{j_1} is v_{i_2} .

Case 2b(i): If the predecessor of v_{j_1} is not v_{i_2} , then a change of the st -ordering brings us back to a previous case: All vertices inside the cycle have degree 2. So we can rearrange the vertices to $\{v_1, \dots, v_{i_2-1}, v_{j_1}, \dots, v_{j_k}, v_{i_2}, \dots, v_n\}$, and get an st -ordering. Now, the last predecessor of v_l is v_{i_2} and not $v_{l-1} = v_{j_k}$, which brings us back to Case 2a.

Case 2b(ii): Assume the predecessor of v_{j_1} is v_{i_2} .

v_{i_2} it has a successor on the cycle, and it has the successor v_{j_1} inside the cycle. So $outdeg(v_{i_2}) \geq 2$. By Lemma 4.2.7, v_{i_2} has only one successor, inside the cycle. So by planarity, v_{j_1} must be either the right-most or the left-most successor of v_{i_2} . Consequently, by $deg(v_{j_1}) = 2$, we can place it at the bend that would otherwise have been produced with the embedding of v_{i_2} , and preserve the planar embedding. This saves one unit in height and one bend.

Figure 4.8: The improvement if the predecessor of v_{j_1} is v_{i_2} .

Case 3: $\text{indeg}(v_l) = 4$.

Only the vertex v_n can have indegree 4, so $l = n$. This case is actually irrelevant for the places where we apply this improvement. However, we will treat it for the sake of completeness.

The first $n - 1$ vertices induce a tree, so $G(n - 1)$ has $n - 2$ edges. Adding v_n adds 4 edges, so $m = n + 2$. By $n \geq 3$ and biconnectivity, every vertex must have degree ≥ 2 . Therefore, at most two vertices $\neq v_n$ can have a degree greater than 2, otherwise we had too many edges.

v_n has four predecessors, so it must have one, v_k , which is neither v_1 nor a vertex with degree > 2 . So $\text{deg}(v_k) = 2$. We want to place v_k at a bend that otherwise would have been produced when embedding v_n . Since we have two possible placements for v_n , this is always possible. We save one row for v_k and one bend.

Figure 4.9: The improvement if $\text{indeg}(v_l) = 4$, contrasted with the old embedding.

Definition 9 *The vertex v^* involved in the improvement is the vertex v_{l-1} in the cases (1) and (2a), the vertex v_{i_2} in case (2bi), the vertex v_{j_1} in case (2bii), and the vertex v_k in case (3). In either case we have $v^* \neq v_n$.*

Lemma 4.2.8 *With the improvement, we get a grid of width $m - n + \chi(\text{deg}(v^*) = 2)$, height $n - 1 + \chi(\text{deg}(v_n) = 4)$, and with $2m - 2n + 1 + \chi(\text{deg}(v^*) = 2) + \chi(\text{deg}(v_n) = 4)$ bends.*

Proof: We have to show in comparison with Lemma 4.2.6, the improvement saves one unit of height, $\chi(\text{deg}(v^*) \geq 3)$ units of width, and $1 + \chi(\text{deg}(v^*) \geq 3)$ bends.

With BICONN-PLANAR, v^* has been embedded in a separate row (hence the seemingly stupid constructions in Figure 4.1 and 4.2). With the improvement, v^* is embedded in the row of some other vertex, so we save one row.

The claim on the width and the bends can be seen directly from the construction. \square

To be able to use this improvement for the scheme CONN, we have to make sure that the last vertex is still drawn as final vertex.

Lemma 4.2.9 *If $\text{deg}(v_n) \leq 3$, then it is drawn as final vertex.*

Proof: Nothing changes in the drawing of v_n if $l < n$. So assume $l = n$. If $\text{deg}(v_n) = 2$, then it is drawn on one row with v_{n-1} , but still with right angle and in the last row. It is possible that v_n was drawn on the left side, we then rotate the drawing to have v_n drawn as final vertex.

If $\text{deg}(v_n) = 3$, then directly from the construction one checks that the column of v_n is unused above v_n . \square

One other advantage for simple graphs is that we can be more explicit which graphs can be drawn with 2 bends per edge. There is only one planar simple 4-regular graph with ≤ 6 vertices, namely, the octahedron. For this graph Even and Granot [EG] have shown that it is not possible to embed it with at most two bends per edge.

Figure 4.10: The octahedron and the drawing by BICONN-PLANAR.

Putting all this together we arrive at:

Theorem 4.2 (Biedl & Kant [BK]) *Let G be a biconnected planar simple 4-graph with n vertices. Then G has a planar drawing in an $n \times n$ -grid with $2n + 2$ bends. Every edge is 2-bent, unless the graph is the octahedron.*

Proof: After the improvement step the height is n by Lemma 4.2.8. If G is 4-regular, then v^* has degree 4, the width is $m - n = n$ and the number of bends is $2m - 2n + 4 - 2 = 2n + 2$ by Lemma 4.2.8. If G is not 4-regular, the claim is true by the special case of Theorem 4.1. \square

For future reference, we specify one special case:

Special Case: *Let G be a biconnected planar 4-graph with n vertices. Let $v \in V$ with $\deg(v) \leq 3$ be given. Then G has a planar drawing in an $(n - 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid with $2n - 1$ bends. All edges are 2-bent.*

Proof: We chose v as last vertex of the st -ordering, so $\deg(v_n) \leq 3$. Since we applied the improvement step, the height is $n - 1$ by Lemma 4.2.8. If $m = 2n - 1$, then there is no vertex $\neq v$ with degree 2, and $\deg(v^*) \geq 3$. So the width is $m - n = n - 1$ and there are $2m - 2n + 1 \leq 2n - 1$ bends. If $m \leq 2n - 2$, then the width is $m - n + 1 \leq n - 1$ and the number of bends is $2m - 2n + 2 \leq 2n - 1$. \square

4.2.2 Connected graphs

For planar graphs, applying scheme CONN in combination with BICONN-PLANAR leads to about the same results in terms of grid-size and bends as for non-planar graphs. For simple graphs, this was shown by Biedl and Kant [BK]. We present their result and extend it to non-simple graphs.

Apply CONN with the following parameters:

- If there exists a vertex v with $\deg(v) \leq 3$, then choose the outer-most block B_0 to contain this vertex, and define $\text{parent}(B_0) = v$. Otherwise, choose B_0 to be a leaf of \mathcal{B} .
- If $v = \text{parent}(B_0)$ is defined, choose a face F incident to v as the outer-face of G . Otherwise, choose a face incident to the unique cutvertex of B_0 as the outer-face of G .
- Draw loops in a 1×1 -grid with 3 bends.

- Draw biconnected graphs with algorithm BICONN-PLANAR, with the following parameters:
 - Choose the last vertex t as in CONN-NONPLANAR, i.e. define t to be the parent-vertex $parent(B)$, if it is defined. Otherwise, set it to be a critical cutvertex, if $cr(B) > 0$. Otherwise, set it to be some vertex of minimal degree.
 - For each block look whether there is a face F incident to both the vertex t chosen above, and to a critical cutvertex. If so, change the embedding of B such that this face is the outer-face of B , and choose s to be this critical cutvertex. Otherwise, choose some face F incident to t as the outer-face of B , and choose s to be some vertex $\neq t$ on F .
 - Apply the improvement if the graph is simple.
- A proper drawing in this case is a planar drawing such that all critical cutvertices are drawn with right angle.

We refer to this algorithm as CONN-PLANAR.

We will from now on assume that the outer-face is fixed, i.e. that all vertices that are on the outer-face after the above steps are also on the outer-face of the final drawing (this agrees with the changes necessary to obtain a pl - st -ordering). We have two different cases: either there is a vertex of degree less than 4 on this outer-face. Then the outer-most block has a parent-vertex. Or, the graph is 4-regular. We analyze the obtained size similar as in the non-planar case.

Lemma 4.2.10 *Assume B is a block that is not a bridge, and the parent-vertex of B is defined. Then its correction terms are $\Phi_w(B) \leq 1$, $\Phi_h(B) \leq 1$ and $\Phi_b(B) \leq 2$.*

Proof: We have to show that B is embedded in an $n \times n$ -grid with $2n + 1 - cr(B)$ bends. We have two cases to consider: either B was a loop, or it was embedded with BICONN-PLANAR. If it was a loop, it is embedded in a 1×1 -grid with 3 bends. Since $parent(B)$ is the only vertex in this block, there is no critical cutvertex, and the claim holds.

If B was embedded with BICONN-PLANAR we chose $t = parent(B)$, so $deg(t) \leq 3$. With that, we get an $(m - n + 1) \times n$ -grid with $2m - 2n + 3$ bends. If we have cr critical cutvertices, then we add up to cr units of width and cr bends to get a proper drawing. On the other side, we know that $m \leq 2n - 1 - cr$ by the corollary of Lemma 2.3.4. So the width of the proper drawing is at most $cr + (2n - 1 - cr) - n + 1 = n$. The number of bends is at most $cr + 2(2n - 1 - cr) - 2n + 3 = 2n - cr + 1$. \square

Lemma 4.2.11 *If the outer-most block B_0 is not a bridge, then $\Phi_w(B_0) \leq 1$, $\Phi_h(B_0) \leq 1$ and $\Phi_b(B_0) \leq 2 + \chi(G \text{ is } 4\text{-regular})$.*

Proof: If G is not 4-regular, then B_0 had a parent-vertex defined, and we can apply the previous lemma. Otherwise, B_0 is a leaf in the blocktree, and the proof is exactly the same as in Lemma 3.1.5 on Page 24. \square

In the worst case, we need these correction terms for every block.

Corollary 4.1 *If bl is the number of blocks in G , then the sums of the correction terms are*

$$\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_w(B) \leq bl, \sum_{B \in G} \Phi_h(B) \leq bl, \sum_{B \in G} \Phi_b(B) \leq 2bl + \chi(G \text{ is } 4\text{-regular}).$$

We apply this corollary on the general analysis of the merging scheme. Therefore, we have to demand that the graph has no bridges.

Lemma 4.2.12 *If G has no bridges, then CONN-PLANAR embeds G planarily in a $2n \times 2n$ -grid with $4n + 2$ bends. If a vertex with degree ≤ 3 is on the outer-face, then CONN-PLANAR embeds G in a $(2n - 1) \times (2n - 1)$ -grid with $4n - 1$ bends.*

Proof: By Lemma 2.3.3 the width is $n - 1 + \sum_{B \in G} \Phi_w(B)$, so by Corollary 4.1 the width is at most $n - 1 + bl$. The number of blocks is at most $n + 1$ for a graph without bridges. This shows the first claim for the width. The calculation for the height and the number of bends are similar.

If a vertex of degree ≤ 3 is on the outer-face, then G is not 4-regular, and the number of blocks is only n (Lemma 3.1.7). This shows the second claim for the width and height. Also $\Phi_b(B_0) \leq 2$, so $\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_b(B) = 2bl$, and the number of bends is as stated. \square

Now we add the treatment of bridges. As opposed to non-planar graphs we cannot simply get rid of bridges by adding edges in a planar graph – this might introduce crossings. Therefore, we have to embed them directly.

Theorem 4.3 *Let G be a planar 4-graph with n vertices. Then G can be embedded planarily in a $2n \times 2n$ -grid with $4n + 2$ bends. If G has a vertex of degree ≤ 3 on the outer-face, it can be embedded in a $(2n - 1) \times (2n - 1)$ -grid with $4n - 1$ bends.*

Proof: By choice of the outer-face, we have a vertex of degree ≤ 3 on the outer-face if and only if the graph is not 4-regular. We proceed by induction on the number of bridges br . The case $br = 0$ is done with the above lemma.

Assume G contains a bridge (v_1, v_2) , and we split G into G_1 and G_2 . G_1 has less bridges than G , so it can be embedded in a grid of width and height $2n(G_1)$ with $4n(G_1) + 2$ bends. G_2 has less bridges than G and v_2 is a vertex on the outer-face of G_2 with $\deg_{G_2}(v_2) \leq 3$. So G_2 can be embedded, with v_2 as final vertex, in a grid of width and height $2n(G_2) - 1$ and $4n(G_2) - 1$ bends.

Merging G_2 into G_1 adds one unit of width or one unit of height, and no bends. That gives a drawing of G of height $1 + 2n(G_1) + 2n(G_2) - 1 = 2n$ and width $1 + 2n(G_1) + 2n(G_2) - 1 = 2n$. There are $4n(G_1) + 2 + 4n(G_2) - 1 = 4n + 1$ bends.

If a vertex of degree less than 4 is on the outer-face, then G_1 can be embedded in a smaller grid with fewer bends. The calculations are similar. \square

Remark: *Since we need only either a unit of width or a unit of height for the merging, the drawing is actually smaller in the presence of bridges. By induction one can show that the half-perimeter is $4n - 2 - br$, and there are $4n - 1 - br$ bends, where br is the number of bridges.*

Remark: *In the worst case, the bounds are almost the same for non-planar and planar drawings. Usually, non-planar drawings will be much smaller. Note that the sums of the correction terms are determined by the number of leaves in the blocktree in the non-planar case, while it is determined by the number of blocks in the planar case. In the worst case, those two numbers differ by only one, but usually the number of leaves is significantly less than the number of blocks.*

Multi-graphs

We can achieve improvement if the graph has no loops. Namely, in a multi-graph a block has positive correction terms only if it has some vertices that are not critical cutvertices.

Lemma 4.2.13 *Assume we have a block B which is not a bridge, $v = \text{parent}(B)$ is defined and $\deg(v) = 2$. Assume further $n \leq 2 + cr(B)$. Then all correction terms are non-positive.*

Proof: We must have $n \geq 2$, since we have no loop. Also, we must have $n \geq 1 + cr(B)$ since v is not a critical cutvertex. The claim is easily proved if $cr = cr(B) = 0$: We have two vertices, and, by $\deg(v) = 2$, a double edge. This can be embedded in a 1×1 -grid with 2 bends.

So assume $cr \geq 1$. We claim that one critical cutvertex is a neighbor of v . This is clear if $n = 1 + cr$, since v must have one neighbor, and there are only critical cutvertices in the graph, except for v . So assume $n = 2 + cr$ and $cr > 0$. We have one vertex that is neither v nor a critical cutvertex, call it w . If v has no neighbor that is a critical cutvertex, then w is the only neighbor of v . But with $cr > 0$ we have $n \geq 3$ and w is a cutvertex; a contradiction to biconnectivity.

So one neighbor of v , say v_1 , is a critical cutvertex. v and v_1 are on a common face, and we chose a planar embedding of B such that v and v_1 are on the outer-face. We took v_1 as first and v as last vertex for the st -ordering for BICONN-PLANAR. This saves one unit of height and one bend at v_1 , and we get an $(m - n + 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid and $2m - 2n + 2$ bends.

Since v_1 was drawn as first vertex, it is already drawn with right angle, so we need to add only $cr - 1$ units of width and $cr - 1$ bends to get a proper drawing of B . So the width is at most $cr - 1 + (2n - cr - 1) - n + 1 = n - 1$ and the number of bends is at most $cr - 1 + 2(2n - cr - 1) - 2n + 2 = 2n - cr - 1$, so all correction terms are at most 0. \square

Lemma 4.2.14 *Assume G has no bridges, and a vertex v with $\deg(v) \leq 2$ is on the outer-face. Then $\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_w(B) \leq \frac{n}{3}$, $\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_h(B) \leq \frac{n}{3}$, and $\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_b(B) \leq \frac{2}{3}n$.*

Proof: We chose the outer-most block B_0 such that it contains v , and defined $\text{parent}(B_0) = v$. So every block has a parent-vertex. Moreover, since we have no bridges, for every block the parent-vertex has degree 2 in the block.

The claim is now immediate with the above lemma: Every block B of G where the correction terms are positive has at least $3 + cr(B)$ vertices. We assign the three vertices that are not critical cutvertices to B . Then we have assigned 3 vertices to every block without counting a vertex twice, so there are at most $\frac{n}{3}$ blocks with positive correction terms.

Since each block has a parent-vertex, a block B with positive correction terms has $\Phi_w(B) \leq 1$, $\Phi_h(B) \leq 1$, and $\Phi_b(B) \leq 2$ (Lemma 4.2.10). This gives the result. \square

Lemma 4.2.15 *Assume G has no bridges, and a vertex v with $\deg(v) \leq 3$ is on the outer-face. $\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_w(B) \leq \frac{n}{3} + 1$, $\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_h(B) \leq \frac{n}{3}$, and $\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_b(B) \leq \frac{2}{3}n$.*

Proof: The proof is almost the same as for the above lemma, with the exception that the outer-most block B_0 now may have a larger correction term. Namely, the B_0 may have less than $3 + cr(B_0)$ vertices and still need correction terms, since its parent-vertex may have degree 3.

Reinspect the proof of Lemma 4.2.13. We used $\deg(v) = 2$ only in the case $cr = 0$. So only if B_0 is a triple edge do we actually need an increase. However, a triple edge can be embedded in an 2×1 -grid with 4 bends. None of the vertices of the triple edge is a cutvertex (otherwise we had a bridge). So $G = B_0$ is embedded in an $n \times (n - 1)$ -grid with $2n$ bends, and the correction term is 0 for the height and 1 for the width and the bends. By $n = 2$ we are done. \square

Now we need to include the possibility that the outer-most block has no parent-vertex.

Lemma 4.2.16 *Assume G has no bridges. Then G can be embedded in a $\frac{4}{3}n \times \frac{4}{3}n$ -grid with $\frac{8}{3}n + 2$ bends. If a vertex v with $\deg(v) \leq 3$ is on the outer-face, then the drawing has height $\frac{4}{3}n - 1$, width $\frac{4}{3}n - \chi(\deg(v) = 2)$, and $\frac{8}{3}n - 1$ bends.*

Proof: If a vertex v with $\deg(v) \leq 3$ is on the outer-face, then apply Lemma 4.2.15 to the general analysis (Lemma 2.3.3) to get the result. So assume G is 4-regular.

Let B_0 be the outer-most block, and let v be its unique cutvertex. We chose the planar embedding of G such that v was on the outer-face, and v is chosen as last vertex for the drawing of B_0 with BICONN-PLANAR. Since $\deg_{B_0}(v) \leq 3$, B_0 is embedded in an $n(B_0) \times n(B_0)$ -grid with $2n(B_0) + 1$ bends.

Let B_1 be the unique other block containing v (it is unique since we have no bridge), and let G_1 be the graph of the subtree of \mathcal{B} rooted at B_1 . We know $n(G_1) + n(B_0) = n + 1$, since v is counted in both graphs. v has degree 2 in both B_0 and G_1 , since we have no bridge. Also, v is on the outer-face of G_1 , so G_1 can be embedded in a grid of width and height $\frac{4}{3}n(G_1) - 1$ with $\frac{8}{3}n(G_1) - 1$ bends, with v as final vertex.

v is drawn with right angle in either drawing. So we can merge the drawings without adding extra columns. We get a width and height of

$$n(B_0) + \frac{4}{3}n(G_1) - 1 = (n - n(G_1)) + \frac{4}{3}n(G_1) \leq \frac{4}{3}(n - n(G_1)) + \frac{4}{3}n(G_1) = \frac{4}{3}n.$$

The number of bends is at most

$$\begin{aligned} 2n(B_0) + 1 + \frac{8}{3}n(G_1) - 1 &= 2(n - n(G_1) + 1) + \frac{8}{3}n(G_1) \\ &\leq \frac{8}{3}(n - n(G_1)) + 2 + \frac{8}{3}n(G_1) = \frac{8}{3}n + 2. \end{aligned}$$

□

The drawing achieved with CONN-PLANAR is 2-bent for multigraphs.

Lemma 4.2.17 *If G is not biconnected, then the proper drawing of a block B is 2-bent.*

Proof: We had a very similar statement in Lemma 3.1.11. There, the main argument was that the incident edges of a vertex of degree 2 are drawn 1-bent, since $\deg(s) \leq 3$ and $\deg(t) \leq 3$.

This argument does not carry over, since we choose s differently in CONN-PLANAR. So it is possible that $cr(B) > 0$, but $\deg(s) = 4$. In this case, the edge at the bottom connection of s has at least two bends, regardless of the degree of the other endpoint.

Assume that the other endpoint of this edge was a critical cutvertex v_1 that was drawn straight, therefore $v_1 \neq t$. Since we reflect the planar embedding, v_1 was on the outer-face of B . But also t was on the outer-face of B , so t and v_1 were on a common face. This is a contradiction to the choice of s : we do not choose a vertex of degree 4 as s , if there is a critical cutvertex on a common face with t .

So all edges incident to a critical cutvertex are drawn 1-bent with BICONN-PLANAR when applied with the parameters given for CONN-PLANAR. So the proper drawing achieved after adding the extra bends is 2-bent. □

Now finally, we include bridges and wrap everything together in one theorem.

Theorem 4.4 *Let G be a planar multi-4-graph with n vertices. Then G can be embedded planarily in a $\frac{4}{3}n \times \frac{4}{3}n$ -grid with $\frac{8}{3}n + 2$ bends. If G is not 4-regular, then G can be embedded planarily in a grid of width $\frac{4}{3}n$, height $\frac{4}{3}n - 1$, and with $\frac{8}{3}n - 1$ bends. Every edge is 2-bent.*

Proof: We know that the drawing is 2-bent by Lemma 4.2.17. By choice of the outer-face, we have a vertex of degree ≤ 3 on the outer-face if and only if the graph is not 4-regular. We proceed by induction on the number of bridges br . The case $br = 0$ is done with Lemma 4.2.16.

Assume G contains a bridge (v_1, v_2) , and we split G into G_1 and G_2 . G_1 has less bridges than G , so it can be embedded in a grid of width and height $\frac{4}{3}n(G_1)$ with $\frac{8}{3}n(G_1) + 2$ bends. G_2 has a vertex of degree ≤ 3 on the outer-face, so it can be embedded in a grid of height $\frac{4}{3}n(G_2) - 1$, width $\frac{4}{3}n(G_2)$ and with $\frac{8}{3}n(G_2) - 1$ bends.

If for merging G_2 we use the connection *left* or *right* of v_1 , then merging G_2 into G_1 rotates the drawing of G_2 , and switches width and height of G_2 . It also adds one unit of width. If we used the connection *top* or *bottom*, we add one unit of height. Either way, we add no bend and get a drawing of G of height and width $\frac{4}{3}n(G_1) + \frac{4}{3}n(G_2)$ with $\frac{8}{3}n(G_1) + 2 + \frac{8}{3}n(G_2) - 1$ bends, which proves the first claim since $n(G_1) + n(G_2) = n$.

If a vertex of degree less than 4 is on the outer-face, then G_1 can be embedded in a smaller grid with fewer bends. The calculations are similar. \square

Remark: *For multi-graphs, the half-perimeter does not reduce in the presence of bridges. However, by induction one can show that the number of bends is at most $\frac{8}{3}n + 2 - br$, where br is the number of bridges.*

Simple graphs

CONN-PLANAR does even better for simple graphs and achieves the same grid-size as for non-planar graphs. This was shown by Biedl and Kant [BK].

Lemma 4.2.18 *Assume B is a simple block which is not a bridge, and the parent-vertex of B is defined. Then its correction terms are non-negative.*

Proof: The parent-vertex v has $\deg(v) \leq 3$. We applied BICONN-PLANAR with v as last vertex and with the improvement step. There are two possibilities, depending on whether the vertex v^* involved in the improvement had degree 2. Assume $\deg(v^*) \geq 3$. Then we saved two bends and one unit in each width and height. So we got an $(m - n) \times (n - 1)$ -grid and $2m - 2n + 1$ bends. We also had $m \leq 2n - cr - 1$ by the corollary of Lemma 2.3.4. To get a proper drawing of B , we have to add cr units of width and cr bends. This gives a width of $cr + m - n \leq n - 1$ and $cr + 2m - 2n + 1 \leq m \leq 2n - 1 - cr$ bends.

Assume $\deg(v^*) = 2$, so we had an $(m - n + 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid and $2m - 2n + 2$ bends. There are two subcases, depending on whether v^* was a critical cutvertex. If it was, then it is now drawn with right angle, and we have to add only $cr - 1$ units of width and $cr - 1$ bends. This gives a width of $cr - 1 + m - n + 1 \leq n - 1$ and $cr - 1 + 2m - 2n + 2 \leq 2n - 1 - cr$ bends.

If $\deg(v^*) = 2$, but v^* was not a critical cutvertex, then we get a better bound on m . We have $1 + cr$ vertices of degree 2. Furthermore, v^* is not the last vertex, so $\text{parent}(B)$ is one different vertex of degree ≤ 3 , and $m \leq 2n - cr - 2$ by Lemma 2.3.4. Therefore the width of the proper drawing is at most $cr + m - n + 1 \leq n - 1$ and the number of bends is at most $cr + 2m - 2n + 2 \leq 2n - 2 - cr$.

In either of the cases, we now have a drawing of B with grid-size $(n - 1) \times (n - 1)$ and at most $2n - 1 - cr$ bends, so all correction terms are at most 0. \square

Lemma 4.2.19 *Assume \mathcal{B} was non-trivial, and the outer-most block B_0 is not a bridge. Then its correction terms are $\Phi_w(B_0) \leq 0$, $\Phi_h(B_0) \leq 0$ and $\Phi_b(B_0) \leq \chi(\text{parent}(B_0) \text{ is undefined})$.*

Proof: If the parent-vertex of B_0 is defined, then we are done by the above lemma. So assume the graph was 4-regular. We need to find a drawing in an $(n-1) \times (n-1)$ -grid with $2n - cr(B)$ bends.

We chose the outer-most block B_0 to be a leaf of the blocktree. t was chosen as the cutvertex in B_0 , so $\deg_{B_0}(t) \leq 3$. We applied the improvement, so B_0 is drawn in an $(n-1) \times (n-1)$ -grid with $2n - 1$ bends (Lemma 4.2.8). Moreover, if $\deg(t) = 2$, it was drawn with right angle. Since B , being a leaf of \mathcal{B} , has no other critical cutvertex than possibly t , the drawing is a proper drawing. The claims are now true since $cr(B) \leq 1$. \square

Lemma 4.2.20 *Assume G has no bridges. Then it is embedded in an $(n-1) \times (n-1)$ -grid with $2n$ bends. If there is a vertex with degree less than 4 on the outer-face, then there are only $2n - 1$ bends.*

Proof: The claim is true, since with Lemma 4.2.18 and 4.2.19 we know

$$\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_w(B) \leq 0, \sum_{B \in G} \Phi_h(B) \leq 0, \sum_{B \in G} \Phi_b(B) \leq \chi(\text{parent}(B_0) \text{ is undefined}),$$

and we can apply this on Lemma 2.3.3. \square

Now we need to extend these results to graphs with bridges.

Theorem 4.5 (Biedl & Kant [BK]) *Let G be a not biconnected planar simple 4-graph with n vertices. Then G can be embedded planarily in an $(n-1) \times (n-1)$ -grid with $2n$ bends. If G is not 4-regular, then there are only $2n - 1$ bends.*

Proof: We know that the drawing is 2-bent by Lemma 4.2.17. By choice of the outer-face, we have a vertex of degree ≤ 3 on the outer-face if and only if the graph is not 4-regular. We proceed by induction on the number of bridges br . The case $br = 0$ is done with the above lemma.

If we have a bridge, then removing it splits the graph into two graphs, G_1 and G_2 . G_1 can be embedded in a grid of width and height $n(G_1) - 1$ with $2n(G_1)$ bends. G_2 has the endpoint v_2 of the bridge on the outer-face. Since $\deg_{G_2}(v_2) \leq 3$, it can be drawn with width and height $n(G_2) - 1$ and $2n(G_2) - 1$ bends.

Merging the two drawings costs one unit in width or height, and no bends. So the final drawing has height $1 + n(G_1) - 1 + n(G_2) - 1 = n - 1$, width $1 + n(G_1) - 1 + n(G_2) - 1 = n - 1$ and $2n(G_1) + 2n(G_2) - 1 = 2n - 1$ bends.

If a vertex of degree less than 4 is on the outer-face, then G_1 can be embedded in a smaller grid with fewer bends. The calculations are similar. \square

Previously known results: *This theorem is a slight improvement over the previously known grid-size of $n \times n$ [St, TT87]. The previously best known bounds on the number of bends were $\frac{12}{5}n + 4$ [TT89] and $\frac{7}{3}n$ [LMS].*

Remark: *Since we need only either a unit of width or a unit of height for the merging, the drawing is actually smaller in the presence of bridges. By induction one can show that the half-perimeter is $2n - 2 - br$, where br is the number of bridges.*

4.3 Algorithms for plane graphs

In this section we deal with plane graphs, i.e. we are given a planar graph where both the combinatorial embedding and the outer-face is specified. We want to find an orthogonal drawing such that the given combinatorial embedding and outer-face are exactly reflected. Such algorithms are useful if a user already has a picture of the graph, and wants to convert it into an orthogonal drawing without destroying his mental map.

4.3.1 Biconnected graphs

Remember that for BICONN-PLANAR, we had a statement saying that “we exactly reflect the planar embedding that we had after we chose the st -ordering” (Lemma 4.2.5). So if we choose s and t on the given outer-face, and compute the st -ordering without changing the combinatorial embedding, we automatically get a plane drawing.

Apply BICONN with the following parameters:

- Choose s and t on the outer-face.
- Choose an st -ordering without changing the embedding.
- Assign temporary endpoints according to the given combinatorial embedding.

We refer to this algorithm as BICONN-PLANE. With Lemma 4.2.5 and 4.2.6 we get:

Theorem 4.6 *Let G be a biconnected plane 4-graph with n vertices. G has a plane drawing in an $(n + 1) \times (n + 1)$ -grid with at most $2m - 2n + 4$ bends.*

Previously known results: *The grid-size was known before [TT87], and so was the worst case of the number of bends, namely, $2n + 4$ [TT89].*

Remark: *This theorem is optimal: there exists a biconnected graph that an $(n + 1) \times (n + 1)$ -grid and $2n + 4$ bends (Theorem 4.14).*

If we have a vertex of degree less than 4 on the outer-face, then we can choose it as t and do better:

Special Case: *Let G be a biconnected plane 4-graph with n vertices. Let $v \in V$ with $\deg(v) \leq 3$ be on the outer-face. G has a plane drawing in an $n \times n$ -grid with at most $2n + 1$ bends.*

We get an interesting corollary from Theorem 4.6. Tamassia [Ta87] gave an algorithm that computes for a plane graph a drawing with the minimum number of bends. By the results of Tamassia and Tollis [TT89] it was clear that the number of bends can never be worse than $2n + 4$ for a biconnected graph. But to the author’s knowledge nothing was known about the grid-size achieved with this algorithm. We show now such bounds.

Theorem 4.7 *The algorithm of Tamassia [Ta87] embeds every biconnected plane 4-graph in an $(n + 1) \times (n + 1)$ -grid with the optimal number of bends; and the number of bends is at most $2m - 2n + 4$.*

Proof: We know that BICONN-PLANE embeds every plane 4-graph with $2m - 2n + 4$ bends. Since the algorithm of Tamassia achieves the optimal number, it can never do worse than that.

Now, by Theorem 2.1, if the drawing has b bends, then the width and the height each are at most $\frac{1}{2}b + 2n - m - 1$. Since $b \leq 2m - 2n + 4$, this gives a width and height of at most $m - n + 2 + 2n - m - 1 = n + 1$. \square

Simple graphs

Nowhere in the improvement step for simple planar graphs (Page 38) did we change the combinatorial embedding. Hence, we immediately get a better result for simple graphs.

Theorem 4.8 *Let G be a biconnected plane simple 4-graph with n vertices. Then G has a plane drawing in an $n \times n$ -grid with at most $2n + 2$ bends.*

Previously known results: *The results on the grid-size were known before [St], while the number of bends is a slight improvement over the bound of $2n + 4$ shown by both Storer [St] and Tamassia and Tollis [TT89].*

Again, we have the special case of graphs where a vertex of lower degree is on the outer-face.

Special Case: *Let G be a biconnected plane 4-graph with n vertices. Let $v \in V$ with $\deg(v) \leq 3$ be given and on the outer-face. Then G has a plane drawing in an $(n - 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid with at most $2n - 1$ bends.*

4.3.2 Connected graphs

Both Storer [St] and Tamassia and Tollis [TT87, TT89] indicated a method how to use their algorithm for biconnected graphs to also draw graphs that are not biconnected. The problem is that for non-biconnected graphs their algorithm does not necessarily reflect the combinatorial embedding of the biconnected components – this can be seen already since the achieved grid-size of $n \times n$ is less than the lower bound that will be given in Section 4.4.1. We now present an algorithm which indeed produces plane drawings of plane non-biconnected graphs. To our knowledge, no such algorithm has been known before.

Apply the merging scheme CONN with the following parameters:

- The outer-most block is chosen to be a block on the outer-face. If the outer-face contains a vertex v of degree less than 4, then the outer-most block is chosen as to contain v , and define v to be the parent-vertex of it.
- If the outer-most block is a loop enclosing the graph, then draw this loop in a 1×2 -grid with 4 bends, such that the vertex is drawn straight.
- All other loops are drawn in a 1×1 -grid with 3 bends.
- To draw a block B that is not a loop, employ the algorithm BICONN-PLANE with the following parameters.
 - If $\text{parent}(B)$ is defined, choose it to be t . For the outer-most block, choose t to be a vertex of minimal degree on the outer-face of B .
 - Choose s to be a vertex different from t on the outer-face of B .
 - If B is simple and $\text{cr}(B) = 0$, apply the improvement step.
 - If $\text{cr}(B) > 0$, then all critical cutvertices are drawn straight using the connections *top* and *bottom*, as follows:
 - * For all vertices $\neq s, t$ this is achieved automatically, since BICONN-PLANE draws vertices of degree 2 straight using the top and bottom connection. Also, the improvement was not applied in the presence of critical cutvertices.
 - * If B had only two vertices, then draw it in a 1×2 -grid such that all critical cutvertices are drawn straight.

- * So assume $n \geq 3$. If s is a critical cutvertex, then it has degree 2. The two neighbors of s must be different by biconnectivity. So embed s in the same row as v_2 . This adds one bend, but no height.
- * t can be a critical cutvertex only for the outer-most block. In this case, draw it straight by adding one extra unit of height and one bend.

Figure 4.11: The special drawings if either of v_1 and v_n is a critical cutvertex. One can see that Lemma 4.2.6 holds unchanged if v_n is not a critical cutvertex and $\deg(v_n) \leq 3$. Otherwise, we have at most an $(m - n + 1) \times (n + 1)$ -grid and $2m - 2n + 4$ bends.

- If a cutvertex v_1 is drawn straight, and the drawing is converted into one with a right angle (Figure 2.8 on Page 14), then there are two choices for the placement of v_1 . Do this choice as dictated by the planar embedding.
- A proper drawing in this case means a plane drawing where all critical cutvertices are drawn with right angle, but the angle is in such a way that the subgraph is merged to the correct side, according to the combinatorial embedding.
- If a subgraph is connected by a bridge, then check whether one connection is free such that the embedding is reflected. If it is not, add one extra unit in width and change the drawing, so that such a connection is free (see Figure 4.12).

Figure 4.12: How to cut for a bridge when the combinatorial embedding is fixed.

We refer to this algorithm as CONN-PLANE.

Lemma 4.3.1 *The combinatorial embedding is exactly reflected.*

Proof: Since every critical cutvertex is drawn straight using the connections *top* and *bottom*, we add one column and one bend for each. With that, we have the choice where to place the critical cutvertex on the newly produced bends, i.e. whether to add its subgraph to the right or to the left. We do this according to the combinatorial embedding, so we reflect it exactly with our orthogonal drawing.

For bridges, preserving the combinatorial embedding is ensured due to the special merging shown in Figure 4.12. \square

Now we need to analyze the size of the correction terms.

Lemma 4.3.2 *Assume B is a block that is not a bridge, and the parent-vertex of B is defined. Then its correction terms are $\Phi_h(B) \leq 1$, $\Phi_w(B) \leq 1$ and $\Phi_b(B) \leq 2$.*

Proof: The proof is the same as the proof in the planar case (Lemma 4.2.10). We only have to make sure that the above named changes interfere with this proof. Since $\text{parent}(B)$ is defined, t is chosen to be $\text{parent}(B)$. The only change concerns s if $\text{deg}(s) = 2$ and if s was a critical cutvertex. But we only used that the drawing is an $(m - n + 1) \times n$ -grid with $2m - 2n + 3$ bends. This claim holds since $\text{deg}(t) \leq 3$; regardless of the special placement of s . \square

If we have a vertex of degree less than 4 on the outer-face, then all blocks have a parent-vertex. Assuming we have no bridge, the sum of the correction terms of the width and height is at most the number blocks bl . The correction term for the bends is at most $2bl$. We can combine this with the general analysis of Lemma 2.3.3 and get the following result.

Lemma 4.3.3 *Let G be plane graph without bridges with bl blocks, and let a vertex of v with $\text{deg}(v) \leq 3$ be on the outer-face. Then G can be embedded in a grid of width and height $n - 1 + bl$ with $2n - 1 + 2bl$ blocks.*

We now consider the outer-most case and the case of merging bridges, to get the grid-size for all graphs.

Lemma 4.3.4 *If the outer-most block B_0 is not a bridge, its correction terms are $\Phi_w(B_0) \leq 2$, $\Phi_h(B_0) \leq 2$ and $\Phi_b(B_0) \leq 5$.*

Proof: If B_0 is a loop, we embedded it in a 1×2 -grid with 4 bends, and it has at most one critical cutvertex. So this is a drawing of width $n(B_0) - cr(B_0) + 1$, height $n(B_0) + 1$ with $2n(B_0) - 2cr(B_0) + 4$ bends.

The same bound holds if B_0 was embedded with BICONN-PLANE: We get a drawing with height $n(B_0) + 1$, width $m(B_0) - n(B_0) + 1$ and with $2m(B_0) - 2n(B_0) + 4$ bends (this holds whether or not t is a critical cutvertex). B_0 has at most $2n - cr(B_0)$ edges by Lemma 2.3.4. This gives a drawing in a grid of width $n(B_0) - cr(B_0) + 1$, height $n(B_0) + 1$ with $2n(B_0) - 2cr(B_0) + 4$ bends.

Converting either drawing into a proper drawing adds $cr(B_0)$ units of width and $cr(B_0)$ bends. So it gives a proper drawing of width and height $n(B_0) + 1$ with $2n(B_0) - cr(B_0) + 4$ bends, which proves the claim. \square

Lemma 4.3.5 *Let G be a plane graph with bl blocks that are not bridges. Then G can be embedded in an $(n + bl) \times (n + bl)$ -grid with at most $2n + 2 + 2bl$ bends. If a vertex of degree ≤ 3 is on the outer-face, then the height and width is $n + bl - 1$ and there are at most $2n - 1 + 2bl$ bends.*

Proof: We proceed by induction on the number of bridges br . Assume first $br = 0$. By Lemma 4.3.3 nothing is to show if a vertex of degree ≤ 3 is on the outer-face. If there is no such vertex, then with Lemma 4.3.2 and Lemma 4.3.4 the sums of the correction terms increase to $bl + 1$ for the width and height and to $2bl + 3$ for the number of bends. This proves the claim by the general analysis (Lemma 2.3.3).

Assume G has a bridge (v_1, v_2) and let G_1 and G_2 be the graphs resulting from removing the bridge. Let $bl(i)$ be the number of blocks that are not bridges in G_i , then $bl(1) + bl(2) = bl$.

G_i has less bridges than G , so we can apply induction. Embed G_1 by induction in a grid of width and height $n(G_1) + bl(1)$ and $2n(G_1) + 2 + bl(1)$ bends. v_2 is on the outer-face of the induced embedding of G_2 , so $deg_{G_2}(v_2) \leq 3$, and by induction embed G_2 with v_2 as final vertex in a grid of width and height $n(G_2) - 1 + bl(2)$ with $2n(G_2) - 1 + 2bl(2)$ bends.

Now merge G_2 into G_1 . This adds at most one unit of height and width, and one bend (since we might have to incorporate the changes for merging a bridge shown in Figure 4.12). The resulting width and height is at most $1 + n(G_1) + bl(1) + n(G_2) - 1 + bl(2) = n + bl$. The number of bends is at most $1 + 2n(G_1) + 2 + bl(1) + 2n(G_2) - 1 + bl(2) = 2n + 2 + bl$.

If a vertex of degree less than 4 is on the outer-face, then G_1 can be embedded in a smaller grid with fewer bends. The calculations are similar. \square

Remember that we found already an estimation on the number of blocks in a graph without bridges (Lemma 3.1.7). We will now generalize this to graphs with bridges.

Lemma 4.3.6 *Every 4-graph has at most $n + 1$ blocks that are not bridges.*

Proof: In Lemma 3.1.7 we computed the formula

$$bl \leq \#\{\text{cutvertices}\} + 1 \leq \#\{\text{vertices of degree 4}\} + 1 \leq n + 1 \quad (4.1)$$

for the number of blocks bl of a graph without bridges. Assume G has a bridge, and removing it splits G into G_1 and G_2 , where $n(G_1) + n(G_2) = n$. We can choose the bridge in such a way that G_1 has no bridge. By induction G_2 has at most $n(G_2) + 1$ blocks that are not bridges. G_1 has a vertex of degree ≤ 3 (the endpoint of the bridge), and by Equation 4.1 at most $n(G_1)$ blocks. So the number of blocks that are not bridges is at most $n(G_1) + n(G_2) + 1 = n + 1$. \square

Figure 4.13: It is not true that a 4-graph has at most $n + 1$ blocks. The shown graph has $n = 9$ vertices and $bl = 15$ blocks. However, it has only 7 blocks that are not bridges.

Lemma 4.3.7 *Every multi-4-graph G has at most $n - 1$ blocks.*

Proof: Let bl be the number of blocks. We are done if $bl = 1$, since every multigraph has at least 2 vertices. So assume $bl > 1$. If G has no bridges, then consider the blocktree \mathcal{B} of G . Let B be a leaf in the blocktree. Then B has only one cutvertex, but since we have no loops, it has at least two vertices. So G contains a vertex that is not a cutvertex. Since $bl > 1$, \mathcal{B} has at least two leaves, and we have at least two vertices in G that are not a cutvertex. By Equation 4.1 this implies $bl - 1 \leq n - 2$.

If G has a bridge, and removing it leaves the two graphs G_1 and G_2 , then by induction on the number of bridges G_i has at most $n(G_i) - 1$ blocks ($i = 1, 2$). The removed bridge is one more block, so together we have at most $1 + n(G_1) - 1 + n(G_2) - 1 = n(G) - 1$ blocks. \square

Applying these estimations on Lemma 4.3.5 we get the following theorem.

Theorem 4.9 *Let G be a plane 4-graph that is not biconnected. Then it can be embedded in a $(2n + 1) \times (2n + 1)$ -grid with $4n + 4$ bends. If G is a multi-graph, it can be embedded in a $(2n - 1) \times (2n - 1)$ -grid with $4n$ bends.*

Remark: *While Lemma 4.3.7 gives an estimation on the number of all blocks, we only needed an estimation on the number of blocks that are not bridges. Hence, for a multi-graph the drawing has a better size if there are many bridges.*

Simple graphs

Theorem 4.9 is optimal for 4-graphs and nearly optimal for multi-4-graphs. For simple graphs a sharper bound on bl is possible. But in fact, we save even more, since we apply the improvement step for leaves of the blocktree. We deal with this in this subsection. The algorithm itself undergoes only very few changes, but the analysis is lengthy. The idea is that every small block (i.e. with few vertices) contributes less to the sum of the correction terms. We get a bound of $\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_w(B) \leq \frac{n}{5}$, and similarly for the height and the number of bends.

Assume for now that G contains no bridge, and that we have a parent-vertex defined for every block. Since we have no bridge, every block has at least 3 vertices.

First we proof that every leaf of the blocktree does not need correction terms. Since we have no bridge, a block B is a leaf in the blocktree if and only if $cr(B) = 0$.

Lemma 4.3.8 *Assume B is a simple block that is not a bridge. If the parent-vertex is defined and $cr(B) = 0$, then all correction terms are non-positive.*

Proof: Since $cr(B) = 0$, any plane drawing is a proper drawing. Since B is simple, we apply the improvement step. The parent-vertex is chosen as the last vertex and has degree ≤ 3 . With that, we get an $(n - 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid and $2n - 1$ bends by the special case of Theorem 4.8. \square

Now we specify the notion of a small block.

Definition 10 *Assume B is a block that is not a bridge, and where $v = \text{parent}(B)$ is defined. Call B a small block, if $3 \leq n(B) \leq 4$ and $\deg(v) \leq 3$; or if $n(B) = 5$ and $\deg(v) = 2$.*

There are two reasons, why small blocks need smaller corrections terms: they cannot have as many edges (which reduces the width and the number of bends), and it is always possible to save some height as well. We show this in the following series of lemmas.

Lemma 4.3.9 *Let B be a small block. Then $m \leq 2n - 2$, and equality holds only if every vertex $\neq \text{parent}(B)$ has degree ≥ 3 .*

Proof: For $n = 3$ we have at most $3 = 2n - 3$ edges by simplicity. For $n = 4$ we have at most $6 = 2n - 2$ edges, and equality holds if we have the K_4 and all vertices have degree 3. So assume $n = 5$, which implies $\deg(\text{parent}(B)) = 2$.

The maximum degree is 4, and there can be at most two vertices which have degree 4, since every such vertex must be adjacent to $v = \text{parent}(B)$. In fact, these can only be the two neighbors x_1, x_2 of v , the two other vertices must have degree ≤ 3 . So $2m = \sum_{w \in V} \deg(w) \leq \deg(v) + \deg(x_1) + \deg(x_2) + 2 \cdot 3 \leq 2 + 4 + 4 + 6 = 16 = 4n - 4$. We have $m = 2n - 2$ only if equality holds everywhere, in particular $\deg(x_i) = 4$ ($i = 1, 2$) and $\deg(y) = 3$ for all $y \neq v, x_1, x_2$. \square

This is already enough to show how the correction terms reduce for small blocks without critical cutvertices.

Lemma 4.3.10 *Let B be a small block and $\text{cr}(B) = 0$. Then B has a proper drawing of size $(n - 2) \times (n - 1)$ with $2n - 3$ bends with $v = \text{parent}(B)$ as final vertex.*

Proof: Since $\text{cr}(B) = 0$, any plane drawing is a proper drawing. The last vertex for BICONN-PLANE had degree less than 4. We applied the improvement for simple planar graphs, and distinguish by the degree of the vertex v^* involved in the improvement.

If $\text{deg}(v^*) = 3$, the obtained sizes are an $(m - n) \times (n - 1)$ -grid and $2m - 2n + 1$ bends by Lemma 4.2.8. We are done since $m \leq 2n - 2$.

If $\text{deg}(v^*) = 2$, then we must have $m \leq 2n - 3$, by Lemma 4.3.9 and since $v^* \neq v$. We get an $(m - n + 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid and $2m - 2n + 2$ bends by Lemma 4.2.8, which gives the result. \square

For blocks with critical cutvertices, we first deal with drawings of B where all critical cutvertices are drawn straight. Then we study how converting this drawing into a proper drawing affects the needed grid-size and number of bends.

Lemma 4.3.11 *Let B be a small block. Then B can be drawn in an $(m - n + 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid with $2m - 2n + 3$ bends, so that $v = \text{parent}(B)$ is drawn as final vertex. All vertices of degree 2 that are not v are drawn straight, using the connections top and bottom.*

Proof: We draw B with BICONN-PLANE with v as last vertex. Since $\text{deg}(v) \leq 3$, this gives the desired properties, except for one unit in height. We distinguish two cases:

- There is a vertex $s \neq v$ with $\text{deg}(s) \leq 3$ on the outer-face:

Then we chose s as first vertex for BICONN-PLANE. We have an $(m - n + 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid and $2m - 2n + 2$ bends. If s was a critical cutvertex and $\text{deg}(s) = 2$, we drew it in one row with v_2 , which adds one more bend, but neither width nor height.

- All vertices $\neq v$ on the outer-face have degree 4:

By simplicity the vertices of degree 4 must be connected to four different vertices, in particular $n \geq 5$. So $n = 5$, and $\text{deg}(v) = 2$, by definition of a small block.

All vertices of degree 4 must be connected to all other vertices, in particular to v . Since $\text{deg}(v) = 2$, we can have at most two vertices x_1, x_2 of degree 4, so the outer-face has at most degree 3. It has at least degree 3 by simplicity. The other two vertices are not on the outer-face and connected to both x_1 and x_2 . There are at most two graphs that fulfill this, they are shown in Figure 4.14 and called G_{exc}^1 and G_{exc}^2 . Both can be embedded with the desired properties. \square

Figure 4.14: The only two graphs, G_{exc}^1 and G_{exc}^2 , for the second case, and a suitable drawing.

Lemma 4.3.12 *Let B be a small block and $\text{cr}(B) = 1$. Then B has a proper drawing of size $(n - 1) \times (n - 1)$ with $2n - 2$ bends with $v = \text{parent}(B)$ as final vertex.*

Proof: The critical cutvertex is a vertex $\neq v$ of degree 2, so $m \leq 2n - 3$ by Lemma 4.3.9. Embed B as in Lemma 4.3.11 in an $(m - n + 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid with $2m - 2n + 3$ bends such that the critical cutvertex is drawn straight. Converting this drawing into a proper drawing happens at an increase of one unit in width and one bend. We are done with $m \leq 2n - 3$. \square

Lemma 4.3.13 *Let B be a small block and $\text{cr}(B) \geq 2$. Then B has a proper drawing of size $n \times (n - 1)$ with $2n + 1 - \text{cr}(B)$ bends with $v = \text{parent}(B)$ as final vertex.*

Proof: Embed B as in Lemma 4.3.11 in an $(m - n + 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid with $2m - 2n + 3$ bends. Convert the straight drawings of the $cr = \text{cr}(B)$ critical cutvertices into right angles, at an increase of cr units in width and cr bends. After this the width is $cr + m - n + 1$ and there are at most $cr + 2m - 2n + 3$ bends.

We have $m \leq 2n - cr - 1$ by the corollary of Lemma 2.3.4, so the width is at most n and there are at most $m + 2 \leq 2n + 1 - cr$ bends. \square

By classifying the blocks, we can combine these lemmas into one corollary.

Definition 11 *The blocks are distinguished by their number of critical cutvertices: we call B to be of type 0 if $\text{cr}(B) = 0$, to be of type 1 if $\text{cr}(B) = 1$, and to be of type 2 otherwise.*

Corollary 4.2 *For a small block B we have the following correction terms:*

- *B of type 0: $\Phi_w(B) = -1$, $\Phi_h(B) = 0$, $\Phi_b(B) = -2$.*
- *B of type 1: $\Phi_w(B) = 0$, $\Phi_h(B) = 0$, $\Phi_b(B) = -1$.*
- *B of type 2: $\Phi_w(B) = 1$, $\Phi_h(B) = 0$, $\Phi_b(B) = 2$.*

With this corollary and the following definitions, we can get estimations on the sums of the correction terms.

Definition 12 *Define the following sets and cardinalities:*

- \mathcal{T} = the set of all blocks where $\text{parent}(B)$ is defined,
- $\mathcal{T}_{small} = \{\text{small blocks}\} = \{B \in \mathcal{T} : n(B) \leq 4\} \cup \{B \in \mathcal{T} : n(B) = 5, \deg(\text{parent}(B)) = 2\}$,
- $\mathcal{T}_{large} = \mathcal{T} - \mathcal{T}_{small}$,
- \mathcal{T}_i = the set of blocks in \mathcal{T} of type i ,
- $t_i = |\mathcal{T}_{small} \cap \mathcal{T}_i|$,
- $T_i = |\mathcal{T}_{large} \cap \mathcal{T}_i|$.

Lemma 4.3.14 *Let G be a graph without bridges with a vertex v with $\deg(v) \leq 3$ on the outerface. Then*

- $\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_w(B) \leq T_1 + T_2 - t_0 + t_2$,
- $\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_h(B) \leq T_1 + T_2$,
- $\sum_{B \in G} \Phi_b(B) \leq 2T_1 + 2T_2 - 2t_0 - t_1 + 2t_2$.

Proof: Since $\deg(v) \leq 3$, every block has a parent-vertex, and the sum over all blocks in G is the same as the sum over all blocks in \mathcal{T} . Every block B in \mathcal{T}_1 or \mathcal{T}_2 has $\Phi_w(B) \leq 1$, $\Phi_h(B) \leq 1$ and $\Phi_b(B) \leq 2$ by Lemma 4.3.2. Every block in \mathcal{T}_0 has $\Phi_w(B) \leq 0$, $\Phi_h(B) \leq 0$ and $\Phi_b(B) \leq 0$ by Lemma 4.3.8. By definition of T_i and t_i , the estimations follow from Corollary 4.2. \square

We need two things: we want to somehow remove the ‘ $+t_2$ ’ term from these equations, and we need an estimation for $T_0 + T_1 + T_2$.

Lemma 4.3.15 *We have $t_2 + T_2 \leq t_0 + T_0 - 1$.*

Proof: If cv is the number of cutvertices, then we have

$$m(\mathcal{B}) = n(B) - 1 = cv + |\mathcal{T}| - 1 = cv + (t_0 + T_0) + (t_1 + T_1) + (t_2 + T_2) - 1. \quad (4.2)$$

Every cutvertex has degree 2 in \mathcal{B} . Assume a block B is not the root of \mathcal{B} . If B is of type 0, it has $\deg_{\mathcal{B}}(B) = 1$, if it is of type 1, then $\deg_{\mathcal{B}}(B) = 2$, and if it is of type 2, then $\deg_{\mathcal{B}}(B) \geq 3$. If B is the root, then its degree is one less than these bounds. Altogether, we have

$$2m(\mathcal{B}) = \sum_{v \text{ cutvertex}} \deg(v) + \sum_{B \in \mathcal{T}} \deg(B) \geq 2cv + (t_0 + T_0) + 2(t_1 + T_1) + 3(t_2 + T_2) - 1, \quad (4.3)$$

where the last ‘ -1 ’ comes from the root. Subtracting Equation 4.2 twice from Equation 4.3, we arrive at the result. \square

Lemma 4.3.16 *We have $T_0 + T_1 + T_2 \leq \frac{n}{5}$ in a graph without bridges.*

Proof: We show that we can assign five vertices to each block B in \mathcal{T}_{large} in such a way that no vertex is assigned to two blocks. Namely, if $n(B) \geq 6$ we assign to B the five vertices of B that are not $parent(B)$. If $n(B) = 5$, then $\deg(parent(B)) = 3$ by the definition of \mathcal{T}_{large} , and we assign all vertices of B to B .

Assume we counted a vertex v twice, for the blocks B_1 and B_2 in \mathcal{T}_{large} . Since blocks intersect only in cutvertices, and each cutvertex is parent-vertex for one of the blocks in a graph without bridges, we may assume $v = parent(B_2)$.

If $n(B_2) \geq 6$, then v was not counted for B_2 . So $n(B_2) = 5$ and by $B_2 \in \mathcal{T}_{large}$ we have $\deg_{B_2}(v) = 3$. But then B_1 must be a bridge – a contradiction. \square

Now we can combine all this into one lemma for a graph without bridges where every block has a parent-vertex.

Lemma 4.3.17 *Assume G has no bridge and a vertex v of $\deg(v) \leq 3$ is on the outer-face. Then G has a drawing in an $(\frac{6}{5}n - 2) \times (\frac{6}{5}n - 1)$ -grid with $\frac{12}{5}n - 3$ bends such that v is drawn as final vertex.*

Proof: Since we have no bridges, the width is

$$n - 1 + \sum_{B \in G} \Phi_w(B) \leq n - 1 + T_1 + T_2 - t_0 + t_2 \leq n - 1 + T_0 + T_1 - 1 \leq \frac{6}{5}n - 2$$

by the general analysis of Lemma 2.3.3 and by Lemma 4.3.15 and 4.3.16. The height is

$$n - 1 + \sum_{B \in G} \Phi_h(B) \leq n - 1 + T_1 + T_2 \leq n - 1 + T_0 + T_1 + T_2 \leq \frac{6}{5}n - 1$$

by Lemma 4.3.16. Finally, the number of bends is

$$2n - 1 + \sum_{B \in G} \Phi_b(B) \leq 2n - 1 + 2T_1 + 2T_2 - 2t_0 - t_1 + 2t_2 \leq 2n - 1 + 2T_0 + 2T_1 - 2 \leq \frac{12}{5}n - 3.$$

\square

Remark: *Even though we seem to have given away a lot by crude estimations, these bounds are almost sharp, compare with the class CS_i that will be defined on Page 70.*

Next we remove the requirement that a vertex of smaller degree is on the outer-face.

Lemma 4.3.18 *Let G be a simple plane 4-graph without bridges that is not biconnected. Then G can be embedded in a grid of width $\frac{6}{5}n$, height $\frac{6}{5}n + 1$, and with $\frac{12}{5}n + 1$ bends.*

Proof: Let B_0 be the outer-most block. We know $n(B_0) \geq 3$ by simplicity. Assume B_0 had cr critical cutvertices. Since we have no bridges, and since G is not biconnected, we must have $cr > 0$. We know that the outer-most block B_0 has a proper drawing in a grid of width and height $n(B_0) + 1$ with $2n(B_0) - cr + 4$ bends (Lemma 4.3.4). We split off some graphs in Step (2) of CONN, call those graphs $G_{j_1}, \dots, G_{j_{cr}}$. We showed before that $\sum_{l=1}^{cr} n(G_{j_l}) = n(G) + cr - n(B_0)$ (Equation 2.2).

The parent-vertex of G_{j_l} is on the outer-face of the induced embedding, so by Lemma 4.3.17 we can embed G_{j_l} in a grid of width $\frac{6}{5}n(G_{j_l}) - 2$, height $\frac{6}{5}n(G_{j_l}) - 1$, and with $\frac{12}{5}n(G_{j_l}) - 3$ bends. So altogether we get a width of

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{l=1}^{cr} \left(\frac{6}{5}n(G_{j_l}) - 2 \right) + n(B_0) + 1 = \frac{6}{5} \left(\sum_{l=1}^{cr} n(G_{j_l}) \right) - 2cr + n(B_0) + 1 \\ & = \frac{6}{5}(n + cr - n(B_0)) - 2cr + n(B_0) + 1 \leq \frac{6}{5}n - \frac{4}{5}cr - \frac{1}{5}n(B_0) + 1 \leq \frac{6}{5}n, \end{aligned}$$

since $n(B_0) \geq 3$ and $cr \geq 1$. The height is

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{l=1}^{cr} \left(\frac{6}{5}n(G_{j_l}) - 1 \right) + n(B_0) + 1 = \frac{6}{5} \left(\sum_{l=1}^{cr} n(G_{j_l}) \right) - cr + n(B_0) + 1 \\ & = \frac{6}{5}(n + cr - n(B_0)) - cr + n(B_0) + 1 \leq \frac{6}{5}n + \frac{1}{5}cr - \frac{1}{5}n(B_0) + 1 \leq \frac{6}{5}n + 1, \end{aligned}$$

since $cr \leq n(B_0)$. The number of bends is

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{l=1}^{cr} \left(\frac{12}{5}n(G_{j_l}) - 3 \right) + 2n(B_0) - cr + 4 = \frac{12}{5} \left(\sum_{l=1}^{cr} n(G_{j_l}) \right) - 3cr + 2n(B_0) - cr + 4 \\ & = \frac{12}{5}(n + cr - n(B_0)) - 4cr + 2n(B_0) + 4 \leq \frac{12}{5}n - \frac{8}{5}cr - \frac{2}{5}n(B_0) + 4 \leq \frac{12}{5}n + 2, \end{aligned}$$

since $n(B_0) \geq 3$ and $cr \geq 1$. □

Finally, we take care of bridges.

Theorem 4.10 *Let G be a simple plane 4-graph that is not biconnected. Then it can be embedded in a grid of width $\frac{6}{5}n$, height $\frac{6}{5}n + 1$, and with $\frac{12}{5}n + 2$ bends. If a vertex of degree ≤ 3 is on the outer-face, G can be embedded in a grid of width and height $\frac{6}{5}n - 1$ with $\frac{12}{5}n - 1$ bends.*

Proof: We show the claim by induction on the number of bridges br . The case $br = 0$ is done by Lemma 4.3.18 respectively by Lemma 4.3.17 (the statement here is actually weaker than the one proved there).

Assume G contains a bridge (v_1, v_2) , and we split G into G_1 and G_2 . Since G_1 contains less bridges than G , it can be embedded in a grid of width $\frac{6}{5}n(G_1)$, height $\frac{6}{5}n(G_1) + 1$, and with $\frac{12}{5}n(G_1) + 2$ bends. G_2 has a vertex of degree ≤ 3 on the outer-face, so it can be embedded in a grid of width and height $\frac{6}{5}n(G_2) - 1$ with $\frac{12}{5}n(G_2) - 1$ bends.

Merging G_2 into G_1 adds at most one unit of height and width each, and at most one bend. That gives a drawing of G of width $\frac{6}{5}(n(G_1) + n(G_2))$, height $\frac{6}{5}(n(G_1) + n(G_2)) + 1$, and with $\frac{12}{5}(n(G_1) + n(G_2)) + 2$ bends, which proves the first claim since $n(G_1) + n(G_2) = n$.

If a vertex of degree less than 4 is on the outer-face, then G_1 can be embedded in a smaller grid with fewer bends. The calculations are similar. □

4.3.3 Triconnected graphs

In this section we deal with drawing triconnected graphs. The algorithm presented is independent of the schemes BICONN and CONN. Remember that a graph is called triconnected if it is simple, and if after removing two arbitrary vertices the remaining graph is connected.

For non-planar graphs, no algorithm seems to be known that takes advantage if the graph is triconnected. For plane graphs (and hence also for planar graphs) there exists such an algorithm, given by Kant [Ka]. We describe his algorithm here. Kant showed a bound of an $n \times n$ -grid and $\frac{3}{2}n + 2$ bends. We show that the algorithm with only a few changes produces at most $\frac{4}{3}n + 4$ bends. This is used to show that it also gives a smaller grid-size than the one shown by Kant.

Kant uses another ordering of the vertices, called canonical ordering. For an ordering of the vertices let $G(i)$ to be the graph induced by $\{v_1, \dots, v_i\}$.

Definition 13 [Ka] *Let G be a plane graph. An ordering $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ is called a canonical ordering if the following holds:*

- (v_1, v_2) is an edge and belongs to the outer-face.
- v_n belongs to the outer-face and has at least two neighbors.
- For every $3 \leq j \leq n - 1$, v_j is in the outer-face of $G(j - 1)$, and one of the following holds:
 - Either “ v_j is a new vertex”, i.e. v_j has at least two neighbors in $G(j - 1)$ and at least one neighbor in $G - G(j)$. $G(j)$ is biconnected.
 - Or “ v_j is part of a new chain”, i.e. there exists i, k , $i \leq j \leq k$, such that for all $i < l < k$ v_l is adjacent to v_{l-1} and v_{l+1} , has no other neighbor in $G(k)$, and at least one neighbor in $G - G(k)$. Furthermore, v_i and v_k have each exactly one neighbor in $G(i - 1)$ and at least one neighbor in $G - G(k)$. $G(k)$ is biconnected.

Figure 4.15: The two different possibilities for v_j .

Kant also showed the existence of such an ordering for triconnected planar graphs.

Lemma 4.3.19 [Ka] *Let G be a triconnected planar graph. Then for every combinatorial embedding and outer-face of G there exists a canonical ordering. It can be found in $\mathcal{O}(m)$ time.*

Assume a canonical ordering is given. For a vertex v we defined the *incoming edges* to be the edges to neighbors with a smaller number, and, for a vertex that is part of a chain, also the incident edges of the chain. The other incident edges are called *outgoing*. We denote their number by $\text{indeg}(v)$ respectively $\text{outdeg}(v)$. Every vertex v_j , $3 \leq j \leq n - 1$ has $\text{outdeg}(v_j) \leq 2$, since we have a 4-graph, and since by definition $\text{indeg}(v_j) \geq 2$.

Assume a vertex v has $\text{indeg}(v) \geq 2$. The combinatorial embedding of the planar graph defines an ordering of the incoming edges, and we can distinguish the *right* and *left incoming edge*. If $\text{indeg}(v) \geq 3$ we also have one or two *middle incoming edges*. Similarly, for a vertex with $\text{outdeg}(v) = 2$, we can define the *left* and *right outgoing edge*.

For a new vertex v_j in the canonical ordering, the *leftvertex* and *rightvertex* are the endpoints of the left and right incoming edge. For a new chain v_i, \dots, v_k , assume that after adding it the outer-face contains v_i, \dots, v_k in clockwise order. Then the *leftvertex* is the endpoint of the left incoming edge of v_i , and the *rightvertex* is the endpoint of the right incoming edge of v_k .

Figure 4.16: Notations for incoming and outgoing edges.

Definition 14 We mark some vertices as left or right. Assume $\text{outdeg}(v_i) = 2$ for some $i \geq 3$ (this implies $\text{deg}(v_i) = 4$). Consider the outgoing edges at v_i , and whether they are right, middle, or left incoming to the other endpoint.

- If the right outgoing edge is a middle incoming edge, we mark v_i as left.
- If the left outgoing edge is a middle incoming edge, we mark v_i as right.
- If both outgoing edges are right incoming edges, we mark v_i as left.
- If both outgoing edges are left incoming edges, we mark v_i as right.
- Otherwise, we leave v_i unmarked.

We have to make sure that the first two of the above cases are not contradictory:

Lemma 4.3.20 Assume we have a vertex v_i with $\text{outdeg}(v_i) = 2$, $i \geq 3$, and its two outgoing edges are to the vertices v_j, v_k , $i < j < k$. Then the edge (v_i, v_j) is not middle incoming.

Proof: Assume the edge (v_i, v_j) was middle incoming. Then $\text{indeg}(v_j) \geq 3$, so v_j was a new vertex in the canonical ordering. The leftvertex c_1 of v_j is to the left of v_i on the outer-face of $G(j-1)$, and the rightvertex c_2 of v_j is to the right of v_i on the outer-face of $G(j-1)$.

By biconnectivity of $G(j-1)$ there exists a path from c_1 to c_2 that topdoes not use v_i . After adding v_j , this path together with the edges (c_1, v_j) and (c_2, v_j) encloses v_i , so v_i disappears from the outer-face. But this contradicts planarity: v_k is in the outer-face of $G(k-1)$, and also in the outer-face of $G(j)$, and connecting v_i with v_k gives a crossing. \square

Figure 4.17: The edge to the successor with the smaller number cannot be middle incoming, otherwise planarity is violated.

Now we describe the algorithm. For a vertex v we denote the four incident connections by $u(v)$, $d(v)$, $l(v)$, and $r(v)$. The embedding of a vertex happens only in terms of these connections, i.e. we do not specify the precise grid-coordinates. After the drawing is finished, it is fairly easy to calculate the final coordinates in linear time, using an additional graph structure (see in [Ka]).

The first two vertices are embedded together, using for the edge between them the connection *down* for both. The edge outgoing from the left vertex to the left is bent upward, and so is the edge outgoing from the right vertex to the right. After possible renaming, we may assume that v_1 is the left of those two vertices.

For every following vertex the embedding depends on whether it is part of a chain or not, on its degree, and whether and how it is marked. We demonstrate algorithm TRICONN-PLANE in pictures in Figure 4.18 to 4.21, and give an algorithmic description in Figure 4.22. Remember that every vertex must have either degree 3 or 4, since the graph was triconnected.

Figure 4.18: Drawing the first two and the last vertex.

Figure 4.19: Various ways of adding a chain. l and r stands for *left* and *right*.

Figure 4.20: Various ways of adding a vertex of indegree 2.

Figure 4.21: Various ways of adding a vertex of indegree 3.

Sometimes, we added an extra bend at an edge that uses the left or the right connection at the endpoint with the smaller number. The reason is that for easier estimations we want to count this bend to the first endpoint, and not the second, of those edges.

Definition 15 An edge $e = (v_i, v_j)$, $i < j$ is said to look upward, if v_i is embedded, but v_j is not; and if either e uses $u(v_i)$, or it got an extra bend when embedding v_i .

Algorithm TRICONN-PLANE:

Compute a canonical ordering.

Embed the first two vertices:

Embed v_1 and v_2 via $d(v_1)$ and $d(v_2)$, assume v_1 is left.

if $\text{deg}(v_1) = 4$, bend the left outgoing edge at v_1 upward.

if $\text{deg}(v_2) = 4$, bend the right outgoing edge at v_2 upward.

Go through the steps of the canonical ordering:

if we add next a chain w_1, \dots, w_p , $p > 1$:

Let the leftvertex be w_0 and the rightvertex be w_{p+1} .

if $r(w_0)$ is free, connect w_0 to w_1 via $r(w_0)$, **else** via $u(w_0)$.

for $1 \leq l \leq p$

if w_l is marked *left*, connect w_l to w_{l-1} via $d(w_l)$, **else** via $l(w_l)$.

if $\text{deg}(w_l) = 3$, connect w_l to w_{l+1} via $r(w_l)$,

else if $d(w_l)$ is free, connect w_l to w_{l+1} via $d(w_l)$, **else** via $r(w_l)$.

if $l(w_{p+1})$ is free, connect w_{p+1} to w_p via $l(w_{p+1})$, **else** via $u(w_{p+1})$.

if we used $u(w_0)$ for edge (w_0, w_1) and w_1 is marked *right*:

Change the drawing and connect w_1 via $d(w_1)$ and $r(w_1)$.

Bend the left outgoing edge of w_1 upward.

if we used $u(w_{p+1})$ for edge (w_p, w_{p+1}) and w_p is marked *left*:

Change the drawing and connect w_p via $l(w_p)$ and $d(w_p)$.

Bend the right outgoing edge of w_1 upward.

if we add next a vertex v with $\text{indeg}(v) = 2$:

Let the leftvertex be c_i and the rightvertex be c_j .

if $r(c_i)$ is free, connect c_i to v via $r(c_i)$, **else** via $u(c_i)$.

if $l(c_j)$ is free, connect c_j to v via $l(c_j)$, **else** via $u(c_j)$.

if we use $u(c_i)$ and $u(c_j)$,

if v is marked *right*, connect v via $l(v)$ and $d(v)$, **else** via $d(v)$ and $r(v)$.

if we use $u(c_i)$ and $l(c_j)$,

connect v to its neighbors via $d(v)$ and $r(v)$.

if v is marked *left*, bend the edge outgoing from v to the left upward.

if we use $r(c_i)$ and $u(c_j)$,

connect v to its neighbors via $l(v)$ and $d(v)$.

if v is marked *right*, bend the edge outgoing from v to the right upward.

if we use $r(c_i)$ and $l(c_j)$,

if $\text{deg}(v) = 3$, connect it via $l(v)$ and $r(v)$,

else if v is marked *right* connect v via $l(v)$ and $d(v)$, **else** via $d(v)$ and $r(v)$.

if we add next a vertex v with $\text{indeg}(v) \geq 3$:

Let the leftvertex be c_i and the rightvertex be c_j :

if $r(c_i)$ is free, connect c_i to v via $r(c_i)$, **else** via $u(c_i)$.

if $l(c_j)$ is free, connect c_j to v via $l(c_j)$, **else** via $u(c_j)$.

if $\text{indeg}(v) = 3$, connect v to its incoming edges via $l(v)$, $d(v)$ and $r(v)$.

if $\text{indeg}(v) = 4$, connect v to c_i via $l(v)$, to c_j via $u(v)$,

and to the others via $d(v)$ and $r(v)$.

Figure 4.22: The algorithm for plane triconnected graphs by Kant [Ka].

We prove various invariants of this algorithm.

Invariant 2 *Directly from the construction one checks the following:*

1. *If v_i is marked left, then its right outgoing edge looks upward.*
2. *If v_i is marked right, then its left outgoing edge looks upward.*
3. *For incoming edges of $v_i \neq v_n$ we never use $u(v_i)$.*

With the following statement, we prove that we did treat all possible cases of used connections at the leftvertex. A similar statement holds for the rightvertex.

Invariant 3 *Assume we have vertex v with leftvertex c_i . Then the edge (c_i, v) either looks upward, or it leaves c_i at $r(c_i)$.*

Proof: Consider the time when we are about to embed v , and assume that $r(c_i)$ is used, and the edge (c_i, v) does not look upward. This already excludes $c_i = v_1$, since here one of the two cases always happens.

The edge (c_i, v) was assigned to the left connection at c_i . So the connection at $u(c_i)$ was used already, say by some edge (c_i, w) . This edge cannot be middle incoming of w , by Lemma 4.3.20. Similar one shows that it cannot be right incoming. So it was left incoming to w .

The edge from c_i to v was also left incoming, and c_i was marked *right*. But for any vertex marked *right*, the left outgoing edge looks upward. \square

Invariant 4 *Assume $\text{indeg}(v_j) \geq 3$, and the edge (v_i, v_j) is a middle incoming edge of v_j . Then it looks upward at v_i .*

Proof: We are done if $\text{outdeg}(v_i) = 1$, since in this case the outgoing edge can always choose the top connection. So assume $\text{outdeg}(v_i) \geq 2$ and the edge is right outgoing at v_i (the other case is analog). If $i \geq 3$, then by definition of the marking v_i was marked *left*. We are done by Invariant 1.

If $i = 1$, two of the outgoing edges look upward anyway. We show that the edge to the right is not a middle incoming edge. Namely, by biconnectivity of the resulting graph, v_1 must be connected to v_3 or the chain containing v_3 . By planarity, this vertex or chain must use the right outgoing edge of v_1 . But by simplicity $\text{indeg}(v_3) = 2$, and the right outgoing edge of v_1 is indeed not middle incoming. $i = 2$ is analog. \square

In his paper Kant showed that this algorithm gives at most $\frac{3}{2}n + 2$ bends. But this is not tight: the algorithm always produces at most $\frac{4}{3}n + 4$ bends, as we show with the following analysis.

Definition 16 *After embedding the i th vertex, let $up(i)$ to be the number of unfinished edges which look upward, and let $b(i)$ to be the number of bends. Also, let $n_3(i)$ be the number of vertices of degree 3 among the first i vertices.*

Lemma 4.3.21 *For $1 < i < n$ we have $3b(i) + 2n_3(i) + up(i) \leq 4i + 8$.*

Proof: We proceed by induction on the steps of the canonical ordering. Consider the embedding of v_1 and v_2 . We have to show that the left hand side is at most 16, and distinguish by the number of vertices of degree 3 among those two.

- If $n_3(2) = 0$, i.e. if v_1 and v_2 have degree 4, we have four bends and four upward-drawn edges. Therefore $b(2) = 4$, $up(2) = 4$ and $3b(2) + 2n_3(2) + up(2) = 12 + 0 + 4 = 16$.
- If $n_3(2) = 1$, then $up(2) = 3$ and $b(2) = 3$, so $3b(2) + 2n_3(2) + up(2) = 9 + 2 + 3 = 14$.
- If $n_3(2) = 2$, then $up(2) = 2$ and $b(2) = 2$, so $3b(2) + 2n_3(2) + up(2) = 6 + 4 + 3 = 12$.

Now consider adding either a chain or a vertex. By Invariant 3 the connection to the left vertex c_i is done via $u(c_i)$ or $r(c_i)$, and analog that the connection to the right vertex c_j is done via $u(c_j)$ or $l(c_j)$. Depending on which directions are used at the left vertex and the right vertex, we can classify the cases into UU, RU, UL, and RL.

- We add a chain of p vertices:

For each vertex w in the chain, we add at most one bend in the column of w if $deg(w) = 4$, and no bend if $deg(w) = 3$. If we used $u(c_i)$, and w_1 was marked *right*, then we have one more bend at the left outgoing edge of w_1 , but in exchange no new bend in the column of w_1 . Similarly for w_p . So in all, $b(i+p) \leq b(i) + p + n_3(i) - n_3(i+p)$.

Every vertex in the chain produces one new upward-edge. w_1 and w_p each might produce two new upward-edges, but only if we used $u(c_i)$ respectively $u(c_j)$. In all, the number of upward edges increases by p . Since $n_3(i+p) \geq n_3(i)$, we have by induction

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3b(i+p) + 2n_3(i+p) + up(i+p) \\
& \leq 3(b(i) + p + n_3(i) - n_3(i+p)) + 2n_3(i+p) + (up(i) + p) \\
& \leq 3b(i) + 2n_3(i) + up(i) + 4p \leq 4i + 8 + 4p = 4(i+p) + 8.
\end{aligned}$$

- We add v with $indeg(v) = 2$:

We have to show that $3b(\cdot) + up(\cdot)$ increases by at most 4, and by at most 2 if $deg(v) = 3$. We explain this in detail for the first case, and sketch it briefly for the other cases.

- UU: We use two upward looking edges at the incoming edges, and have one new bend. We produce one new upward looking edge at v . So $up(i+1) = up(i) - 2 + 1$ and $b(i+1) = b(i) + 1$; and $3b(\cdot) + up(\cdot)$ increases by 2.
- RU or UL: If $deg(v) = 4$ we have $b(i+1) \leq b(i) + 1$ and $up(i+1) \leq up(i) + 1$, so $3b(\cdot) + up(\cdot)$ increases by at most 4. If $deg(v) = 3$, then $b(i+1) = b(i)$ and $up(i+1) = up(i)$, so $3b(\cdot) + up(\cdot)$ increases by 0.
- RL: If $deg(v) = 4$ we have $b(i+1) = b(i) + 1$ and $up(i+1) = up(i) + 1$, so $3b(\cdot) + up(\cdot)$ increases by 4. If $deg(v) = 3$, then $b(i+1) = b(i)$ and $up(i+1) = up(i)$, so $3b(\cdot) + up(\cdot)$ increases by 0.

- We add v with $indeg(v) = 3$ where $v \neq v_n$ (this in particular implies that $deg(v) = 4$):

The middle incoming edge of v leaves its other endpoint looking upward (Invariant 4), and never produces a bend. We have to show that the $3b(\cdot) + up(\cdot)$ increases by at most 4. We explain this in detail for the first case, and sketch it briefly for the other cases.

- UU: We have two new bends, and use one upward looking edge from each incoming edge. We produce one new upward looking edge at v . So $up(i+1) = up(i) - 3 + 1$ and $b(i+1) = b(i) + 2$, and $3b(\cdot) + up(\cdot)$ increases by $6 - 2 = 4$.
- RU or UL: We have $b(i+1) = b(i) + 1$ and $up(i+1) = up(i) - 2 + 1 = up(i) - 1$, so $3b(\cdot) + up(\cdot)$ increases by 2.
- RL: We have $b(i+1) = b(i)$ and $up(i+1) = up(i)$, so $3b(\cdot) + up(\cdot)$ increases by 0.

□

Lemma 4.3.22 *We have $3b(n) + 2n_3(n) + up(n) \leq 4n + 12$.*

Proof: We know that $3b(n-1) + 2n_3(n-1) + up(n-1) \leq 4(n-1) + 8 = 4n + 4$ by the above lemma. So we only need to show that with adding the last vertex, the left hand side (LHS) increases by at most 8.

If $deg(v_n) = 3$, then we add the same amount of bends and use the same amount of upward edges as for any other vertex of indegree 3. So $3b(\cdot) + up(\cdot)$ increases by at most 4, as shown in the previous lemma. In fact, this number increases by only 3, since we do not add an upward edge. But we added one vertex of degree 3, so the LHS increases by at most 5.

Now assume $indeg(v_n) = 4$. We distinguish subcases.

- UU: We have $b(n) = b(n-1) + 4$, but also $up(n) = up(n-1) - 4$. The LHS increases by 8.
- RU or UL: We have $b(n) = b(n-1) + 3$ and $up(n) = up(n-1) - 3$. The LHS increases by 6.
- RL: We have $b(n) = b(n-1) + 2$ and $up(n) = up(n-1) - 2$. The LHS increases by 4.

□

Lemma 4.3.23 *The number of bends in total is at most $\frac{4}{3}(m - n + 3)$.*

Proof: Denote by n_3 the number of vertices of degree 3 in G . After the algorithm is finished, there is no upward edge left. So $up(n) = 0$, and the number of bends is $b(n) = \frac{1}{3}(4n - 2n_3 + 12)$.

Every vertex in the graph has degree either 3 or 4. With the formula for degrees, we can compute $2m = \sum_{v \in V} deg(v) = 4(n - n_3) + 3n_3 = 4n - n_3$. Consequently, $2n_3 = 8n - 4m$, and the total number of bends is $b(n) = \frac{1}{3}(4m - 4n + 12)$. □

Remember the theorem that we showed in the section of general ideas?

Theorem 4.11 *(see Theorem 2.1) Assume we are given an orthogonal drawing Γ of a graph G that has b bends. Then the half-perimeter is at most $b + 2n - m - 2$, and the width and height each are at most $\frac{1}{2}b + 2n - m - 1$.*

Lemma 4.3.24 *In TRICONN-PLANE, the half-perimeter is at most $\frac{4}{3}n + 2$, and each individual side is at most $\frac{5}{6}n + 1$.*

Proof: We combine the above lemma and theorem. We have at most $\frac{1}{3}(4m - 4n + 12)$ bends, so the half-perimeter is at most

$$\frac{1}{3}(4m - 4n + 12) + 2n - m - 2 = \frac{1}{3}(4m - 4n + 12 + 6n - 3m - 6) = \frac{1}{3}(m + 2n + 6) \leq \frac{4}{3}n + 2.$$

Since $m \geq \frac{3}{2}n$ for a triconnected graph, each individual side is at most

$$\frac{1}{6}(4m - 4n + 12) + 2n - m - 1 = \frac{1}{6}(4m - 4n + 12n - 6m) + 1 = \frac{1}{6}(8n - 2m) + 1 \leq \frac{1}{6}(8n - 3n) + 1.$$

□

Theorem 4.12 *(the algorithm due to Kant [Ka]) Let G be a triconnected plane 4-graph. Then G can be embedded in an $(\frac{5}{6}n + 1) \times (\frac{5}{6}n + 1)$ -grid with at most $\frac{4}{3}n + 4$ bends. The half-perimeter is at most $\frac{4}{3}n + 2$.*

Remark: *This algorithm is optimal in the number of bends and in the half-perimeter. If G is 4-regular, then $m = 2n$, and each individual side is bounded by $\frac{2}{3}n + 1$, which is optimal. We strongly suspect that the individual sides can always be bounded by $\frac{2}{3}n + 1$.*

4.4 Lower bounds

In this section we give lower bounds for planar and plane drawing, i.e. we exhibit graph classes such that every graph needs at least a certain grid-size and a certain number of bends in any planar respectively plane orthogonal drawing.

4.4.1 Plane graphs

For lower bounds of plane drawings we use arguments such as “ H surrounds G , and needs two more units of width and height.” Similar arguments have for example been used by Storer [St]. We try now to make this more precise.

Definition 17 *Assume we have a plane graph H and after taking away all edges on the outer-face we get the graph G . Then we say that G is inside H , and H surrounds G .*

Lemma 4.4.1 *Let H and G be plane 4-graphs. Let G be inside H , and let the minimum degree of G be at least 2. If H has a plane drawing in a $w \times h$ -grid, then G has a plane drawing in an $(w - 2) \times (h - 2)$ -grid.*

Proof: Take a drawing Γ_H of H in a $w \times h$ -grid. Deleting the edges on the outer-face of H we get a drawing Γ_G of G . Consider the top-most used row of Γ_G . Since G has minimum degree 2, this row cannot be used by a vertex only, so it must be used by an edge. So it contains a horizontal line which belongs to some edge e on the outer-face of G . Now e is not on the outer-face of H since G is inside H . Since Γ_H reflects the combinatorial embedding of H , we must have a line drawn above e in Γ_H . Therefore Γ_H has at least one more unit in top-direction. The same holds for the other three directions. So Γ_H has at least two more units in width and height than Γ_G , and Γ_G is contained in a $(w - 2) \times (h - 2)$ -grid. \square

Triconnected graphs

Previously known results: *The best lower bound for triconnected graph was given by Kant [Ka]. He found a width and height of $\frac{2}{3}(n - 2) + 2$ and $\frac{4}{3}(n - 2) + 2$ bends.*

We improve Kant’s result slightly with the following graph class:

Definition 18 *Define the graph classes $\{T'_i\}$ and $\{T_i\}$ as follows:*

- T'_1 is a 3-cycle.
- T'_i ($i \geq 2$) is obtained by taking a copy of T'_{i-1} , and adding three vertices in the outer-face. Then we add a 6-cycle alternating between the three new vertices and the three vertices of degree 2 on the outer-face of T'_{i-1} , such that T'_i surrounds T'_{i-1} .
- T_i is obtained by taking a copy of T'_i and adding a 3-cycle between the three vertices of degree 2 on the outer-face of T'_i such that T_i surrounds T'_i .

Lemma 4.4.2 *T_i needs a width and height of $2i + 1$ in any plane drawing.*

Proof: We first show a lower bound for T'_i , namely, it needs a width and height of $2i - 1$. This is shown by induction on i . Since T'_1 is a triangle, it certainly needs a 1×1 -grid, so the claim is true for $i = 1$.

Figure 4.23: T_4 drawn in a 9×9 -grid with 20 bends.

Now consider T'_i , $i \geq 2$. By construction it surrounds T'_{i-1} , so if we could embed T'_i with width or height less than $2i + 1$, then by Lemma 4.4.1 we could embed T'_{i-1} in a grid of width or height less than $2i - 1 = 2(i - 1) + 1$, a contradiction.

Now finally consider T_i . By construction it surrounds T'_i , so it needs two more units in width and height than T'_i , which gives a lower bound of $2i + 1$ on the width and height. \square

Lemma 4.4.3 T_i needs $4i + 4$ bends in any plane drawing.

Proof: T_i is 4-regular, so $m(T_i) = 2n(T_i)$. Now if T_i could be embedded with $b < 4i + 4$ bends, then by Theorem 2.1 this drawing would have a width and height of at most $\frac{1}{2}b + 2n - m - 1 < (2i + 2) - 1 = 2i + 1$. This is a contradiction to the above lemma. \square

Theorem 4.13 *There exists a lower bound of an $(\frac{2}{3}n + 1) \times (\frac{2}{3}n + 1)$ -grid and $\frac{4}{3}n + 4$ bends for drawing triconnected plane graphs.*

Proof: T_i is triconnected for $i \geq 2$ and has $n = 3i$ vertices. We are done by Lemma 4.4.2 and Lemma 4.4.3. \square

Biconnected graphs

Previously known results: *The known lower bounds were an $(n - 2) \times (n - 2)$ -grid by Storer [St] and $2n + 4$ bends by Tamassia, Tollis and Vitter [TTV]. The graph of Tamassia, Tollis, and Vitter is a multi-graph, and making it simple reduces the lower bound to $2n - 2$ bends.*

We introduce the graph class used by Tamassia, Tollis, and Vitter, and show that it also gives a slightly better bound on the grid-size, namely an $(n + 1) \times (n + 1)$ -grid for multi-graphs and an $(n - 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid for simple graphs.

Definition 19 *Define the graph classes $\{B'_i\}$ and $\{B_i\}$ as follows:*

- B'_1 is a double edge.
- B'_i is obtained by taking a copy of B'_{i-1} , adding two vertices in the outer-face, and adding a 4-cycle alternating between the two new vertices and the two vertices on the outer-face of B'_{i-1} , such that B'_i surrounds B'_{i-1} .
- B_i is obtained by taking a copy of B'_i and adding a double edge between the two vertices on the outer-face of B'_i such that B_i surrounds B'_i .

Figure 4.24: B_4 drawn in a 9×9 -grid with 20 bends.

Lemma 4.4.4 B_i needs a width and height of $2i + 1$ in any plane drawing.

Proof: The proof is nearly the same as for the triconnected class T_i (Lemma 4.4.2). We show a lower bound for B'_i , namely, it needs a width and height of $2i - 1$. This is shown by induction on i . Since B'_1 is a double edge, it certainly needs a 1×1 -grid, so the claim is true for $i = 1$.

If we could draw B'_i with less than $2i - 1$ width or height, then by Lemma 4.4.1 we could draw B'_{i-1} with less than $2i - 1 - 2 = 2(i - 1) - 1$ width or height, a contradiction. If we could draw B_i with less than $2i + 1$ width or height, then we could draw B'_i with less than $2i - 1$ width or height, also a contradiction. \square

The following lemma has been shown by Tamassia, Tollis, and Vitter. However, it can also be shown with “our” methods, exactly as in Lemma 4.4.3.

Lemma 4.4.5 (Tamassia, Tollis, Vitter [TTV]) B_i needs $4i+4$ bends in any plane drawing.

Theorem 4.14 *There exist the following lower bounds for drawing plane biconnected graphs:*

- G simple: $(n - 1) \times (n - 1)$ -grid and $2n - 2$ bends.
- G a multi-graph: $(n + 1) \times (n + 1)$ -grid and $2n + 4$ bends.

Proof: For multi-graphs we are done by Lemma 4.4.4 and Lemma 4.4.5 and since B_i has $2i$ vertices. Let \bar{B}_i be the graph obtained from B_i by subdividing one edge in each of the double edges. \bar{B}_i is a simple biconnected plane graph, which needs the same grid-size as B_i . Also, it is B_i with two subdivided edges, so it needs $(4i + 4) - 2$ bends by Lemma 2.4.3. So we get a lower bound of an $(2i + 1) \times (2i + 1)$ -grid and $4i + 2$ bends for \bar{B}_i . We are done since \bar{B}_i has $2i + 2$ vertices. \square

Connected graphs

Previously known results: *To the author’s knowledge, no lower bounds have been proved for simple non-biconnected graphs. For non-biconnected multi-graphs, Tamassia, Tollis and Vitter [TTV] showed a lower bound of $8\frac{n-1}{3}$ bends, for graphs with loops they gave a bound of $2(n - 2)$ bends. No bounds were known on the grid-size.*

We develop new (and better) bounds for connected graphs, dealing first with graphs with loops, then with multi-graphs, and then define another graphs class to give lower bounds for simple connected graphs.

Definition 20 Define the graph classes $\{C'_i\}$ and $\{C_i\}$ as follows:

- C'_1 is a loop.
- C'_i is obtained by taking a copy of C'_{i-1} , adding one vertex in the outer-face, and adding a double edge between the new vertex and the vertex on the outer-face of C'_{i-1} , such that C'_i surrounds C'_{i-1} .
- C_i is obtained by taking a copy of C'_i and adding a loop at the vertex on the outer-face of C'_i such that C_i surrounds C'_i .

Figure 4.25: C_4 drawn in a 9×9 -grid with 20 bends.

Lemma 4.4.6 C_i needs a width and height of $2i + 1$ and $4i + 4$ bends in any plane drawing.

Proof: The proof is nearly the same as for the triconnected class T_i (Lemma 4.4.2). We show a lower bound for C'_i , namely, it needs a width and height of $2i - 1$. This is shown by induction on i . Since C'_1 is a loop, it certainly needs a 1×1 -grid, so the claim is true for $i = 1$.

If we could draw C'_i with less than $2i - 1$ width or height, then by Lemma 4.4.1 we could draw C'_{i-1} with less than $2i - 1 - 2 = 2(i - 1) - 1$ width or height, a contradiction. If we could draw C_i with less than $2i + 1$ width or height, then we could draw C'_i with less than $2i - 1$ width or height, also a contradiction. \square

Lemma 4.4.7 C_i needs $4i + 4$ bends in any plane drawing.

Proof: The proof is exactly as in Lemma 4.4.3, in combination with Lemma 4.4.6. \square

Definition 21 Define the graph classes $\{CM''_i\}$, $\{CM'_i\}$ and $\{CM_i\}$ as follows:

- CM''_1 is a quadruple edge, with one edge on the outer-face subdivided.
- CM''_i ($i \geq 2$) is obtained by taking a copy of CM''_{i-1} and adding one vertex in the outer-face. Then we add a double edge between the new vertex and the vertex of degree 2 on the outer-face of CM''_{i-1} , such that CM''_i surrounds CM''_{i-1} .
- CM'_i is obtained by taking a copy of CM''_i and adding two new vertices in the outer-face. Then we add a 3-cycle between the two new vertices and the vertex of degree 2 on the outer-face of CM''_i , such that CM'_i surrounds CM''_i .
- Finally, CM_i is obtained by taking a copy of CM'_i and adding a double edge between the vertices of degree 2 on the outer-face of CM'_i , such that CM_i surrounds CM'_i .

Figure 4.26: CM_4 drawn in a 13×13 -grid with 28 bends.

Lemma 4.4.8 CM_i needs a width and height of $2i + 5$ in any plane drawing.

Proof: Show first a lower bound of $2i + 1$ on the width and height of CM_i'' . This is clear for CM_1'' , since this graph equals B_1 with one edge subdivided. To get CM_i'' we need two more units in width and height than for CM_{i-1}'' , which gives the lower bound by induction. Finally, CM_i' surrounds CM_i'' , and CM_i surrounds CM_i' , so we need twice two more units in width and height. This gives the bound of $2i + 5$. \square

Lemma 4.4.9 CM_i needs $4i + 12$ bends in any plane drawing.

Proof: The proof is very similar to the one of Lemma 4.4.2. If n is the number of vertices and m the number of edges of CM_i , then $m = 2n$ since CM_i is 4-regular.

If we had a drawing of CM_i with $b < 4i + 12$ bends, then this drawing by Theorem 2.1 would have width and height at most $\frac{1}{2}b + 2n - m - 1 < (2i + 6) - 1 = 2i + 5$, a contradiction. \square

Definition 22 Define the graph classes $\{CS_i\}$, $\{CS_i'\}$ and $\{CS_i''\}$ as follows:

- CS_1'' is a 3-cycle.
- CS_i' ($i \geq 1$) is obtained by taking a copy of CS_i'' and adding two vertices in the outer-face. Then we add a 4-cycle alternating between the two new vertices and two vertices of degree 2 on the outer-face of CS_i'' , such that CS_i' surrounds CS_i'' .
- CS_i ($i \geq 1$) is obtained by taking a copy of CS_i' and adding one vertex in the outer-face. Then we add a 3-cycle between this new vertex and the two vertices of degree 2 on the outer-face of CS_i' , such that CS_i surrounds CS_i' .
- CS_{i+1}'' ($i \geq 1$) is obtained by taking a copy of CS_i and adding two vertices in the outer-face. Then we add a 3-cycle between the two new vertices and the vertex of degree 2 on the outer-face of CS_i , such that CS_{i+1}'' surrounds CS_i .

Figure 4.27: CS_2'' , CS_2' , and CS_2 ; and an optimal drawing.

Lemma 4.4.10 CS_i needs a width and height of $6i - 1$ in any plane drawing.

Proof: We show the lower bound by induction on i ; showing at the same time a lower bound for CS_i'' of $6i - 5$ and a lower bound for CS_i' of $6i - 3$. CS_1'' is a triangle that needs a width of $1 = 6 \cdot 1 - 5$. Assume the claim was shown for CS_i'' , i.e. CS_i'' needs a width and height of $6i - 5$.

CS_i' surrounds CS_i'' , so it needs two more units in width and height than CS_i'' , which gives a lower bound of $6i - 3$. CS_i surrounds CS_i' , so it needs two more units in width and height than CS_i' , which gives a lower bound of $6i - 1$. Finally, CS_{i+1}'' surrounds CS_i , so it needs two more units in width and height than CS_i , which gives a lower bound of $6i + 1 = 6(i + 1) - 5$. \square

Lemma 4.4.11 CS_i needs $12i - 2$ bends in any plane drawing.

Proof: If n is the number of vertices and m the number of edges of CS_i , then $m = 2n - 2$, since CS_i has two vertices of degree 2.

Now assume CS_i were drawn with $b < 12i - 2$ bends. Then the half-perimeter of this drawing by Theorem 2.1 is at most $b + 2n - m - 2 < 12i - 2$. This implies that at least one of width and height must be smaller than $6i - 1$, a contradiction to the above lemma. \square

Theorem 4.15 *There exists the following lower bounds for drawing plane graphs:*

- G with loops: $(2n + 1) \times (2n + 1)$ -grid and $4n + 4$ bends.
- G a multi-graph: $(2n - 3) \times (2n - 3)$ -grid and $4n - 4$ bends.
- G simple: $(\frac{6}{5}(n - 1) - 1) \times (\frac{6}{5}(n - 1) - 1)$ -grid and $\frac{12}{5}(n - 1) - 2$ bends.

Proof: For a graph with loops this follows with Lemma 4.4.6 and Lemma 4.4.7, since C_i has i vertices. For multi-graphs, observe that CM_i'' has $i + 2$ and CM_i has $i + 4$ vertices, the results follow from Lemma 4.4.8 and Lemma 4.4.9. Finally for the simple case, one shows easily by induction that CS_i has $5i + 1$ vertices and the results follows with Lemma 4.4.10 and Lemma 4.4.11. \square

Remark: *A very slight improvement for simple graphs is possible. Namely, with some extra effort it can be shown that G_{exc}^2 indeed needs either a width or a height of 4 (see the drawing in Figure 4.14 on Page 55). If we now let CS_1 be this graph, and build CS_i from CS_{i-1} as before, we can show that the larger of width and height must be $6i - 2$. On the other hand, this varied CS_i has only $5i$ vertices, which gives a lower bound of $\frac{6}{5}n - 2$ for the larger of width and height.*

4.4.2 Planar graphs

For planar graphs we can choose the combinatorial embedding, hence more orthogonal drawings are possible, and one expects the lower bounds to be smaller than for plane graphs.

To the author's knowledge no research has been done into lower bounds for planar drawings. We provide some results here which are close to optimality in the number of bends.

Triconnected graphs

It is known that for triconnected planar graphs there exists only one combinatorial embedding. If we consider all possible choices of the outer-face of T_i , then we get a lower bound for any planar drawing of T_i .

Lemma 4.4.12 T_i needs a width and height of i and $4i - 2$ bends in any planar drawing.

Proof: Assume that T'_1 had the vertices $\{v_1, v_2, v_3\}$ and that we obtained T'_i by adding the vertices $\{v_{3i-2}, v_{3i-1}, v_{3i}\}$.

Let Γ be the combinatorial embedding and the outer-face of T_i defined in Definition 18, and let Γ' be some other embedding of T_i . The outer-face of Γ' can have degree 3 or 4. If the degree is 3, then without loss of generality we may assume that the outer-face of Γ' is either the outer-face of Γ , or one of the three faces adjacent to it.

We are done if the two outer-faces are the same. In this case $\Gamma = \Gamma'$, and we have at least $4i + 4$ bends and a width of at least $2i + 1 > i$. If the outer-face of Γ' is adjacent to the outer-face of Γ , then we delete the three edges of the outer-face of Γ from Γ' . This gives a drawing of T'_i in an embedding as in Definition 18. As shown in Lemma 4.4.2 we need at least a width and height of $2i - 1 \geq i$. Similar as in Lemma 4.4.3 one can show that T'_i in this embedding needs $4i - 3$ bends. The three deleted edges form a triangle and need at least 1 bend, so we get a lower bound of $4i - 2$ bends.

So we may now assume that the outer-face had degree 4, and, after possible renumbering, that the outer-face is $\{v_{3j-3}, v_{3j-1}, v_{3j}, v_{3j+1}\}$ for some $1 < j < i$. Removing v_{3j-2}, v_{3j-1} and v_{3j} would split T_i into two components. If we add the three vertices to either components, then we get a copy of T'_j and a copy of T'_{i-j+1} . Moreover, those two are exactly embedded as in Definition 18.

As shown in Lemma 4.4.2, T'_j in this embedding needs a width and height of $2j - 1$. Similar as in Lemma 4.4.3 one can show that T'_j in this embedding also needs $4j - 3$ bends. So T'_j and T'_{i-j+1} together need $4j - 3 + 4(i - j + 1) - 3 = 4i - 2$ bends. Also, the needed width and height is at least $\min\{2j - 1, 2(i - j + 1) - 1\}$, which is smallest for $j = \frac{i+1}{2}$ and then equals i . \square

Figure 4.28: T_i drawn in a $(\frac{2}{3}n - 2) \times (\frac{1}{3}n + 3)$ -grid with $\frac{4}{3}n - 2$ bends.

Since T_i has $3i$ vertices and is triconnected, we immediately get the following theorem.

Theorem 4.16 We have a lower bound of a $\frac{n}{3} \times \frac{n}{3}$ -grid and $\frac{4}{3}n - 2$ for planar drawings of triconnected graphs.

We conjecture that the drawing of Figure 4.28 is optimal, i.e. that T_i needs a $(\frac{2}{3}n - 2) \times (\frac{1}{3}n + 3)$ -grid.

Biconnected graphs

We do quite the same for biconnected graphs as we did for triconnected graphs. For biconnected graphs the combinatorial embedding is not unique. However, for the class B_i this does not make a difference: even though B_i has many different combinatorial embeddings, all give the same planar drawing, except for possible renaming of the vertices and edges, and the choice of the outer-face.

Lemma 4.4.13 B_i needs a width and height of i and $4i$ bends in any planar drawing.

Proof: The proof is quite similar to the proof of Lemma 4.4.12. Assume that B'_1 had the vertices $\{v_1, v_2\}$ and that we obtained B'_i by adding the vertices $\{v_{2i-1}, v_{2i}\}$. The outer-face can either have degree 2, 3, or 4. If the degree is 2 or 3, one shows easily that we need at least a width and height of $2i-1$ and at least $4i$ bends. So assume the degree of the outer-face is 4, and, after possible renumbering, that the outer-face is $\{v_{2j+1}, v_{2j}, v_{2j-2}, v_{2j-1}\}$ for some $1 < j < i$.

Splitting the graph at v_{2j} and v_{2j-1} , we get a copy of B'_j and a copy of B'_{i-j+1} , both embedded as in Definition 19. As shown in Lemma 4.4.4, B'_j in this embedding needs a width and height of $2j-1$. Similar as in Lemma 4.4.3 one can show that it also needs $4j-2$ bends. So B'_j and B'_{i-j+1} together need $4j-2 + 4(i-j+1) - 2 = 4i$ bends. Also, the needed height and width is at least $\min\{2j-1, 2(i-j+1)-1\}$ which is smallest for $j = \frac{i+1}{2}$ and then equals i . \square

Figure 4.29: B_n drawn in an $(n-1) \times (\frac{n}{2} + 2)$ -grid with $2n$ bends.

Theorem 4.17 *There is the following lower bounds for planar drawings of biconnected graphs:*

- G a multi-graph: $\frac{n}{2} \times \frac{n}{2}$ and $2n$ bends.
- G simple: $(\frac{n}{2} - 1) \times (\frac{n}{2} - 1)$ and $2n - 6$ bends.

Proof: For B_i we have $n = 2i$ and are done by the above lemma. Now obtain the simple graph \bar{B}_i by subdividing one of each of the double edges. We have the same grid-size, two bends less, two vertices more, and a width and height of $\frac{n-2}{2} = \frac{n}{2} - 1$ and $2(n-2) - 2 = 2n - 6$ bends. \square

We conjecture that the drawings of Figure 4.29 is optimal, i.e. that B_i needs an $(n-1) \times (\frac{n}{2} + 2)$ -grid. If that were true, then \bar{B}_i would need an $(n-3) \times (\frac{n}{2} + 1)$ -grid.

Connected graphs

Nothing is known about lower bounds for non-biconnected graphs that would be any better than those for the biconnected graphs. Some better bound on the number of bends was obtained when we found lower bounds for non-planar drawings.

So we get as lower bounds for simple connected graphs a grid of width and height of $\frac{n}{2} - 1$ and $2n - 6$ bends (Theorem 4.17). For multi-graphs, we get a lower bound on the width and height of $\frac{n}{2}$ (Theorem 4.17), and for the bends we get a lower bound of $\frac{8}{3}n$ (Theorem 3.10). Finally, for graphs we get a lower bound on the width and height of $\frac{n}{2}$ (Theorem 4.17), and for the bends we get a lower bound of $3n$ (Theorem 3.10).

Chapter 5

Conclusion

We conclude with a summary all results obtained in this thesis. We give various tables for the various different classes of graphs. We provide the citation of the first article that gave this result. Everything without citation is a new result shown in this thesis. We also mention some possible points of improvement and open problems.

5.1 Nonplanar graphs

		Connected	Biconnected	Triconnected
Simple Graphs	Upper Bounds	$(n-1) \times (n-1)$ [B] $2n$ [B]	half-per. $\frac{7}{4}n - 2$ [PT] $2n + 2$ [B]	half-per. $\frac{7}{4}n - 2$ [PT] $2n + 2$ [B]
	Lower Bounds	area $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ [V81] $\frac{11}{6}n$	area $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ [V81] $\frac{10}{6}n$	area $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ [V81] $\frac{18}{13}n$
Multi- Graphs	Upper Bounds	$(\frac{4}{3}n - 1) \times (\frac{4}{3}n - 1)$ $\frac{8}{3}n + 2$	$(n+1) \times (n+1)$ [B] $2n + 4$ [B]	– –
	Lower Bounds	area $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ [V81] $\frac{7}{3}n$	area $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ [V81] $2n$	– –
With Loops	Upper Bounds	$(2n-1) \times (2n-1)$ $4n$	– –	– –
	Lower Bounds	area $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ [V81] $3n$	– –	– –

Table 5.1: Overview of the results for non-planar drawings. The first number denotes the grid-size, unless otherwise specified. The second number denotes the number of bends.

A lot of work remains to be done for non-planar graphs. In particular, better lower bounds for the grid-size would be desirable. The method of counting crossings is not a very good idea, since it does not take into account grid-points that are needed to draw very long edges. Can a better constant be achieved by considering the minimal sum of edge lengths? What are other methods to prove lower bounds on the grid-size?

One would expect that for non-planar drawings there are smaller drawings and fewer bends than for planar drawings. However, the bounds achieved here are significantly better only for simple biconnected graphs. They are in fact worse than for planar graphs for triconnected graphs. So improvement should be possible.

How can the algorithm for planar triconnected graphs be transferred to non-planar graphs? There exists something similar to the canonical ordering for non-planar graphs as well (Kant, private communication). However, we have not found a way of defining a marking and embedding the vertices, such that the crucial Invariant 3 (the left incoming edge goes either to the right or upward) can be proved.

One interesting area is non-planar drawings of planar graphs. Leiserson [Leis] showed that a grid-size of area $\mathcal{O}(n \log^2 n)$ can always be achieved. We provided lower bounds for the number of bends. Is it possible to draw planar graphs in a non-planar fashion so that the number of bends is reduced significantly?

5.2 Planar graphs

		Connected	Biconnected	Triconnected
Simple Graphs	Upper Bounds	$(n-1) \times (n-1)$ [BK] $2n$ [BK]	$n \times n$ [St] $2n+2$ [BK]	half-per. $\frac{4}{3}n+2$ $\frac{4}{3}n+4$
	Lower Bounds	$\frac{n-1}{2} \times \frac{n-1}{2}$ $2n$	$\frac{n-1}{2} \times \frac{n-1}{2}$ $2n-6$	$\frac{n}{3} \times \frac{n}{3}$ $\frac{4}{3}n-2$
Multi- Graphs	Upper Bounds	$(\frac{4}{3}n-1) \times (\frac{4}{3}n-1)$ $\frac{8}{3}n+2$	$(n+1) \times (n+1)$ [BK] $2n+4$ [BK]	— —
	Lower Bounds	$\frac{n}{2} \times \frac{n}{2}$ $\frac{7}{3}n$	$\frac{n}{2} \times \frac{n}{2}$ $2n$	— —
With Loops	Upper Bounds	$2n \times 2n$ $4n+2$	— —	— —
	Lower Bounds	$\frac{n}{2} \times \frac{n}{2}$ $3n$	— —	— —

Table 5.2: Overview of the results for planar drawings. The first number denotes the grid-size, unless otherwise specified. The second number denotes the number of bends.

For planar graphs, the results on the number of bends are quite good, the lower bounds are within a small constants of the upper bounds for all but two cases.

Work remains to be done for the grid-size, in particular for connected graphs. Is it possible to reduce the grid-size in the algorithms? Or to find better lower bounds? Are T_i and B_i drawn optimally in Section 4.4.2? What are methods to prove this?

Is it possible to reduce the grid-size and the number of bends by splitting the graph into triconnected components? What is a general merging scheme for that, what are the conditions that have to be put on the cutting vertices?

5.3 Plane graphs

One open problem for plane graphs is to show that Kant's algorithm for triconnected graphs indeed always produces a $(\frac{2}{3}n+1) \times (\frac{2}{3}n+1)$ -grid. Another problem is the question whether Theorem 4.7 can be extended to graphs that are not biconnected, i.e. whether the algorithm of Tamassia [Ta87] embeds a graph in a grid that is at most as large as the one achieved with CONN-PLANE.

		Connected	Biconnected	Triconnected
Simple Graphs	Upper Bounds	$\frac{6}{5}n \times (\frac{6}{5}n + 1)$ $\frac{12}{5}n + 1$	$n \times n$ [St] $2n + 2$ [BK]	half-per. $\frac{4}{3}n + 2$ $\frac{4}{3}n + 4$
	Lower Bounds	$(\frac{6}{5}n - 2) \times (\frac{6}{5}(n - 1) - 1)$ $\frac{12}{5}(n - 1) - 2$	$(n - 1) \times (n - 1)$ $2n - 2$ [TTV]	$(\frac{2}{3}n + 1) \times (\frac{2}{3}n + 1)$ $\frac{4}{3}n + 4$
Multi- Graphs	Upper Bounds	$(2n - 1) \times (2n - 1)$ $4n - 2$	$(n + 1) \times (n + 1)$ [BK] $2n + 4$ [BK]	– –
	Lower Bounds	$(2n - 3) \times (2n - 3)$ $4n - 4$	$(n + 1) \times (n + 1)$ $2n + 4$ [TTV]	– –
With Loops	Upper Bounds	$(2n + 1) \times (2n + 1)$ $4n + 4$	– –	– –
	Lower Bounds	$(2n + 1) \times (2n + 1)$ $4n + 4$	– –	– –

Table 5.3: Overview of the results for plane drawings. The first number denotes the grid-size, unless otherwise specified. The second number denotes the number of bends.

Other than that, the results are quite satisfying for plane drawing: almost everything is optimal, and if it is not optimal, then it is within a small constant.

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